

London South Bank University

Faculty of Business

**Why and how do workplace library users
utilise library space for non-library
activities?**

Morag Clarkson

Student number **3127702**

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Abstract

Aim

The aim of this study is to critically analyse the reasons why NHS staff go to a workplace library to carry out activities which are not specifically related to the library. Qualitative one-to-one interviews were conducted with a convenience sample of library users to discover themes around usage at Croydon Health Services NHS Trust

Context

Recent research into public libraries suggests that library use supports well-being and social capital. There is little literature relating to NHS library use and well-being or social capital. Generally, research into NHS libraries focuses on the services provided e.g. a clinical librarian service or access to online resources. Many measures of usage are quantitative rather than qualitative metrics. However, public bodies have recently published qualitative value measures of public library use. A similar qualitative measure could be used to critically evaluate usage of the NHS workplace library.

Results

It emerged from the study results that participants found the workplace library positively impacted on their wellbeing and was used as a third space in the workplace, in addition to providing a full library service. Respondents valued the quiet, non-judgmental environment which

allowed them to think, disengage and see colleagues in a different way. The enforced quiet within the library space offered respondents protection from having to interact with colleagues, unless they wanted to. Participants were able to access IT, complete their work and read in an environment of calm which gave them a break from demanding and noisy work departments in the trust. Participants valued the unique contribution the physical library space gave to the organisation, frequently referring to it as the only place in the trust where they get the quiet space they needed to recharge themselves for the demands of work. They also valued uninterrupted access to IT equipment and free wifi. Participants reported feeling that reading, study and learning were not valued in the trust and that reading evidence-based information for practice, and unwinding was seen as “skiving off”. Senior managers, who rarely took breaks during the working day valued the physical library space as somewhere they go and be “on duty” and visible yet be in a relaxing environment. Senior managers also valued that fact that if junior staff were not in their department, but were in the library they could be contacted and their managers knew where they were.

Recommendations

The research recommends that the value of the physical library space to all staff is embedded within the trust’s wellbeing agenda. The main purpose of the library is not to support wellbeing but many users come to the library for reasons related to wellbeing, therefore the library’s

development and usage should be supported as part of wellbeing at the trust. The physical environment should be welcoming, calm and quiet and employ library staff who are able to recognize the unique role the physical library space plays for users during their working day. Development and use of the library services should be championed at board level.

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Chapter one

- 1.1 Research context
- 1.2 Definitions
- 1.3 Introduction
- 1.4 Purpose of the study
- 1.5 Research aims and objectives
 - 1.5.1 Research question
 - 1.5.2 Research objectives
- 1.7 Value of research

1.1 Research context

“We shape our buildings: thereafter they shape us”

(Great Britain. Parliament. House of Commons, 1943)

Recent research suggests a significant association has been found between frequent public library use and reported wellbeing (Great Britain. Department for Culture, Media and Sport (2014, p.9). The report suggests that library users are able engage with both the library space and with the educational content of the library. The Arts Council (Arts Council England, 2014 Hypothesis 3 p. 8) suggest that there is also value in the library as an institution even for individuals that make no use of it (e.g. the library has a non-use value). The report further suggests that public libraries contribute to the maintenance of mental and physical wellbeing as well as to social inclusivity (Arts Council England, 2014 p.5). Research by Oldenburg (1999, p.149) suggests that aspects of the physical library also contribute to the

community by providing a “third space” which influences literacy, social relationships and ultimately wellbeing.

1.2 Definitions

Within the context of this research, third spaces are defined as public places on neutral ground where people can gather, interact and feel restored and at ease. Third spaces: promote social equality; offer support to both individuals and communities; foster democracy, and encourage tolerance, understanding and friendship. (Oldenburg, 2001 p.16). Mixing with different people encourages social relationships and networks, which build an individual’s social capital. Social capital has many definitions, but one that is relevant for this research is social capital as the connections between individuals and the trust that comes from them (Putnam 2000 p.19). These connections, along with things like quality of life and equality, influence wellbeing (Great Britain. Office for National Statistics, 2012). In its constitution, the World Health Organisation Health Organization (World Health Organization, 1946), defines health, which influences wellbeing, as “a state of complete physical, mental and social wellbeing and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity” (World Health Organisation Health Organization, 1946) This was expanded in 1986 to include “the extent which an individual or group is able on the one hand to realise aspirations and satisfy needs; and on the other hand, to change or cope with the environment” (World Health Organisation Health Organization, 1986). Libraries can support this vision.

1.3 Introduction

At a time when the provision of knowledge and culture is increasingly digital and screen-based, the value and importance of high-quality physical spaces and experiences is growing, not diminishing (British Library 2015 pg. 8)

Gorman (2000 p. 45) suggests that we need the physical library because we are human beings, and people need human help negotiating the online world.

The Common Libraries initiative encourages libraries to “evolve into sustainable platforms for the creation, consumption and exchange of knowledge and know-how in both physical and virtual spaces” (Chartered Institute of Library and Information Professionals, 2014(a), p.41). This highlights how libraries in some sectors are re-designing space and services to fit user demands. There is less research to show whether these trends are emerging in NHS libraries. In London, NHS libraries have a strategic steer at regional level from London Health Libraries (LHL) and nationally from Health Education England (HEE). LHL is a co-operative group of member libraries, managed by a strategic lead who is employed by Health Education England.

The generic role of NHS library services is outlined in “Knowledge for healthcare a development framework for NHS library and knowledge services in England” (HEE, 2014). LHL produces its own additional regional guidance for its members, based on HEE guidance. One strategic aim of LHL is “promoting physical libraries as attractive study and learning spaces for the whole health and care workforce” (LHL 2013) This aim neatly fits the research focus of this study which will critically examine why and how do workplace library users utilise library space for non-library activities.

1.4 Purpose of the study

At Croydon Health Services (CHS) the library service offers support to all clinical and non-clinical staff regardless of grade. The library is not, however, just the services it provides. The library is also a physical space. The purpose of this study is to critically investigate reasons why staff use the physical library space at CHS for non-library services, and to identify any perceptions of well-being and social relationships associated with usage which reflects current literature from public libraries and higher education libraries.

1.5 Research aims and objectives

1.5.1 Research question

Why and how do workplace library users utilise library space for non-library activities?

1.5.2 Research objectives

- For what purposes do library users use the CHS library and the spaces within it?
- Why do CHS library users use the CHS library space rather than non-library locations?
- How do CHS library users think their use of the CHS library contributes to their feelings of wellbeing?
- How do CHS library users think their use of the CHS library space contributes to developing and maintaining workplace social relationships?

Value of research

It is relevant to transpose the findings of research in other library sectors onto NHS libraries, as the services provided and skills and training of library staff from all sectors are transferrable. This research will add to the literature on NHS libraries and especially to explorations around the benefits to users of the physical space in NHS libraries. The qualitative methodology may expand the readership to HR or workforce development leads in order to:

- identify the gaps between organisational policy around wellbeing and evidence-based practice, and how it is actually applied to achieve trust objectives.
- produce recommendations for the library service as a tool to support the organisation's objectives for wellbeing, as well as supporting evidence-based practice
- resource the physical library space for the wider personal and professional needs of the users

This research may be interest to strategic library service funders at national and local levels and could be significant for both policy and practice for NHS staff.

Chapter 2

2. Literature review

2.1 Search strategy

2.2 Introduction

2.3 Social capital

2.4 The third space

2.5 Well-being

2.1 Search strategy

Searches on the LISA, HMIC, Medline, CINAHL, Health Business Elite brought back relevant articles about social capital and wellbeing research in the public library and higher education sector (see Appendix 1) There were few results for research into social capital and wellbeing in workplace or NHS libraries. LSBU databases brought back some results. Evidence was included or excluded and critically appraised using CASP qualitative checklists (Critical Appraisal Skills Programme, 2013) However, the main current sources of evidence about wellbeing and libraries have come from government and public organisations.

2.2 Introduction

There is a large amount of literature discussing library services. However, there is little published evidence investigating workplace libraries and in particular the qualitative benefits of the physical library space in the workplace. Research into workplace libraries generally, is limited. Spiller (1999) defines

'special libraries' or workplace libraries as commercial or government bodies that provide information to advance the goals of their organisation. The lack of literature about workplace libraries is endemic because they differ significantly in size, subject matter and type. As the workplace library exists to further the aims and objectives of the organisation so, commercial organisations do not wish to make available information about their activities. (Spiller, 1999 p. 63). The Public Health Responsibility Deal (Great Britain. Department of Health, 2012) highlights the workplace as a vehicle for promoting public health and improving health and wellbeing of staff. Workplace libraries may not be seen as a resource specifically to promote well-being however, as Lewis (1998 p.192) identifies, libraries make information more available to people, communities and organisations than if people are left to find information themselves which makes organisations more productive and improves the quality of life in communities. Workplace libraries have a role in engaging staff with the organisation by increasing learning capability (Bennett, 2003, preface) As Gorman (2000, p.29) suggests, libraries exist to enable individuals to continue their education, become more knowledgeable and also to live the life of the mind in a place where all are welcome. The majority of literature about libraries is published in professional library journals and is aimed at library professionals. Publishing to a wider readership e.g. in management and human resources journals, may influence the promotion of library services and library space within organisations. There is significant literature about how libraries' delivery of their services is constantly changing and developing, driven by "disruptive" technologies, education and learning styles, user expectations and needs. The Victorian Public Libraries Strategic Framework 2030 (State Library of Victoria 2013, p.12) sees the future "creative" library as

a hub for creativity and learning, centrally located and containing creative and learning spaces that allow independent and collaborative learning. It is this constant development of the library space to fit user needs which makes it a popular destination for users to carry out non-library specific activities e.g. activities not specifically related to the library collection: reading own resources, learning, internet surfing, attending events or simply connecting with the community and developing social relationships. The design of the library space, and the services it provides, are inseparable, as space will enable or disable services (Watson, 2013 p.xiv)

2.3 Social capital

Coleman (1988) defines social capital as the processes and experiences of non-elite groups. It is the pattern and intensity of networks among people and the shared values which arise from those networks which builds social capital. As Putnam (2000, p.19) suggests, it is the connection rather than the isolation of individuals that is important, and which breaks down hierarchies and silos. In the workplace, the pressure to achieve targets can make staff retreat to their silos rather than encouraging them to work collectively (Ward, 2014 p.xviii) The workplace library offers a physical space – a third space - for staff to get away from their departments and use the environment for either for work or relaxation. Mixing with colleagues in different situations improves social capital. Studies suggest that through increasing social capital, public libraries contribute to enhanced community cohesion and thereby to healthier communities (Arts Council England, 2014 p.3) As a safe, equitable and non-market social space, libraries increase a sense of identity and raise

awareness of rights and benefits (Museums, Libraries and Archives, 2004, p.vi). Information flows through social capital networks, and this helps staff achieve their goals. Further, psychological and biological processes can be brought to the surface and examined within the neutral library physical space (Putnam, 2000). Wavell (2002) suggests libraries have social impacts which relate to an individuals' personal development specifically around challenging and changing attitudes, development of self-esteem and the acquisition of skills. The physical library allows users to interact in a different way to work or home, providing the third space for social capital to be built.

2.4 The third space

Oldenburg defines the third space as somewhere inclusive which expands possibilities, allowing people to see each other in a different context (Oldenburg, p.24). In the workplace there are few third spaces for staff to retreat to. As a physical environment, Line (1998) suggests that libraries have traditionally been designed to fit printed materials, and users have had to fit around this. Information technology has changed user demand, expectations and the type of services libraries are expected to provide. Using the library as a third space can offer staff an opportunity to become a "different person" during the working day by allowing a change in environment (de Botton 2006 p. 13) We have many different selves within us and our moods and emotions can be influenced and rebalanced by our environment (de Botton 2006 pg. 121) It is well accepted that space and design quality impacts on staff's working life (Jensen, 2005). Without adequate design, places and services

may work but not be user friendly. This can limit users' interaction with them. Investment in a well-designed library environment will dictate the services that are available within those spaces. As community spaces become increasingly important (Arts Council England 2014 p. 6) the library's safe, neutral space, has a natural role as a community learning hub providing opportunities for people to try out new experiences with minimal risk. (Arts Council England 2014 p. 24) The option to "dip in a toe" and experience learning in a non-hierarchical environment supports wellbeing. The government suggests that economic growth requires places that promote good health, and that planning should facilitate place-based innovations that could improve health and wellbeing (Public Health England, 2013 p. 5) The development of the library space fits into this agenda.

2.5 Wellbeing

The concept of the library has been described as a safe home for people in a complicated world Sieghart (2014). Libraries by the nature of their collections, staff and information skills training, support learning and education both in the workplace and in the public library sector. The benefits of education and learning are clear: people with university degrees have better health and longer lives than those without. People with higher socioeconomic position in society have greater life chances and more opportunities to lead a flourishing life (Marmot, 2010 p.3). However, the wellbeing of all members of the community needs to be considered. The UK Government Sustainable Development Strategy (Great Britain. Environment, Food and Rural Affairs 2005 p.17) suggests that a strong, healthy and just society can be achieved

by meeting the diverse needs of all people in existing and future communities by promoting personal wellbeing, social cohesion and inclusion, and creating equal opportunity for all. Libraries in the NHS have a role in achieving this objective, as they provide an accessible, non-hierarchical space for all staff, which can support wellbeing and personal and professional development. The Croydon Health Services Employee Health and Wellbeing Improvement Framework (Croydon Health Services. 2013 pg 3) (Appendix 2) is centred around one of the Trust's five "Here For You" promises, *You feel cared for* (Croydon Health Services, 2015) and sets out a framework to improve staff motivation and morale by improving wellbeing

Chapter 3

Research methodology

- 3.1 Introduction
- 3.2 Study Design
- 3.3 Sampling
 - 3.3.1 Sampling type
 - 3.3.2 Inclusion and exclusion criteria
 - 3.3.3 Sample Size
 - 3.3.4 Recruitment
- 3.4 The Interview
- 3.5 Ethics
- 3.6 Analysis
 - 3.6.1 Themes
 - 3.6.2 Thematic analysis summary
- 3.7 Limitations of research
- 3.8 Related research
- 3.9 Potential problems with research

3.1 Introduction

There are multiple methodological approaches which could have been considered to address the objectives of this study. To answer the research question, descriptive research exploring why and how library users utilise library space for non-library activities was required. Qualitative research has been used to answer the research question. As a term qualitative research covers a wide range of approaches and methods, with no one single accepted way of carrying it out. The focus of the study is to explore why users choose

to come to the library instead of going elsewhere. The perceptions of library users were essential to inform this study. Therefore interviews were conducted within the interpretivist tradition, which is also called the social constructionist position. The population of this study is Croydon Health Services library users. As the researcher works in Croydon Health Services library and has access to library users in a professional capacity, convenience sampling was undertaken. A convenience sample is described as one that is easily available to the researcher (Bryman, 2012, p. 201). However, there are problems associated with this type of sampling, namely that the results cannot be generalised, as it is unclear that the sample is representative of the population. (Bryman, 2012, p. 210)

3.2 Study Design

The method for generating data is through one-to-one interviews as this allows a comprehensive understanding of the issues being explored (Punch, 2009). The interview transcripts are then analysed for commonly occurring themes.

3.3 Sampling

3.3.1 Sampling Type

In order to address the objectives of this study, a sample population was required. Convenience sampling is the least rigorous means of sampling, as the selection is from the most accessible participants. Such a selection does not represent any group apart from itself and so the findings cannot be generalised to represent the wider population. Approval to interview library users was sought and given via email by Croydon Health Services, from the

researcher's line manager (Appendix 6) Library users were invited to take part in an interview by letter (Appendix 7). Those who agreed to participate were asked to complete a consent form and agree a mutually convenient time to be interviewed. Although the participants were known to the researcher it was important to establish a new relationship with the participants to ensure rigour during the research process. In order to do this, and to establish an open working relationship with participants, the procedure for the data collection was outlined before each interview. It was reiterated that information was confidential and that comments made during the process would not impact on the relationship between the researcher and the participant once the research was over. This ensured good communication and made the research process person-centred. The participants were made aware that they could withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences to their relationship with researcher, the organisation other library users or staff. Throughout the process, the participants were free to discuss any aspects of the study with the researcher. A mutually convenient time and location for a face-to-face interview was arranged. From this convenience sample 100% of participants consented to being interviewed.

3.3.2 Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Within this convenience sample of library users, the selection criteria for participation in the research study was specifically refined by the process of purposive sampling which is also known as judgment sampling. This is the most commonly applied sampling technique (Marshall, 1996) and requires the researcher to actively select the most productive sample to answer the

research question. For this study, library users who were observed to use the library often and who were known to the researcher were chosen from a population targeted specifically because of particular characteristics that they possess (Creswell, 2007). There was no discrimination regarding gender or job role. All participants were adults. The researcher sought an equal mix of genders and job roles - both clinical and non-clinical in order that the results could be gathered from as wide a population as possible.

3.3.3 Sample Size

Qualitative research does not require large numbers of participants to validate the findings. As this study is not trying to generalise or extrapolate findings to the wider population, a sample size of 14 participants seemed acceptable to adequately answer the research question by being large enough to show the emergence of themes in response to the interview schedule. When the participants had been selected they were required to give their informed consent to participate in the study.

3.3.4 Recruitment

In order to enrol potential participants, they first need to be identified and then given information about the research study. This was done via a written letter (Appendix 7). This process gives an opportunity to ensure the participant is interested in taking part and determines whether they can commit their time to the interview process. A response rate of 85% was achieved.

3.4 The Interview

The interviews were conducted individually and face-to-face in the library manager's office. This is a natural setting and although this could bias participants' responses, due to the fact they are answering questions about the library space, it was the most private and convenient location for participants to come to. An interview schedule (Appendix 8) was used, enabling the participants to fully describe their perceptions and experiences while being guided through the topics necessary to address the objectives of the study in a consistent manner. The interview schedule contained probes to prompt participants, if further clarification of the questions were required. The Occupational Health Manager was also interviewed in her office, as her opinion on library use in the context of wellbeing was valid, although she is not a library user. She agreed to be identified as the Occupational Health Manager, rather than being anonymised. All the interviews were recorded digitally and on tape, for which consent was obtained from all participants (Appendix 7).

3.5 Ethics

All efforts were taken to ensure that the researcher was unbiased in the treatment of research participants. The researcher ensured that no harm or risk came to participants during the research process. The researcher ensured that participants could not be identified either personally or by reference, unless they have given their consent to this. Personal information relating to participants was kept confidential. Ethical consideration has been observed throughout this research process. This can increase the validity and

reliability of research data (Bowling, 2009). Ethical approval for this study was sought from Croydon Health Services. This was granted by the researcher's line manager (Appendix 6). Participants agreed to one-to-one digitally recorded interviews. Participants' anonymity, confidentiality and consent to take part in one-to-one interviews was gained via a signed declaration form (Appendix 7). Ethical approval was not required from IRAS as only Croydon Health Services staff who used the library were to be interviewed, but it was obtained from LSBU. Prior to the interview, it was emphasised to participants that they could withdraw from the study at any time without consequences to their relationships with library staff, other staff or with the organisation. The emphasis on these issues was particularly important as the participants were regular library users and they needed to feel enabled to make negative comments if required.

3.6 Analysis

3.6.1 Themes

A qualitative method of analysis was undertaken for this study. The interviews were recorded digitally and on analogue tape, and transcribed verbatim. An analytical technique was then used as a method for ordering and synthesising data (Ritchie 2003, 219 as cited in Bryman, 2012 pg. 579) The interview schedule was pre-coded around the main research objective themes – space, wellbeing and social relationships. The transcripts were read many times. A coding framework (Appendix 4) was developed from frequently occurring words and phrases in the transcripts. This process of segmentation

enabled the reduction of the data to a manageable form (Gilbert, 2008 p.340)

The interview schedule defined this coding. As new themes emerged in subsequent interviews, these new segments were then looked for in preceding interviews to see if they occurred. The verbatim responses were added to the text research report to illustrate certain points (Gilbert, 2008 p.340) The analysis revealed themes and concepts. These themes e.g. commonly occurring words or phrases, allowed a true comparison and contrast between the interviews, so enabling a methodical analysis of the textual data. Similar themes were clustered together in order to reveal meaning and significance around the core themes. Underlying patterns were then explored and were interpreted within the research question.

3.7 Validity and reliability

Bias can occur from poor methodology, especially as qualitative research is a dynamic process and variable data is collected. Bias can also come from the interviewer, with misdirected probes. It is important for the researcher to find out whether the participant has any particular beliefs about the research topic which may bias their views (Selltiz, 1964. p.245 as cited in Silverman, 2011, p. 171)

3.8 Limitations of research

This is a very small study which relies on a population known to the researcher. Convenience sampling was undertaken which is not the most reliable method of sampling. Therefore the results cannot be extrapolated to the population of the study. The results will be very specific to the organisation.

3.9 Related research (see Appendix 12)

3.10 Potential problems with research

The data collected in this study will be subjective. The interview setting (in the Library Manager's office) may bias participant's responses as the interviewer is the Library Manager. Respondent's subjective replies may not be substantiated by "facts", they may simply be perceptions. However, this research aims to critically examine subjective perceptions as well as collecting objective data such as frequency of library use. Participants may not wish to divulge exactly why they are coming away from their work environment e.g. staff who work in an open plan office or who share an office with someone they don't like may frequently come to the library to work to get away from colleagues and / or office noise. Admitting this may be seen as admitting to a weakness or as having an inability to cope with the work environment. The researcher ensured there was a supportive, trusting relationship with participants in order to guard against this being an issue for participants.

Chapter 4

Research results

4.1 Participants

Fourteen Croydon Health Services library users agreed to participate in the study. They satisfied purposive sampling criteria and were therefore included. Two participants did not turn up for their interviews due to unforeseen changes to work commitments. Time constraints meant that the interviews could not be rescheduled. One digital recording was corrupted and was not transcribed. The analogue back-up was recovered, so data was taken directly from that recording and added to the results. The twelve participants who were interviewed consisted of 6 females and 6 males. 7 participants were clinical staff and 5 were non-clinical staff. Demographic data of participants is presented in table 1.

Table 1: Demographic of participants

Participant number	Male	Female	Clinical	Non-clinical	Attended interview	Did not attend interview
010		X	X		X Digital recording corrupted	
020		X	X			X
030	X		X		X	
040	X		X		X	
050		X	X		X	
060		X		X	X	
070		X		X	X	
080	X		X		X	
090	X			X	X	

100	X		X		X	
110		X	X		X	
120		X	X			X
130		X		X	X	
140	X			X	X	

4.2 Thematic Analysis

In order to synthesize the data it was necessary to look at themes that emerged around similarity, difference and frequency. The interview schedule attempted to group together questions: library as a third space; library's contribution to wellbeing, and library's contribution to social relationships in the workplace. The interview schedule consisted of a mixture of open and closed questions, measuring attitude and / or behaviour. Crucial to the research objectives was the ability of participants to critically analyse and verbalise their perceptions and feelings about utilising the workplace library space. In order to address the objectives the following questions were asked of the participants:

1. Do you have any strong beliefs about workplace libraries?

Eleven participants responded positively to workplace libraries, all saying they felt strongly about workplace libraries, describing them as "needing to be accessible" [participant 040], "essential" [participant 03, 090], "necessary" [participant 070, 090], "valued" [participant 010] and "important both professionally and personally to encourage development" [participant 030].

"Professionally it is absolutely essential for us as a resource. But personally for me probably the environment that I can come to sometimes and hopefully not interfering with other people (sic)" [participant 030]

"I think they are a really important part of the NHS as it is a learning organisation" [participant 140]

"When members of my family and myself started having [health] problems, it was a good place to sit down and read and take it all in quietly, so yeah, I think they're essential to be perfectly honest." [090]

"I think every workplace should have one particularly big organisations like the NHS and other statutory services. Employers talk a lot about personal development and reflection and yet if they haven't given people a space to do that in or a space to access either computers or journals, books to build on their knowledge or reflect on their knowledge then the two don't really fit."

[Participant 050]

Three participants [080, 060, 090] felt that the workplace library was a place to relax and reflect.

"I use the library personally as respite from the hectic work of the ward, and more importantly for a reflection on my activities. I use the library as it's more relaxing, although I am reading and trying to find information on the internet, I could find other places, but the library is the best, more relaxing to be in".

[Participant 080]

"It's a quiet calm place to come and de-stress yourself amongst a whole lot of knowledge around with a number of books that you find" [participant 060]

"it's the place where you can get some solace from the hustle and bustle of your workplace" [participant 090]

One participant [participant 110] had no strong beliefs about workplace libraries

2. Why do you come to this library?

Table 2: Reasons for coming to the library

Why do you come to this library	Participant
Time to collect thoughts	010, 140
Because i won't get bothered / interrupted	070, 110
It's convenient	010, 090, 100
It's important managerially	010
To read	030, 040
To relax	030
Because it's quiet	040, 050, 110, 140
Welcoming	030, 050, 140
For the coffee	040, 050
For the IT facilities	060, 070, 080, 130
For resources - journals and books	130
For privacy	070

The most frequent reason given for coming to the library was because it was quiet and calm and this calm, quiet environment enabled participants to carry out activities: relaxation [participant 030] reading [participant 040] time to

collect thoughts [participant 050] [participant 010], “hot-desking” [participant 050], not to be bothered by anyone [participant 070], internet surfing [participant 070], use the library as a retreat [participant 050], privacy [participant 070], quiet contemplation [participant 090], it’s convenient [participant 010] its important managerially [participant 010] The environment offered an opportunity for reflection.

3. What do you use the library for?

Participants’ responses were equally divided between those who used the library for relaxation (coming at break times) and as a place to work.

Table 3: Use of the library for work or relaxation

Work	Relaxation	Both
participant 050, 060, 100, 110,130, 140	participant 030, 040, 070, 090	participant 080

“I don’t have a work base within the hospital so this in effect becomes my hot desk and also a bit of a retreat for me when I just need to collect my thoughts. If I go and sit on a ward or try and sit in someone else’s office I don’t get the quiet time for me as someone will ask me a question or think they have to engage when actually all I want to do is to sit and be quiet.” [Participant 050]

One participant stated that they did non-work related study in the library at break times (e.g. related to their hobbies and interests, or they researched health issued [participant 090]

“For quiet contemplation and to learn what’s wrong and what can be done, when, like I had both knees replaced, was a really good place to come and ask people if they could put you onto the literature, and if they had an article that they knew about, that they could get it for you, and you had a lot more understanding about what was going to happen to you when you were under the surgeon’s knife, which I found extremely helpful” [participant 090]

The participants who always worked in the library didn’t consider coming during break times. Participants who came during break times enjoyed reading in the library: equally either their own books and newspapers or library books and journals

One participant [050] came to the library during working hours as there was constant demand for access to PCs on the wards for immediate patient care:

“I am very conscious of pressures on our computers systems so if I’m not doing something that is acutely needed within that environment for a patient on that ward, I’d rather come away and feel like I am compromising other people’s work space.” [Participant 050]

Of those participants who worked in the library, the space was most frequently used as a source of managerial and clinical information, to gain *“latest research, unusual conditions, evidence to support practice and NHS changes”* [participant 010]

The next most frequent use was as an area for thinking

Table 4: Self reported reasons for using the library

What do you use the library for	Participant
Reading	030
Study	030
Thinking	030, 050, 090, 110
The art exhibited	040
Coffee	040
To work	050, 060, 130
For information – journals and books	010, 050, 060, 070, 090, 140
For meeting rooms	060
For the IT / technology available	050, 060, 070
It's friendly in the library and I have made friends there	060, 100

4. Why do you choose to come to the library rather than go elsewhere?

Table 5: Reasons for choosing the library over other spaces

Why do you choose to come to the library rather than go elsewhere	Participant
I won't get disturbed / bothered	030, 050, 090, 110
It's quiet	030, 040, 050, 060, 090
It's comfortable	030, 110
To read	040
To study / learn	040, 140
It's welcoming	050
For the coffee	050
To work / Hot desk	050, 080
For the IT / technology available	060, 070
It's calm	060
You can stay as long as you want / need	070
Library staff are supportive / helpful and appreciate time pressures	070, 080, 100, 130

When asked why they came to the library rather than going elsewhere, the main themes that emerged apart from the quietness, was the helpfulness of

library staff and that there was an unspoken understanding that they wouldn't be "bothered" in the library, as talking is discouraged; Participants valued this as the only place in the Trust where silence was guaranteed, and they were happy to come some distance across the trust site to have some quiet, uninterrupted time. One participant [110] stated that they also liked going to the chapel for a similar, quiet environment.

"Because there aren't very many spaces, I would go somewhere like the chapel because that's another quiet space where there aren't too many people, but the chairs aren't so low and I like the sense that the chair is comfortable when my legs are down all the time. And other places, if you got to the main restaurant, they don't want you to sit in the main restaurant in the comfy chairs which are lower unless you've bought something. You can go down to main reception, again, there's sort of more standard chairs there, I have gone down there as a different space as well, but I tend to feel I ought to be buying something, so the library is quiet. I think in general, you're not interrupted about work, although one time I was, someone spotted me and it made me think twice about where I sat in the library because they spotted me, and they came in and told me to do something and I went back and I immediately did that thing for that person because they were senior and that individual never did anything with it, and I thought, that's interesting"
[Participant 110]

Other alternative places to go in the Trust instead of the library were the chapel, staff member's car, the canteen, public seating areas around the Trust and staff rooms

"I could have sat in the car which I have done for several years, but um, once somebody had told me how quiet and relaxing it was up here (in the library), before they left the hospital, I thought I'd give it a go and I've been doing it for about four and a half years now. For quiet, you can't get it anywhere else, literally, if you go to a canteen or whatever, it's just hustle bustle, and people walking past saying "hello" or whatever...The only time I interact is when people are next door (in the library training room) and they start making use of their mobile phones or they're just talking too loud, so you just say "I'm closing the door because I don't want to hear what you're talking about" [participant 090]

"...some staff never have any kind of breaks because we eat at our desk, and I get to half two in the afternoon and I think I need to just try and relax a little bit for a few minutes, so I come in and do that, and I appreciate the way you don't interrupt me...there's that sense that...and I see other people in here and I would never ask them about work matters, you know, I wouldn't even interrupt them to say "hello" unless they looked at me and smiled and quietly said "Hello" If I went to the main restaurant...that's kind of like a space where people can come up to you and interrupt you and say "I'm really glad I've seen you here, can I just mention X or Y?"

[participant 110]

Staff came to the library rather than going elsewhere because it was seen as a *"ready resource a space already stocked with books and journals and knowledgeable staff who could help get information quickly"* [participant 010]

One participant spoke at length how admin staff didn't have access to any staff rooms or common rooms. As she worked in an open plan, shared office, the only place she found any quiet was in the library. [participant 070]

"This (the library) is just I guess, our space and you know you can go to the canteen and have a quiet cup of coffee but somebody will join you. You can stay here (in the library) for the day; you can stay here for 5 mins. It is that kind of area. Unfortunately I work in a reception so eat my lunch, answer the phone, do my work in this area and I don't have half an hour where I can switch off. One of our former consultants came in and we asked him how things were going at his new hospital. He said it was great except they don't have this common room (that they have here) and it really makes a difference so imagine how me and my colleague feel (the common room is for consultants only). In Outpatients there was a common room for the admin team but it really wasn't a space away from work because the other admin staff would be there and you were obliged to make conversation. In the Training Dept there wasn't [one] until we moved into a bigger area which has a lovely common room with a TV but again you are sharing it with colleagues. Retinal screening wasn't great because your retinal screening room was also your break room so in those areas I wasn't getting away from work, department or from patients. If patients saw you sitting in there with the door open for ventilation there would be lots of huffing and puffing – "why can't you do me now because I'm early and I can see you sitting in there". And you did you felt obliged to stop your lunch. You felt you didn't have that right to have a break. ...here (in the library) no one can judge, you are in a mixed

environment, mixed as in lots of different staff, not your colleagues who will defer to asking you things....Sometimes with common rooms it is a very selfish environment because the upkeep and the cleanliness of it will go back to me. I feel they (the consultants) are very lucky with the space they have. Now the consultants can have utter privacy” [Participant 070]

Some participants used the library to hot desk either because they had no designated work space or because “*clinic rooms were booked or busy*” [participant 010]

5. Last month, how many times did you come to the library?

6. How long do you stay on average?

The length of time spent in the library and the numbers of times participants came to the library in the previous month varied and is presented below in table 6

Table 6: Frequency of participants’ visits to the library in a month and length of stay

Frequency of participants’ visits to the library in a month and length of stay	≤ 1 hour	≥ 2 hours	≥ 3 hours
≥ every day	040, 030, 090, 100		
≥ twice a week			
≥ once a week			
≤ once a week			

≤ twice a week	140	080	060
≤ once a month	110		
≤ twice a month	010, 070, 130		
Varies	050		

Some participants reported coming to the library at the same, regular time whilst for others it varied

7. Do you come during working hours and / or during your breaks?

When asked whether they used the library during breaks or in working hours there was a split between those who viewed the environment as a place of relaxation and those who viewed it as a place of work (see table 3). Some participants described it as both a place to work and a place to relax. One senior staff member stated that senior managers didn't take breaks [participant 010]. Another senior staff member stated that he was mindful that being seen reading could be seen as "skiving" by some colleagues.

"I'm a senior manager and I am quite happy to take a seat on the comfy chairs in visible full view of whoever is walking by and they can see I'm looking at a journal and I'd be more than happy to be challenged on that because I will give a clear and concise reason. If others want to see it as skiving I will give them a clear and concise reason that I am not and thus far no one has asked me but I am mindful of that. I suppose that is why I sometimes deliberately sit in a prominent position because it is quite legitimate for me to be there. I do it in that way rather than hide away outside" [participant 140].

A breakdown of when participants used the library is contained in table 3

Table 7: Library use during breaks or working hours

Work	Relaxation / Break	Both
participant 010, 050, 060, 080, 130, 140	participant 030, 040, 070, 090, 100	participant 110

8. How would you describe the library environment / physical space?

Participants most frequently described the environment as quiet. This was valued by users. The results of descriptors are given in table..

Table 8: Descriptors of the physical library space

Descriptor	Participant
Quiet	010, 030, 040, 050, 060, 070, 130
Calm	010, 030, 110
Orderly	010
Welcoming / Attractive	010, 050, 130
Comfortable	030, 060, 130
Place to study	030, 060
Multifunctional space	040
Friendly	080
Helpful	080
Comforting	090

Reflective space	090
Peaceful	110, 130

Participants also frequently described the library environment as calm, comfortable and welcoming. The fact that coffee and food could be consumed in the library was positively commented on.

“it’s nice being able to have a drink, because libraries in the past have always been ‘non fluid environments” [participant 050]

The library computers and desk space were mentioned positively, as was the opportunity to sit on the sofas and put their feet up

“I come in and take my shoes off and I put my feet up (on the sofas) ..I could sit in my office, I could lower my chair a bit, I could shut the door and the team wouldn’t disturb me, but I’d be surrounded by all this work I’ve got to do and the computer screen, it’s not the same, it’s that different physical location and quietness.

And you can have space around you, because there are less people in here in a way, so you feel a sense of space, and it just takes you away somehow from the intensity and strain of what you’re working in, even if you actually haven’t got people physically at you all the time, um, it feels like that. [participant 110]

Comparisons were made to similarities between the library environment and the chapel:

"It's comforting to have a place that...I suppose it's a bit like the chapel, you can go there, just relax and gather your thoughts, but you can do that in a totally different way here.

Recently, I found out my brother needs two heart valves and it was comforting to know that you could go to a section, pick out a book, and you could read what it was about, and it was just so quiet you could think about what you were reading and how it would affect you after, you told them because they're scared stiff, but if you can get a photocopy or whatever, pass it on, it's just a natural process." [participant 090]

As participants were using the space for different reasons e.g. work or relaxation they viewed the space differently.

"And it is nice to have the sofas there although I haven't had the time to sit on the sofas but I appreciate that a lots of other people do and it is nice to come in and I suppose it is a bit of a challenge for me too 'cos it makes me think "maybe I should be sitting on the sofa reading a paper or a fiction book" you know using it as a less work space and more of a relaxation space"
[participant 050]

Participant 060 described the environment as formal.

"Erm it is not informal, it is quite formal in that sense. As I am saying that I am trying to explain what I mean. It is not a place where I can come and just say hello, how are you because it is very quiet." [participant 060]

Participant 130 felt in was an environment that allowed a degree of freedom

"It is somewhere you feel you can come and just be yourself and not be watched and you have a bit of freedom" [participant 130]

Participant 040 described the environment as intimate

"It's quite an intimate space. It isn't a large library. It has got multifunctional elements to it. I've also noticed that in the past you've put books out for foreign speaking members of staff which is very good and very interesting. I suppose I know it's a hospital library but I've noticed you have other books."
[participant 040]

Two participants described the environment as being able to be improved: participant 010 and participant 140. Participants stated that improvements in the physical space would encourage collaborative work.

The physical condition of the building that the library is housed in was commented on:

"I visit libraries at the weekend and spend typically half an hour in there choosing some sort of material and also looking at the newspapers and the like. I've got a real empathy and endearment towards libraries; I think they have a valuable, societal benefit. It's a really good idea that libraries exist and not, if you like, become extinct because I know a lot of libraries are because of the changes in technology. You only have to look at the environment (here) to say well, if you were to score it let's say, out of 10, er you would probably be hard pushed to give more than 5 out of 10. It's got to affect the way people use the space. Is it fit for purpose?..... we've got basins on the floor ready to collect water (from leaking roof) which are a health and safety hazard. 5 out of

10 is pushing it really. We do need to make the environment safe, we do need make it fit for purpose, and we do need to bring it up to the 21st century. There is a lot more that can be done really.” [participant 140]

9. Do you bring your own books, journals, magazines, reports or do you use library resources – books, journals whilst you are here?

Participants use of own resources and library wifi was linked to their reason for being in the library e.g. for work or relaxation. Participants who were using the library for relaxation most frequently brought their own resources e.g. a newspaper or a book. (see table 8)

Table 9: Use of own or library resources

	Bring own resources	Use library resources	Use both
Work		010, 050, 060, 080, 110, 130, 140	
Relaxation	030, 040, 070, 110		090

“I do both to be honest, a young lady lends me her paper every day, but when I need to go and use the library, for magazines books whatever, I know they're readily available. Probably once a week I'll read the journals”.
[participant 090]

Participants who were using the space purely for work tended to use the library resources, apart from bringing their own data for inputting.

One participant felt he should be using the library resources

“If I come in here I want to be seen to be using library resources rather than bring my own in because it will almost be, I'm not saying this as a slight, I am thinking why would I want to be bringing in a Guardian or a Times let's say and sit and read those in here when they have not been provided by this service” [participant 140]

10. Do you use library PCs or do you bring your own device?

Participants who were working in the library used the library PCs and their own devices, if they had one. Some participants using the library for relaxation used the library PCs, or they did not use any IT equipment. See table 9 for use of library PCs or own device.

Table 10: Use of library PCs or own device

	Use library PCs	Bring device	Use both	Use neither
Work	010, 050, 080, 100, 110, 140		060, 130	
Relaxation	040, 070			030, 090

“I have an office within an office, it's quite a small office, I've got no complaints, I'm grateful for it, but it feels...some of it's almost psychological, you can be interrupted at any point, phone can ring, e-mails are coming through, even if you try and switch e-mails off, um, hours and hours and hours of that. It's a lot for the brain to cope with, so if I can come here, it's almost as if I can sit and look at all my e-mails and try and read through some of them and clear some of them, respond to them, but I don't have all the other sense of stimuli coming in quite the same way, so that may be a help for me to concentrate on a job that needs doing.” [110]

11. Do you use the library wifi?

Only two participants used the library wifi

Table 11: Use of library wifi

	Use library wifi	Yes	No
Work		060, 130	010, 050, 080, 100, 110, 140
Relaxation			030, 040, 070, 090

“That is a no, because we know we're being charged, I know it's only pounds, but it's the principle of the matter, whereby, at St George's, it's completely free throughout the whole hospital, NHS & medical school and it really is a place of learning, so why are we paying to use a service when we're actually working here, so it's out of principle, not out of costs, I really think, and my colleagues say the same, why are we paying for something that we work here, and now we go to another hospital, everything's completely free (library wifi is free to library users)” [participant 100]

“No, on occasion I come into you and have talks to you about it, about using it, I think it's one area that I haven't really mastered that I would like to and that would be to be able to come in here at any time and be able to look at webinars, there's lots of material available, especially in the States, where I have a membership of the professional body” [participant 110]

“I think it is a massive draw for me to use the (library) wifi especially to do a lot of uploading of videos to YouTube and things that we can't do in the normal trust, you know high security trust internet uploading things.

(How did you feel when you couldn't access the library wifi [because it had gone down?])

The only other place is at home. I end up doing it in my own hours at home so that is a bad thing. It's just disappointing because I know when it works its brilliant. It is a brilliant space to use it in. Just to add that the wifi anywhere else in the trust that you have to pay for so this is the only free source of wifi in the trust” [participant 130]

One participant highlighted that some staff had not received adequate IT training and didn't know how to use PCs and other devices, or wifi.

“No, simply because we've not been trained to use them downstairs, and they've only just after twenty years decided that we can have a PC.

They didn't see any point in us having one before, now we've got one, I tried to get onto it last week and it wouldn't even let me in”. [participant 090]

12. What would make you come to the library more?

Table 12: Drivers to increase library use

Driver to increase library use	Participant
More time	030, 090, 110
Released to study	040
More PCs	050
Later library opening hours	070
Access to more information	080
Innovation	110
Events	130
Geographically closer to my dept	130
Guaranteed wifi access	130
The “wow” factor	140

Not having enough time during the working day or during breaks was the most frequently cited barrier to increasing usage.

“Not having to work so long, to be perfectly honest” [participant 090]

“I think it is a long way to come over here for my break, that is half my break gone when I get here. If there were more events I would definitely come to the library and that might spill over into my work life” [participant 130]

13. How could the Trust encourage you to use the library more?

Table 13: How the Trust can encourage library usage

Driver to increase library use	Participant
Advertising / marketing	030, 040, 050
More study days	040
More PCs	080
Later library opening hours	060, 070
Record of attendance in the library for users' managers	080
Bigger space	090
Events	070
Geographically more central location	070, 090
Management understanding of demands related to studying	100
Investment in the physical library infrastructure	100
Having enough staff on the wards to release others to study	110
Steer from the Board / Directors	140

Respondents cited better advertising and later opening hours as drivers that would encourage library usage. Some participants stated they would come more frequently if the library were closer physically to their work department. One participant suggested that staff didn't know about the library [participant 050]

"It may sound crazy but I'm not sure people really realise it's here. It's in the PGMC and it's stuck out of the way. I'm not sure you can place it above

reception or something but I think for lots of staff it is a long way from their working space so popping in for 10 minutes if you are on Fairfield 1 or you are in the Eye Department, it is quite a walk down here. I think location might improve its usage. People kind of pass it by on the way to training or somewhere else". [participant 050]

A larger space was cited as a positive draw to more library usage, in a more central location [participant 090]

"I think you could do with a slightly bigger library, where it's situated isn't the ideal situation. You could probably do with one of the old type of wards that's long and not really used any more to give you the extra space, but you really could do with being on the ground floor." [participant 090]

The need for more computers was also cited by participant 050 as a reason that she would come more frequently

"The times when I have come in and then gone away again have been when all of the computers have been taken and there about 4 / 5 in that corner and I notice that it is being used very regularly by people like me who don't have the space anywhere or like me, have found their MDT rooms just too frantic"
[participant 050]

Participant 060 stated that longer opening hours might encourage usage.

Participant 060 discussed how having library staff present in the library increases the relaxation element, as they are responsible for the space, not those using it.

“Right now it closes at 5pm but I am guessing that a lot of members of staff work a lot longer than 5pm. With that I think having library staff as well as access to the space after 5pm it’s nice. It will make you feel as though you are not the only one here and someone else is responsible for this place and I am here to get what I need whereas when you are on your own you become responsible for that place so again not very relaxing.” [participant 060]

Longer staffed opening hours and events were cited as a positive incentive to come to the library more often. The library is staffed 8.30am – 5pm

“Probably later opening hours. Sometimes I have to leave work early to catch the 5pm thing (the library closes at 5pm) and get locked out because I don't have key access. I would consider the 24 access but didn't know” [participant 070] (24 hour access to available via a programmable key)

“Perhaps the trust putting talks on here, they would utilise the space so there was I don't know, yoga sessions over here instead of it being in the gym. Some entertainment, talks or perhaps a drive that is going on in the trust”. [participant 070]

Other participants cited reasonably priced coffee as a draw, and the lack of support for studying as a barrier [participant 040]

“I have used the tea and coffee machine a couple of times. It's very good value. You can't get a tea or coffee cheaper than that in the hospital.” [participant 040]

“To be perfectly honest I don't think coming to the library is encouraged in our department in a way that it perhaps was. I think the emphasis so much now is on do your job and there is very little scope for study unless you really make your own effort. I think that is a shame in a way. We used to have designated study days. We were encouraged to take those but those days are gone now.”

[participant 040]

Participant 100 also cited the lack of top management support for studying as a barrier to increased library usage:

“I don't think higher management understand what staff of all levels here require, they just think, it's a PGMC or a UGMC, that's great, but I think they'd have to use it, or be on an actual course to understand what we require, because a lot of what I require, isn't available to me, so that is one factor. I only come here because I know the people, the PCs, and you guys are willing to help me, you're always here to help me, so I think really it's more of an issue not of staff, yes there could be more staff, because you guys are stressed, but the staff are, what can I say? They're perfect, it's really the infrastructure what goes into the library which is the biggest problem, and again, going back to what I've said before, it is just what everyone says.”

[participant 100]

Participant 040 also talked about the lack of support for studying and about more effective marketing of the library space

“More study days, to encourage learning I suppose. I think advertising that kind of information about the library would be useful so that people would come in and be more likely to dip a toe in” [participant 040]

“More spaces (work spaces and having to book library spaces)” [participant 010] were cited as a further reason to come to the library more.

Participant 140 cited the need for Board engagement with the library

“I think there needs to be more of a steer, there needs to be an engagement by the Board, clear statement within a policy document, within the annual report, within the Board agenda to say what a valuable resource if they haven’t already done it.” [participant 140]

One participant stated that it would be useful to have a dedicated area in the library where patients being treated with a specific disorder could come to download information onto the trust supplied ipads they had been given to enable them to better communicate. Library has wifi and library staff would be able to help with any IT problems and patients would be removed from a clinical setting, where there are no quiet spaces. [participant 010]

14. Do you think it would be useful if trust policies on the subject of well-being recommended spending time in the library to encourage personal and professional development?

Table 14: Should library use be embedded in CHS wellbeing policy?

	Yes	No	No strong preference
Should library use be embedded in CHS well-being policy?	010, 030, 040, 060, 080, 090, 100, 110, 130, 140		050, 070

Some participants agreed that adding library use to trust policies would be useful.

“Yes, absolutely. In the NHS staff wellbeing is not always taken into consideration. I think it would be a very positive thing if this trust said in a policy that you can spend a specific amount of time in the library. The line manager would then know where that person was.” [participant 010]

“Most definitely yes however I would probably use a different narrative which is not how much time you want to spend in the library but what a valuable resource it is, this is what it offers and then some examples of how it is helped other professionals. We do so much around the physicality of people but the emotional needs are important and they need to be met and arguably the most important resource we have is the library to do that.” [participant 140]

“it is changing that culture into studying and reflection” [participant 030]

“so much of our profession is evidence based and to have that sort of time to look at what the evidence is, I don't think you can do that now” [participant 040]

“For sure, I mean, one of my profession requirements is to have the CPD and part of it is how much you spend time exploring literature and reading journals and so on, I think because of the financial constraints these days, I think we have to share these resources” [participant 080]

“in terms of it helping my wellbeing, I come here to help my wellbeing, so when I feel I've had seven / eight intense hours, this can help my wellbeing because it's just some place I can just sit and process things in a different way, maybe not work related, so that's important for my well-being. Helps manage stress, helps cope with stress. Everybody should be doing personal and professional development. Much of it, to be fair, can be accessed from a computer and that's the way you're expected to access it, but speaking personally, it's quite difficult to do it when, at your work environment, you're under so much pressure in the here and now.” [participant 110]

“I know the trust has to document the work we do around wellbeing for staff so are we not feeding into that already? There is something about the environment of the library, it is not corporate it is more stimulating and somewhere where you come to get away. For the environment we are in it is a very unique space.” [participant 130]

Other participants commented that staff didn't read trust policies and that putting library use into policies would not encourage usage.

"I am not sure how many people would think "ooh I must read the wellbeing policy and it says I must spend some more time in the library" during their busy day." [participant 050]

"Even though I think there is a wellbeing policy somewhere, that probably in all honestly a lot of us don't read or do anything with. Erm, I think the trust needs to invest a lot more in the wellbeing of staff anyway. I think this is one of the spaces where wellbeing can be incorporated in a working day because it is calming. In comparison to work and what we have to go through in work, busy, full on and some of the areas are really busy, this is a perfect space for wellbeing because it's the opposite of that" [participant 070]

Many participants mentioned they thought there was a "library type" who would seek out and use libraries, whether the trust encouraged staff to do so or not. This was described as "natural selection" rather than something that could be enforced.

"Er, wellbeing. I think again with libraries, its natural selection. People of the character and type of person that will use libraries and you see the same people here all the time using – the doctors, the nurses.." [participant 030]

The participants who described themselves as "library types" then went on to relate how they used their local public library and enjoyed using libraries in general.

Participant 060 was very enthusiastic about embedding library use into the trust well-being policy:

“Yes I think absolutely, absolutely. I haven’t read the trust policy of wellbeing and I don’t know what is there, but if it isn’t then I think it should be there. Right now I don’t think I can, unless I have a meeting in the library I don’t think I will come from my working PC to this office and just sit down because I want some “me” time here. I don’t think I can say very openly in my team that anybody has ever said anything that “I am quite tired, I am quite stressed and I just want to come and sit in the library for a while” because I am not sure how people will react to that so yes if that become part of the trust policy then you can. It’s the same thing like if you have flexible working hours and you leave at 3pm because of child care you can get up and leave because that is your right and you can do it whereas coming to the library, I don’t have a right to do that so it is always open to criticism and comment” [participant 060]

Although the question was about well-being, participants linked wellbeing to study and knowledge. The lack of support for studying was cited again as an issue:

“Definitely, yeah. I mean the whole study issue. I mean so much of our profession is evidence based and to have that sort of time to look at what the evidence is, I don’t think you can do that now.” [participant 040]

15. Is the way library staff behave towards you important?

All respondents agreed that the way library staff behaved towards them was important. However, they expected a high level of customer care from all Trust staff.

16. Is the way library staff behave towards you different from other staff in the trust?

Some respondents felt there was a difference:

“Yes definitely. Sometimes you are not aware that things exist so if you are looking for something, I suppose people know their stuff and people can point you in the right direction so that's helpful” [participant 040]

Participant 140 also felt staff were different in the library

“I think I'm pretty well placed to give a view about that. I currently do audits of all the departments so I know exactly the nature of those departments. The library is all about not being rushed, not being fazed, the staff don't rush me. Contrast that with an audit or inspection where it is for a precise amount of time, it is much more time bound whereas coming to the library, you know, I'll come to library for as long as I need. I have poor encounters on the wards but return nonetheless. Time and pressure factor into things. People change under pressure and without resource. Contrast that to here, sense of calm and wellbeing. [participant 140]

Participant 070 highlighted that in her experience there was a difference in how library staff treated users, in so far as they treated all users the same regardless of hierarchy:

“I think they are quite respectful here. And whether you are a doctor or admin I don't feel there is a differentiation in treatment whereas in other areas of the trust as an admin person you are sometimes not treated equally because managers, doctors and nurses are treated on a higher level and that is also receiving it too from doctors, nurses and managers, so here everybody is a library user, end of. That is one of the reasons that keeps you coming back”.
[participant 070]

17. Would a poor encounter with library staff dissuade you from visiting the library again? If so why?

Poor encounters with library staff were rare and library staff were frequently described as helpful [participant 010] friendly, welcoming, non-judgemental and able to find unusual information [participant 010] which was valued by users.

Some respondents stated that a poor encounter with library staff would dissuade them from using the library again, whilst others said it would not; they would simply talk to the library manager if they felt library staff had been rude.

"Yes I would be quite irritated and wouldn't continue using the service"
[participant 010]

"No. Because it's become part of my life, and we are so hectic downstairs 24/7 basically, I've found recently, that when I go home, your brain is still active and it doesn't actually switch off, so when you can come to a place like this..if you can shut your eyes for ten minutes in an environment like this, a lot of strain and stress just seems to ebb away that you don't seem to be able to do while you're at work or while you're asleep at home, it's a totally different environment". [participant 090]

Some participants did highlight specific behaviour traits in library staff, which meant that poor encounters were rare:

“Yes I mean again I do think it comes back to the library being a very quiet and calm place. It is very much reflected the way the staff behave in the library as well. You can see them extremely calm in the way in the way they ask in help, there is not rush whatsoever, and there is no rush, not in a negative way it is absolutely in a positive sense and they are very friendly, they want to help and they go out of their way to help us in what we want whereas if you go to other areas people are always busy, running and rushing so if you are asking or seeking help it comes in that form, rushed or quickly, so you can feel that stress in that environment and again I think it is that de-stressed environment that helps I guess” [participant 060].

Participant 010 also agreed there was a difference *“because of the nature of their job they are able to take time and reflect themselves on what you need. When they ask me about what exactly do I need that expands my thinking which is really helpful. There is a dialogue with them” [participant 010]*

18. Does your Manager support a learning environment within the workplace where the sharing of knowledge and skills is encouraged?

There was a split between those participants who reported that their manager supported a learning environment and those who felt their manager did not support a learning environment. The frequent theme that emerged was that there was a general lack of support for professional development.

Table 14 shows how many participants felt their manager supported a learning environment

Table 15: Manager supports a learning environment

Yes manager supports a learning environment	No manager does not support a learning environment	I don't know
010, 030, 050, 060, 130	040, 070, 100	080, 090, 110,140

“No idea. My relationship with my line manager has always been quite distant and I'm not sure if this is in their mind or not” [participant 110]

“There is no agenda but I am sure when it comes nitty gritty, with the direction of the trust, the training, education, interactions, it would be encouraged” [participant 080]

“They don't but they do encourage my self-development so maybe management need to be promoting the library more and engage with them more about the resources available. I mean only recently I found out just from chatting with the library manager about some things that you do in the library which I was totally oblivious to and some of that was on staff wellbeing and since then I have definitely taken books out that are of interest to me. I think you don't remember the library is here unless you've got reminders to use it. I don't how you feel about this but I sometimes think that if you are seen to be in a library just reading a book that you are seen as skiving and the fact that it is very essential in your role to be researching or picking up a book and reading especially as some users use it as a rest area it does reinforce that the library is not somewhere where you do your stuff you do extra stuff outside your job”. [participant 130]

"No.(Do you think your Manager should?) Yes" [participant 040]

"My manager didn't, she actually deterred, because she didn't want to spend money, and we all got very frustrated. It took me forever just to get on my course and it's wasted some people's time when they didn't even have the opportunity, luckily for me, but once the manager left, things started rolling. My new manager, yes, she's great, she bent over backwards, forever grateful for that, so yeah." [participant 100]

"He [our Manager] is certainly keen for us to research and be reflective in our work." [participant 050]

"Yes less than it used to be because of err, staff shortages and the more demands of work. There is less training for in-service training" [participant 030]

"I've got a new director so I don't actually know what he really thinks about that. The culture of the organisation, are we a learning organisation? We might say anecdotally that we are but where's the hard evidence to support it?" [participant 140]

"I haven't got a clue. I'll be perfectly honest, I've never had a manager turn round and say, other than what you have to do for courses to keep your wages...I've never had one that has turned round and said, "I think this would be an advantage to you". Like the computers, they didn't want us to basically have a computer because that would put us on the next grade". [participant 090]

19. Do you have personal objectives in mind when you use the library?

Most participants reported that they had personal objectives in mind when they used the library. However, this was clarified by some as being personal objectives related variously to work and also non-work activities. Therefore it was difficult to specify whether the objectives were personal or professional as they blurred and personal became professional and vice versa e.g. *“to increase my learning and knowledge”* [participant 010]

Participant 050 saw personal objectives as relating to work:

“Absolutely. I couldn't do my job without accessing (the library). I couldn't stay clinically within the requirements in terms of time of entry of data and stuff if I didn't have the library space here when all the other spaces are taken. Foolishly I have told other people about it and I get there will be no spaces left! Others, like me who don't have a desk space within the hospital and desperately trying find somewhere to sit” [participant 050].

“I think I am coming here to meet my professional objectives. And maybe if it becomes part of the trust policy I probably could meet some of my personal objectives.”[participant 060]

Participants who weren't studying didn't see themselves as having personal objectives

“I’m not doing it (using the library) for an area of study. I’m not doing any dissertation or private study.” [participant 040]

Some participants simply saw the library space as somewhere to unwind.

“Just to unwind. As I say, there’s two or three people that you interact with as you come in, you acknowledge they’re there, you obviously say “Hello” to the library staff, but it’s just to unwind” [participant 090]

20. Have you ever used library’s fiction collection, books on prescription collection or other resources for your own personal development, not relating to your work?

Some participants had used the self help books and the fiction collection.

Table 16 details which participants had used the wider library collection

Table 16: Use of fiction collection and books on prescription collection

Have used fiction / books on prescription collection	Have not used fiction / books on prescription collection	Didn’t know about fiction / books on prescription collection
030, 050, 060, 070, 080, 090	010, 040, 100, 110, 130, 140,	

Self help books were popular from the wider library collection [participant 030, 060]

“A few of the self help ones I’ve looked at. They are quite interesting because they relate to work issues. Things like Positive Outlook, Anxiety is another one.” [participant 030]

“Yes, I did use them just to see what is there and what my colleagues are reading and it would be great if you could have some information on how many of which publications are used”. [participant 080]

Participant 140 commented on the validity of having a wider library collection:
“Never used those. It raises the point though that who is the principle users of the library? And I know that all junior doctors for example they all have to do audit. They all should be doing audit and revalidation. Rightly or wrongly there might be a sense of it’s a university so we need to be clear in that what’s that about. Is it about medical and nursing colleagues principally?” [participant 140]

Some participants did find the wider book collection useful

“Yes. I haven’t used books on prescriptions, but I have used the other library books as well. I’m not a particularly fiction person, so I do find, if I haven’t got something to read, you’ve got that piece of the library you can got to and find something that’s worth reading, even if you just read a chapter or two a day, it is worth acquiring” [participant 090]

“I never realised there were books on prescription, I’d noticed there were lots of books on depression and things like that and I wondered why there were so many of them.

No I’ve picked them up because I’ve never struggled with things like depression and they didn’t particularly attract me those books, and I’ve noticed the fiction, but I’m just too busy to read fiction, but I have noticed it with “ooh, that’s interesting, some fiction”, but life doesn’t allow fiction.”

[participant 110]

“I would be too embarrassed to be honest. But I think it is great you are doing that for health and wellbeing. I probably wouldn't take them out because of the lack of confidentiality.

The fiction too I probably wouldn't to be honest. I have a kindle; I download everything on the kindle. I don't tend to carry books around with me”

[participant 130]

21. Do you find the library a social environment where you can meet colleagues on a different level from other places in the workplace?

Respondents most frequently stated that they didn't see the library as a social environment, due to the fact that it was a place for quiet rather than talking or collaborative working.

Table 17: Library seen as a social environment

Yes	No	No strong preference
030, 040, 090, 100	010, 050, 060, 070, 080, 110, 130, 140	

“The environment is such that is quiet and they just sit down and do what they need to do. So I don't think this is the place you can network with people. That is not what I think this place is for. This is where you network with the books. That is how I see it. And if you have to network with people then you go outside the library and network with the people there. If you know someone then you smile, but you are free to walk away. There is no expectation that you should be talking to that person”. [participant 060]

“People should not really use the library as a social environment, especially when they whisper that's fine, beyond that it gets very irritating” [participant 080]

“Well at the moment, you've got a radiographer out here and you've got somebody from the path lab and they're interacting, you do get an awful lot of nurses, even nurses that have retired that come in and do voluntary work or whatever, are keeping up with whatever's going on by spending an hour or two a week in the library”. [participant 090]

Participants accept and value the fact they didn't have to interact in a social sense in the library.

“I don't regard it as a social environment, I almost come here to be alone” [participant 110]

“I don't because it isn't an area where you can talk” [participant 130]

“I know when I have been here there will be people that I know and we exchange some pleasantries but we get on with our work because it's not the place to have a long conversation. It is unfair on other users. Even the people I say hello to are a lot calmer here too. You see a different side to people. I've seen people fall asleep. That is how calming it is”. [participant 070]

“I don't come to be sociable in the library, and I like libraries to be quiet, I'm very traditional on that, so if I came in and found lots of people chatting, I'd find that quite off-putting because, especially where this library is located, literally round the corner is an open area where sometimes there's hot drinks

and things, and where you can go and chat to your hearts content".

[participant 050]

Participants 100 and 030 stated they thought the library was a social environment, but they didn't elaborate further. Participants 040 and 090 also felt the library was a social environment

"Yeah I mean I do meet people here. I'm really conscious of the fact that you are not supposed to talk in the library. I've seen work colleagues here occasionally." [participant 040]

"Yeah, I mean, you can actually talk to doctors where you couldn't...Where we used to have the social club, if you felt like having a pint after work, you could go in and physically sit in the same room as a consultant and you'd end up talking to one another, the same thing is similar here, I've never met a consultant or doctor that wouldn't say "Hello" or wouldn't enquire how you are and whatever" [participant 090]

"There are people that I know in the library, so, like doctors I've worked with or other therapists who have come in and there's a kind of a nod "hello" and then we get down to business and people carry on with whatever they're doing, whether it's sitting on the sofa reading a book, um, and I've gone and got a journal out and I think "ooh hello" to a girl or whether it's a doctor who's desperately loading data like I am, who goes "ooh hi, nice to see you on the ward and then off we go, to our respective work" [participant 050]

22. Do you think using the library helps you achieve trust objectives, by giving you a thinking space?

Participants most frequently agreed that the library helped them achieve Trust objectives by providing a thinking space. However there were some participants who used it only for work and did not perceive it as a thinking area.

Table 18: Use of the library as a thinking space

Yes the library helps staff achieve Trust objectives by providing a thinking space	Do not use the library as a thinking space	No strong preference
010, 030, 040, 050, 070, 080, 100, 130, 140	060, 110	090

Two participants did not see the library specifically as a thinking space.

“Again I personally have not used the library for thinking space. I have used the library to meet my professional objectives so coming back to what we said earlier it is because I want to get the training done, it is because I can get the meeting room to talk to people or I can get the certain books to read, so I am doing it for that so the thinking time is not there at that time because once you have finished your purpose here you leave. But yes it would be quite nice to actually sit down and have some thinking time. In other areas of the trust, maybe if it is a nice sunny day then sitting outside on one of the benches near the chapel probably. But I haven’t used the library to do this” [participant 060]

“No, not directly, I think it probably helps the trust in a sense by helping people to cope and have the stamina to stay in the job, then the trust wants to retain its nurses, that’s good.” [participant 110]

“Reflection, informed reflection obviously is very important, and I think being in the library reflecting on patient care with access to standards and what other people do is a great” [participant 080]

“Yes definitely because if there is an article I want to read and it might take only 5-10 mins to read the article, I will deliberately come down here rather than stay in the work environment which you will be interrupted by something else” [participant 030]

One participant felt the library needed to go further to support thinking

“It does in that sense but I think it needs to do more”[participant 140]

“I’d say the trust has ticked a box in providing a space although it is undervalued and it isn’t incorporated in your working day.” [participant 070]

One participant didn’t feel engaged with Trust objectives

“Um, A lot of the trust objectives, I don’t actually don’t get round to using, because I’m not interactive with the patients” [participant 090]

23. Do you feel the library is part of the networks within the organisation?

Responses to questions 23, 24, 25 and 26 gave a measure of how widespread knowledge about library services were amongst participants. Staff who used the full library service e.g. to get articles and for literature searches were more frequently aware of wider networks and organisations that the library was part of. Staff who used the library only for relaxation were less aware of what services were available to them

Table 19: Library is part of networks within the organisation

Library is part of networks within the organisation	Yes	No	Don't know
	010, 030, 040, 080, 090, 100, 130	110	050, 060, 070, 140

“Yes, I do. It is always one of the things that when people start, you direct them and introduce them to the library. So it is an important feature.”

[participant 040]

“Definitely, because I see general doctors, I see nurses, I see midwives, I see administrators coming into the library and that's a very good thing, of course, when they go out of the library, they refer to these activities and thus will be part of the network.” [participant 080]

“Oh yes, you are very attached to education, medical, clinical groups more so than other staff groups so not so much admin. My previous roles have been admin and clerical and I don't think I came up here particularly” [participant 130]

“Regular people come here a lot, yeah” [030]

“I've made many friends through the library, so in a way, beside learning and gaining knowledge here, you also make friends here”. [participant 100]

“I think it's a totally necessary part of the fabric of the hospital, because without it, most of the doctors wouldn't get where they are today. The likes of me and other people like me, who need information, get a very good result by just being able to ask”. [participant 090]

“I've always, since I could read been a library user in my own community, so I kind of seek them out in a way, so, I'm not sure if I wasn't already a library convert how and when I would network it into my day, so I'm not sure”. [participant 050]

“Er.. yes and no about networks. I think the staff connect us here but I am not sure if other areas connect it well. Staff would know other people and who you were talking about. The staff are part of the organisation” [participant 070]

“Right now I think it is used more for the clinical people, for the clinicians, you know junior doctors and the consultants” [participant 060]

“I've no sense that you do, but that said looking at who is in the library I get a sense of who is coming in and why they are here. I get a sense that it's probably a spike in the matrix of people doing these postgraduate diplomas that might encourage them to come here. I know a lot of staff get management days in the wards” [participant 140]

Participant 010 felt the profile of the library had decreased.

“Not really. A few years ago the library had a higher profile” [participant 010]

“No, not particularly, It's not that I mean I don't think you're not part of us, I don't see you as part of the network in the sense of when I come in you're somehow helping me to network, because I think what I like is the separateness, and it's the separateness that's the attraction. In fact, you're quite convenient for my office, if you were in a different building, it might make it even better, but I don't think it would because I often want to go to the chapel and play the piano, but the distance of having to go outside stops me, so no, I like almost the sense of separateness”. [participant 110]

24. Do you feel the library staff know people in the Trust

The most frequent response was both that staff knew people in the Trust and that the Library Manager knows other staff in the Trust but respondents were not sure whether other library staff did [participant 010]

These results are displayed in the table below

Table 20: Library staff know people in the Trust

	Yes	No	Don't know	Library Manager knows people in the Trust
Library staff know people in the Trust	030, 040, 080, 100, 130	090	050	010, 060, 070, 110, 140

"I think people know the library manager's name really and people know, I don't think people know other members of the team unless they come in"
[participant 060]

"I know that you (library manager) do, but I don't know about your colleagues. That's because we chat informally about things and it's clear to me that you interact with different people and you do know people". [participant 110]

"Probably not as well as they could do, nor should do, because you're fairly isolated" [participant 090]

25. Do you feel that the library knows about other organisations that could support you in your development?

The most frequent response was that participants did know the library could support their development

Table 21: library knows organisations to support your development

	Yes	No	Don't know
You feel library knows organisations to support your	010, 060, 080, 090, 100, 130, 140		030, 040, 050, 070, 110

development			
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However several participants did not know if they felt that the library knows about other organisations to support development, as they weren't sure exactly what the library did.

"Erm, I haven't really explored that side, I don't know. I would imagine so because even through search engines you can see various journal and institutions that they're coming from." [participant 030]

"I don't know if you are or not. I wouldn't know that. Is it advertised? I didn't know there were links like that. I'm sure a lot of other people would be interested to know about it". [participant 040]

"I've not tested it out for that, it's not something I use it for, only so much as being able to use the internet here". [participant 050]

"Because I haven't asked for that I don't know but I am sure from when I have been sat outside at a PC that they will point people in the right direction". [participant 070]

"I'm not sure you do, but I'm not sure that's necessarily a right kind of assessment to make. You helped me get books for my masters, but that's all really, it's something about the space, the separate space that I think is the real mark for me". [participant 110]

26. Have you ever come across things you hadn't set out to find in the library?

All participants apart from one, had found things they hadn't set out to in the library

“No not really. I think on a notice board there are all these interesting stuff and I probably would have a wander around every time I come up here just to see what’s happening around the area. It would be helpful if things were highlighted more then I would be more likely to use the library more”.
 [participant 130]

Table 22: Have you ever found unexpected things in the library

	Yes	No
Have you ever found unexpected things in the library	010, 030, 040, 050, 060, 070, 080, 090, 100, 110, 140	130

“Yes. This is very helpful and it comes from library staff” [participant 010]

“Yes I have, I browse the shelves. There were a couple of books that I got and became so keen on I ordered another book after that so I have”. [participant 040]

“Yes, the thing that tempts me, which is awful, is the, where I sit to do the computer work, there’s a rack of changing books and themes, and I’ve often reached back and dipped into something...“Oh no no, must put that back”, erm, so yeah, that’s quite nice because of where it’s situated”. [participant 050]

“Yes I think I have done this a few times with the self help books I think. It isn’t that I came for a self help book but came for something else and then I see this nice book let’s say on stress management”.[participant 060]

“I’d say it was the books on prescription now. I’ve been here for years and it is only now I’ve started to stumble on. Whether that is for personal reason I am

unsure and I have sought them. It is great to see arts and medicine being represented here which I didn't think it would be. You'll start with one thing here and end up down another rack"! [participant 070]

"So often I come for something and I see something else, it's stimulating, it is appetising, it is almost like going to the high street to have some food and you would choose from different things to which you had not thought of initially". [participant 080]

"Yeah, the interactive bit with the fiction and the other stuff with other libraries, I did find that strange at first, but there are times when you just want a space and you don't want to be indulged in heavy reading, and it has to be said that the medical library is heavy reading to say the least, where light relief is enjoyed, greatly I think". [participant 090]

"Often in the past, not so much recently, I've picked up books about management and other topics, sometimes I've taken them and I haven't really read them, but I think they've kind of floated through my mind, maybe dipped into them briefly, so yes, especially if things aren't on the shelf but new books are out and visible". [participant 110]

"Yes I have. There have been times I have come in looking for, er books on a piece of research on something and when I was going through the hardcopy library, the sections, because the library is indexed in such a way you can find links to other resources and linked information in different parts of the library". [participant 140]

27. Have you ever asked / would you feel comfortable asking library staff about training on “modern technologies” e.g. social media Twitter, Facebook, apps, Kindle

Table 23: I would feel comfortable asking for social media training

	Yes	No
I would feel comfortable asking for social media training	010, 030, 040, 050, 060, 070, 080, 090, 110, 130	100, 140

“I hadn't even thought about it, but that would probably be a very good way of upgrading to be a 'silver surfer”. [participant 090]

“Yes, that would be lovely and very helpful and valuable. This training would be very useful but should be rolled out in a wider learning sense. People are enabled to have time to do this but it is controlled”. [participant 010]

“I would. Does the library have its own twitter account?”

(Yes we have. Are you a prolific tweeter?)

I do tweet I mean I have got a twitter account, I've been tweeting for some time. Do you have a Facebook page? (Yes we do)

I didn't know about technology drop-in so it's worth knowing the library does that”. [participant 040]

“Yes, I would always feel happy about asking. I've never asked because of time, I've got so much to cope with and so much to do I'm struggling, so I didn't want anything more to do”. [participant 110]

"I certainly didn't know those services were on offer and I know the trust 'Titters' and I remember someone saying to me "oh, you need to Twitter more, you need to put on when something really good's happened"

[participant 050]

"Yes probably that would be useful. I don't think that people generally think that they should come to the library to check that. People generally think that they would think of IT and then immediately think of 'they would not be able to help us' and leave it at that". [participant 060]

"Actually if I knew it was available I would because sometimes there is a fear with new technology. If I knew that resource was there I would probably ask for it.

(Do you feel that you know enough about what goes on in the library?)

No, I'm sorry to say it. I'd love a more informal session. IT are IT here. The sessions are not informal. So a drop in session which would take into account that, whereas IT doesn't, you have this amount a time, pop in when you can. People learn differently and I think the library would give a wider variety of learning styles". [participant 070]

Participant 100 didn't want social media training via the library and already knew how to use the technology, and would use other sources for that information. Similarly, participant 140 would ask family about social media.

"I would probably be more inclined to use family than ask. So, not necessarily. I know the trust has a social networking type policy stance" [participant 140]

28. Do you trust the library staff? If yes, why?

All participants responded that they trusted library staff.

"Oh yes, it never occurred to me not" [participant 010]

"Yes. I think there should be confidentiality all around the trust". [participant 040]

"I think so. I've been on the wards and heard nurses gossiping about some of the visitors. I don't feel that would happen here in that "so and so has just asked for this journal". None of that. This is the request, let me try and deal with it and off we go.

It's calming; there is no element of judgment. It is your time. You don't feel as though you are wasting trust time or money and staff giving me judgmental looks to that effect, no none of that". [participant 070]

"I've never found them anything other than trustworthy, and there are places in this place that do a similar sort of service that you think to yourself "Yeah, am I asking the right questions of the right person?" It's a nicer atmosphere here, I think a lot of things that go on in this place are down to atmosphere, and the people that are there are producing that atmosphere, I know you've lost half of your staff recently, but you've never stopped having that atmosphere where, even if they were stretched to the limit, you can ask something, and you come back with a polite answer, and it makes all the difference". [participant 090]

Participant 130 felt that *"there is no privacy and dignity in the library. Everyone can see what you are doing. It's quite open in the library"*[130]

Participants were asked whether they had any further comments, some of these included themes that the library was underused:

The library is an underused resource and with careful planning staff should use it more [010]

The library is a cost effective way of furthering people's knowledge and skills in a caring and supportive way [010]

Another theme that emerged in the comments was how the library was valued
"I really think the whole wellbeing thing, for those of us who know it's here, it is a valuable way to help wellbeing. That may not be why the library is here, but that's why some of us are using it." [participant 090]

Occupational Health manager and library use

As part of this research the Occupational Health Manager was interviewed. She was not a library user and so the interview schedule used for the other participants was not used. Rather, the research findings were presented to her and she was asked to comment (see Appendix 3 for Participant OH transcript)

A summary of her comments as contributions to policy are detailed below:

"We had a well-being group which unfortunately, about the time that I started in the trust, which is September 2012, the chairman left and we did have trouble finding a new chair.

We did get a new chair from one of the surgical teams, but due to pressure of work it was actually quite difficult for them to chair, and we couldn't get any other buy in, so basically, I was advised by my director, deputy director, that

there didn't appear to be an appetite for wellbeing at this time in the trust because of the pressure from, er, all other directions, particularly in respect to winter pressures and the recruitment processes that were ongoing and the fact that we were struggling to keep staff etc, the health and well-being agenda has fallen off the horizon, because I did rewrite the health and well-being improvement framework policy / guidance and there were some things in there I needed to update and I was advised basically not to worry about it at the moment. I just don't feel that they're investing in the staff in the way that they should and the only thing that they have invested in is the flu campaign..... there's no financial penalty for not investing in health and well-being."

It would appear that currently there is no board / director level input into the well-being agenda for staff. There is currently no well-being group.

CHS aims to support staff well-being via its well-being framework. In addition, London Health Libraries has a strategic aim of "promoting physical libraries as attractive study and learning spaces for the whole health and care workforce" (LHL 2013) Yet, there are no penalties for not providing either of these services. Stress is now the most frequent reason for staff sick leave at CHS:

Interviewer: I looked at the figures, which I think I got correctly about days lost due to stress last year, and that's the biggest absence reason...

OH Manager: Far overtaken musculoskeletal, used to always be musculoskeletal, was the top one, but it's not now.

Interviewer:...And from my limited view, which is very limited, I can see that people that are coming in, they're not coming in because they want to get a library book out, and that's what I'm trying to measure...

OH Manager: They need downtime.

I was in the process of doing an accreditation with the mayor of London on health and wellbeing but part and parcel of that is having a health & wellbeing improvement framework which we don't have..it wasn't ratified, the things that I wanted to put in it, expand in it, I was basically told to focus on other stuff, so, that's been a bit unfortunate, what I still plan to do before I go, is get the things that I want to get in, in and I'm very happy to add the library into it...

Interviewer...And do you feel that the health and well-being agenda is one of the first things that goes when times are difficult?

OH Manager: And yet, you've got Epsom & St Helier, I was talking to the occupational health manager there and the director of HR put a massive business case forward for them to have a whole new post just dedicated to health and wellbeing

Interviewer...That's great, has that gone through?...

OH Manager: Yes, it's all done, they've advertised the job.

I know it's a bigger trust, but it's all proportionate isn't it, and there isn't the appetite for that kind of...and I think it's penny wise and pound foolish in the fullness of time, because it's all very well saying "we've got an occupational

health department, that's it", but if you don't let me get on and do the things that need to be done, or I'm actually disabled from doing the thing that needs doing, and all I'm allowed to do is focus on things that are non statutory, like flu.....there are certain things that we haven't been able to do that have gone by the wayside, which is completely wrong.

This research suggests that the physical library space provides more than just a repository for resources and services. The value that stakeholders place on the physical library environment could be demonstrated within the trust wellbeing policies via case studies and examples of user experience. Details of how the library has supported personal and professional objectives of staff could encourage library use and so support the organization in achieving its objectives. Subjective, qualitative feedback is a powerful tool to reflect how the trust's staff think and feel and could be aligned with the trusts five "here for you" promises (see Appendix 9) and wider trust objectives (see Appendix 10) Participant OH described the reality of some staff members' working day:

OH Manager: *"I do worry about staff who do 12 hour shifts, there is no break for them, no restrooms like there was in the old days, no restaurant that will sell them hot food.....there's a cold hard chair in a dingy restaurant, there's no comfortable place to go and get away from it all, just let everything go...I don't use it (the library) because I'm lucky enough to have my own quiet space here."* [participant OH]

Chapter 5

Analysis and interpretation of research results and findings

5.1 Introduction

The research aim was to critically analyse why and how workplace library users utilise library space for non-library activities.

The three most frequently occurring segments (e.g. words or phrases) from the interviews, which occurred at least once in a reply were:

1 – quiet (29 times)

2 – read (25 times)

3 – IT (17 times)

During the interview, the context in which these words occurred was linked to the value placed on accessing them by participants. The interviewees highlighted within their responses other frequently occurring words which gave further context to their replies. The themes were not distinct but were linked. Quiet was valued because it enabled respondents to read, gave them a refuge from their work department and an opportunity to disengage with colleagues. Reading allowed them to achieve professional and personal objectives, study, deal with stress, manage information overload and learn. Doing this in the library added value to their sense of self, connecting people who were “library types”, regardless of job or clinical role. Participants chose to come to the library rather than go elsewhere as the library was frequently described as “the only space” where they could achieve what they wanted, and also relax. Quiet in libraries remains a key concept which is valued

(Zickuhr, 2013 p. 44) and is emphasized by Massis (2012). The literature offers further wellbeing benefits linked with reading and mental health, as well as links between literacy and health literacy which suggests that libraries contribute to the health prevention agenda (Arts Council England 2014 pg4) This study's findings reflect that user expectations are changing and linked to emotion. People want and need experiences that are emotionally satisfying: complex combinations of products, services, spaces and information. (Pink as cited in Brown 2008 pg.92) The theme of emotion is picked up by Link (1999) as he highlights that human intelligence and decision-making is often not rational, and is influenced by emotion. In the workplace there are few non-market driven, quiet spaces, available to *all* staff which are specifically able to support staff's emotional needs, apart from the chapel which the library was compared to. Libraries can also be the gateway to the internet for staff, who have limited access to IT on wards or in departments. The library can further be where they learn the skills to use the internet. (Museums, Libraries and Archives, 2004. p.5). The digital divide is a reality and many people lack IT literacy, confidence, technical ability, and social networks, despite having access to many online resources (Museums, Libraries and Archives, 2004). As Gorman suggests, the library allows the space for reflective learning and also provides privacy and equity of access which promotes democracy within the workplace. (Gorman 2000, p.173) The Arts Council reports that public libraries are trusted spaces, open to all, in which reading can be explored and information can be shared (Arts Council 2012)

Berkman and Glass, (2000) as cited in Dahlgren (2007, pg80) suggests that being connected to a community positively affects wellbeing. Where social networks exist so does social support, engagement and access to resources

Participant 030 illustrates this: “..everything's online now but the problem is that the human interaction is very important and the library does provide that environment to interact and exchange information a lot quicker than you can if you are just searching on the web”. [question 30]

Rather than brains being “computers”, humans are driven by intangible biological impulses. Humans are complex and do not naturally inhabit the world of digitized information (Link, 1999 pg181). Despite this, the library is often viewed purely as it's “digital by default” online collection, rather than the space it provides.

The themes that emerged from the research frequently overlapped, especially around the concept of the third space and wellbeing. The library as a third space supported wellbeing and the need for wellbeing dictated how the library as a third space was used. The concept of social relationships and networks revealed that the library gave the opportunity to escape from enforced social relationships and create new ones, either with oneself or with others, by mixing with different staff members in the library environment. The library space offered a certain “protection” to participants, allowing them to disengage from the demands of other colleagues and submit to the library environment of quiet, calm peacefulness. This enabled participants to focus and complete their work or to relax.

This is picked up by participant 090 “*Oh yes, pace is a lot slower (in the library), but you interact when you want to interact, you're not forced to interact and that makes a big difference in the minimum time that you've got for yourself*” Participants valued this as a benefit of using the library space.

Table 24 shows the most frequently valued themes to emerge.

Table 24: Most frequently occurring themes relating to value of library space

Reason for use	Theme
Participants value the quiet library space for both relaxation and as a work space	Quiet
Participants value the library's calm, non-judgemental, non-hierarchical environment as a respite from a busy work space	Quiet
Participants value an opportunity to disengage from the demands of social contact in order to think and relax during the working day. They can "be themselves"	Quiet / Third space
Participants value an attractive, welcoming environment with friendly	Third space

<p>and helpful staff</p> <p>Participants value access to up-date, free IT technology in a modern library environment with enough workstations to satisfy demand</p> <p>Participants who are not studying, have no educational expectations, do not require evidence for practice, do not use any specific library services, and are either clinical or non-clinical value the library for its wider collection and physical space</p> <p>The concept of the library as “separate” is valued</p>	<p>IT</p> <p>Read / Third space</p> <p>Third space</p>
<p>Participants identified a “library type” as a self directed library user who will seek out the workplace library space regardless of whether they are encouraged to use the library by their manager or by the trust via policies</p>	<p>Third space / Social relationships and networks</p>

<p>Studying, actively carrying out personal or professional development and being reflective is often not supported in the trust which means that time in the library is not designated by managers within the working day. Reading for personal or professional development was not viewed as valued in the trust</p>	<p>Reading</p>
<p>The geographically distant / non-central position of the library from many participants' work department was seen as a barrier to usage, although physically leaving a department to come to the library was valued</p>	<p>Third space</p>

5.2 Reading, IT and the third space

The findings of the study revealed that Croydon Health Services (CHS) library is a multifunction space used for reading, work, relaxation, study, access to IT and reflective thinking by a cross section of grades and a mixture of clinical and non-clinical staff. It is a non-hierarchical and non-judgemental space. This supports the premise that the workplace library operates as a third space where activities not specifically related to the library service take place. This

sense of separateness that the library has is valued, although it is felt that the library is part of the organisation. This suggests that in the workplace the library space provides more than just a repository for resources and services. This is reflected in the literature from the public library sector, which puts forward the argument that libraries are developing into community hubs with multi-function roles.

5.3 Social relationships and networks

Recent organisational healthcare research raises recommendations that clinical and managerial communities in hospitals should have more opportunities to network in order to encourage knowledge sharing and learning. (Bresnen, 2014 p.104). The findings from this study suggest that participants saw their use of the CHS library space as allowing them to distance themselves from the need to contribute to workplace social relationship. As quiet is enforced in the CHS library, talking and collaborative working isn't specifically encouraged, participants did not come to the library to carry out joint working. They did use the library meeting room for group work. The library was perceived by some as being a social environment in the sense that people were friendly to each other. It emerged that participants felt they had the opportunity to mix with different grades and job types. Managers stated that if they knew their staff were in the library their whereabouts could be accounted for which reinforces social networks. The library is viewed as being part of workplace networks however it is not universally viewed as a social environment. This was commented on as an area for development by some participants, but should not mean that silence is sacrificed. As talking in the library wasn't encouraged, users could enter the space and not be

expected to engage with anyone, even if they were in uniform. Participants valued this, and they also valued seeing colleagues from different departments whom they wouldn't ordinarily see or engage with. They wanted to know who was using the library from their peer group and from other departments as this highlighted commonalities between staff.

5.4 Quiet and Wellbeing

Participants who used the library for relaxation reported that the library did contribute to their wellbeing e.g. they were able to relax during the working day. As a multifunctional space the library operates as an environment for people to work or hot desk, and also as a relaxing area in which staff can disengage during breaks. It is a legitimate destination to get away from the departmental environment which allows staff thinking space away from pressured wards / departments. Many staff do not have staff rooms in which to take breaks and value the opportunity to use the library environment to disengage. It is often the only quiet space that they feel they have access to. Even in staff rooms it was reported that there was a pressure to talk to colleagues in order to be polite. Also, staff had a responsibility to upkeep the staff room. In the library, library staff have the responsibility, which makes the experience of using it more relaxing. For participants who were working in the library, the environment enhanced their ability to focus and this helped their stress levels and wellbeing. Participants valued not having to talk to colleagues and feel they will be bothered when they are in the library. Access to well maintained IT equipment, wifi and relevant books and journals also adds to participants' wellbeing as they are able to complete work tasks with adequate resources. Library staff are valued for their calm demeanour and

are viewed as non-judgemental. Users value library staff being present in the library as this adds to the sense of relaxation. There are no expectations on participants to “play out” a particular job role. Elsewhere in the trust they could be called upon in a professional capacity (e.g. cafe, staff room, corridor)

Patients can use the library but this is rare, which means that users will generally only be mixing with colleagues from other departments. Staff use the library for a variety of their own reasons, which changes and varies according to their needs at the time.

Personal and professional objectives often overlap so that professional development feeds into personal development and vice versa. A theme did emerge around reading being seen as “skiving off” which is perhaps exaggerated by the fact that the library is seen as a leisure and a work environment.

Chapter 6

Research findings and conclusions

Discussion

In order to build networks and social capital, which positively affects health and well-being, face-to-face interactions are required as social dimensions are key (Woolcock, 2000 p.19). Places where these interactions can occur in the workplace are limited. However, where they do exist, trust between the humans interacting together develops. The trust between individuals can develop into trust between strangers and into trust of institutions (Layard, 2011 pg 7). The workplace library space provides an opportunity to develop social relationships and wellbeing as well as access support, resources and learning opportunities. The usual statement which challenges notions of the development of the library space is that everything is online and that the space doesn't matter. Yet, social relationships, social capital and wellbeing is affected by use of the physical library. As Turkle (2011, p.17) states, *"technology reshapes the landscape of our emotional lives, but is it offering us the lives we want to lead? What do we have, now that we have what we say we want – now that we have what technology makes easy? Are we comfortable with virtual environments that propose themselves not as places for recreation but as new worlds to live in?"* In Croydon Health Services (CHS) the third most common reason for staff absence in 2012/ 13 was anxiety / stress / depression / other psychiatric illnesses with 2935 days lost (Croydon Health Services 2013 pg. 5) In 2015, this has now become the most frequent reason for staff absence, as related by the OH Manager during her interview. CHS has an objective to move from a red staff survey RAG rating in 2012/13 to a green RAG rating by 2015/16 for staff satisfaction. Personal satisfaction

can be viewed as important as it is measured nationally by the Office of National Statistics as part of the personal wellbeing measures (Great Britain. Office of National Statistics 2014). Social capital is important because of its positive contribution to a range of wellbeing aspects relevant to policy makers and researchers, such as personal wellbeing (Helliwell, 2004). The importance of social capital has been highlighted by the Bank of England governor who stated that “prosperity requires not just investment in economic capital, but investment in social capital” (Carney, 2014 pg.4) Economic, natural, human and social capitals are all resources that matter for the present and future well-being of individuals (Siegler 2014. p.2)

A healthy, supported workforce will improve patient care as patient experience is improved when staff feel they are valued. There are links between staff wellbeing, the quality of patient care and improved organisational performance (Great Britain. Department of Health. 2009. p.13). The NHS Health and Wellbeing Review further recommends the establishment of an electronic health and wellbeing library for the NHS and that the evidence-base for wellbeing is developed. (Great Britain. Department of Health. 2009. p.34). It highlights wellbeing initiatives at Addenbrook’s hospital which includes five staff book clubs to increase social networks within the hospital and help staff develop new interests over lunchtime (Great Britain. Department of Health. 2009. p.10) The value of investing in health libraries has been quantified. The return on investment of health libraries in Australia found that they return \$9 for every \$1 invested. The results took into account time saved by medical practitioners in searching for answers, and how much it would cost healthcare staff to buy information they gain free from the library. (SGS Economics and Planning, 2013. p.1)

This time saving aspect of library services will also reduce stress in staff and allow them more time to devote to patient care. In the UK, the monetary value of public libraries to the individual has been put at £1,359 per person per year, for library users, or £113 per person per month. (Fujiwara, 2014. P.9)

6.1 Limitations

The results of this study need to be interpreted with caution, given its limitations. This is a relatively small sample of twelve. The balance of power between the researcher (as a possible influence on management) and interviewees (as staff side employees) might have affected the interview results of some participants.

6.2 Recommendations for further research

The findings suggest that further investigation is required around the barriers to library usage within the workplace, and in particular in NHS trusts. It would be useful to investigate further the unique contribution of libraries to staff wellbeing, social relationships and other intangible benefits that are current in the literature from other library sectors

In order to generalise findings a larger scale study, similar to this research, should be undertaken. The results of this study suggest that the physical library space is valued by users. This is runs contrary to suggestions that, as a lot of information is now online, the physical library space is redundant. The Library Quality Assurance Framework (LQAF) (NHS Library and Knowledge

Services, 2014) (Appendix 14) which is the national tool NHS libraries are benchmarked against for quality monitoring, measures whether the physical library space meets user needs and it also measures library impact. However use and perception of the physical library space not specifically addressed or directly measured. These metrics for NHS library use are gathered annually and give a quantitative measure of use e.g. number of books loaned, number of staff who are members, number of articles supplied.

Chapter 7

Recommendations and policy contributions

There is a gap in existing trust policies which reflect the contribution of the workplace library space to staff wellbeing and social relationships, due to the multifunction use of the library environment as a third space. This research suggests that the physical library space provides more than just a repository for resources and services. The value that stakeholders place on the physical library environment could be demonstrated within trust wellbeing policies via case studies and examples of user experience. Details of how the library has supported personal and professional objectives of staff could encourage library use and so support the organisation in achieving its objectives.

Subjective, qualitative feedback is a powerful tool to reflect how Trust staff think and feel and the data could be aligned with the trust's five "here for you" promises (see Appendix 9) and wider trust objectives (see Appendix 10). One key CHS trust objective is "to develop our workforce and to establish a way of working that builds a culture that is committed to an open transparent evidence based approach" (Croydon Health Services, 2015a). This research suggests that many managers and staff do not see the organisation as providing enough commitment to the provision of time and dedicated space to support this objective. Library services and spaces would benefit from marketing and investment to reach beyond "library types" who seek out the library space in leisure time as well as during working hours. The library space is valued and helps staff achieve trust objectives. The CHS Workforce Development and Study Leave policy states that Croydon Health Services is

“committed to promoting equitable workforce development opportunities to its staff to enhance staff motivation and engagement, increase skills and knowledge and enhance the organisation’s ability to attract high calibre staff” (Croydon Health Services, 2013a pg.3) (Appendix 15). The policy states that CHS promotes fair access to workforce development and education opportunities on a non-discriminatory basis, regardless of seniority or hierarchy (Croydon Health Services, 2013a pg. 4) and that Managers must support a learning environment within the workplace where the sharing of knowledge and skills is encouraged (Croydon Health Services, 2013a pg8) The library is mentioned in this policy (Croydon Health Services, 2013a pg.11) but only as a nod to being a repository for materials that Workforce Development *may* purchase on behalf of staff studying. No specific framework for working collaboratively with library services has been drawn up and no regular meetings or discussions between Workforce Development and Library Services take place. Educational resources are purchased in other trust departments on an ad hoc basis and not systematically under a single “education” department directive. The library is not involved with the working groups associated with Workforce Development: e.g. the People and Organisational Development Committee (POD) which oversees any learning and development activities in line with corporate priorities and which reviews education spend and the scholarship process. Yet the library actively supports many staff who are studying. The Trust supports the use of internet access for development purposes in designated areas, yet it does not say in its policies where these areas are, nor does it specify the costs for upgrading these areas and how the equipment in them will be funded. The library provides access to

the internet via numerous PC workstations, yet library PCs and IT upgrades are not factored into trust policies and funding allocations.

Recommendation 1

Case studies of how library use has positively impacted on staff wellbeing and personal and professional development is included in the CHS health and wellbeing policy

Recommendation 2

In order to support CHS as a learning organization, reading, research and evidence-based practice should be supported and encouraged for all staff for personal and professional development. For senior staff, time spent in the library could be viewed as protected space away from the front line, yet allowing “visible leadership” to take place.

Recommendation 3

Library as a third space to support staff wellbeing and social relationships, as well as an educational resource is actively promoted at Board level by the trust’s Chief Information Officer (also the Medical Director) who has responsibility for the library in his portfolio. Library services and spaces would benefit from marketing and investment to reach beyond “library types” who seek out the library space in leisure time as well as during working hours.

Recommendation 4

Adequate investment in the physical library space, staffing levels and IT equipment is committed via protection of the library budget and library

education tariffs in order to ensure regular upgrades to provide up-to-date, innovative, professional and efficient library services

Recommendation 5

The library service is more involved in with POD (people and organisational development group) and workforce development department in order to provide holistic support to the education portfolio at Croydon Health Services

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Appendices

Appendix 1

Search strategy

HMIC, Health Business Elite, CINAHL, Medline bibliographic databases

<input type="checkbox"/>	1	HMIC	(third AND space).ti,ab	20	Apply Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	2	HMIC	exp SOCIAL CAPITAL/	267	Apply Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	3	HMIC	wellbeing.ti,ab	1841	Apply Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	4	HMIC	exp LIBRARIES/	616	Apply Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	5	HMIC	exp INFORMATION SERVICES/ OR exp HEALTH SERVICE LIBRARIES/ OR exp HEALTH LIBRARIES/	1967	Apply Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	6	HMIC	4 OR 5	2207	Apply Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	7	HMIC	1 AND 6	0	Apply Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	8	HMIC	2 AND 6	1	Apply Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	9	HMIC	3 AND 6	5	Apply Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	10	HEALTH BUSINESS ELITE	(third AND space).ti,ab	537	Apply Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	11	HEALTH BUSINESS ELITE	exp SOCIAL CAPITAL/	509	Apply Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	12	HEALTH BUSINESS ELITE	wellbeing.ti,ab	1264	Apply Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	13	HEALTH BUSINESS ELITE	exp LIBRARIES/	3643	Apply Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	14	HEALTH BUSINESS ELITE	exp INFORMATION SERVICES/ OR exp HEALTH SERVICE LIBRARIES/ OR exp HEALTH LIBRARIES/	12067	Apply Limits	

<input type="checkbox"/>	15	HEALTH BUSINESS ELITE	13 OR 14	15344	Apply Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	16	HEALTH BUSINESS ELITE	10 AND 15	2	Apply Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	17	HEALTH BUSINESS ELITE	11 AND 15	0	Apply Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	18	HEALTH BUSINESS ELITE	12 AND 15	5	Apply Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	19	CINAHL	(third AND space).ti,ab	323	Apply Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	20	CINAHL	exp SOCIAL CAPITAL/	856	Apply Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	21	CINAHL	wellbeing.ti,ab	3449	Apply Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	22	CINAHL	exp LIBRARIES/	23695	Apply Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	23	CINAHL	exp INFORMATION SERVICES/ OR exp HEALTH SERVICE LIBRARIES/ OR exp HEALTH LIBRARIES/	45234	Apply Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	24	CINAHL	22 OR 23	57401	Apply Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	25	CINAHL	19 AND 24	4	Apply Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	26	CINAHL	20 AND 24	18	Apply Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	27	CINAHL	21 AND 24	45	Apply Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	28	Medline	wellbeing.ti,ab	6336	Apply Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	29	Medline	exp LIBRARIES/	9179	Apply Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	30	Medline	exp INFORMATION SERVICES/ OR exp HEALTH SERVICE LIBRARIES/ OR exp HEALTH LIBRARIES/	1132962	Apply Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	31	Medline	29 OR 30	1139582	Apply Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	32	Medline	19 AND 31	213	Apply Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	33	Medline	20 AND 31	0	Apply	

				Limits	
<input type="checkbox"/>	34	Medline	28 AND 31	64	Apply Limits

LISA (Proquest library science) bibliographic database

	S10	hospital libraries	2 databases	19898*	Actions
<input type="checkbox"/>	S9	nhs staff	2 databases	923°	Actions
Select item 9					
<input type="checkbox"/>	S8	nhs libraries	2 databases	1821°	Actions
Select item 8					
<input type="checkbox"/>	S7	a social capital model	2 databases	5990*	Actions
Select item 7					
<input type="checkbox"/>	S6	the dark side of social capital	2 databases	728°	Actions
Select item 6					
<input type="checkbox"/>	S5	a social capital theory	2 databases	5459*	Actions
Select item 5					
<input type="checkbox"/>	S4	((SU.exact("LIBRARIES") OR SU.exact("LIBRARIES 04122")) AND SU.exact("SPECIAL LIBRARIES"))	2 databases	1046	Actions
Select item 4					
<input type="checkbox"/>	S3	((SU.exact("QUALITY OF LIFE") OR PER.exact("QUALITY OF LIFE")) AND (SU.exact("LIBRARIES") OR SU.exact("LIBRARIES 04122"))))	2 databases	14	Actions
Select item 3					
<input type="checkbox"/>	S2	((SU.exact("QUALITY OF LIFE") OR PER.exact("QUALITY OF	2 databases	14	Actions
Select					

item 2		LIFE")) AND (SU.exact("HEALTH") OR ORG.exact("HEALTH"))			
<input type="checkbox"/>	S1	wellbeing	2 databases	739°	Actions

Appendix 2

Employee Health & Wellbeing Improvement Framework 2013 - 2015

Version:	1.0
Ratified by:	
Date ratified:	
Authors:	Emma Jones, HR Business Partner Valerie Cornford, OH Manager
Date launched:	
Health and Wellbeing Strategy	Debbie Eyitayo, Deputy Director of HR

Employee Health & Wellbeing Improvement Framework

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Appendix 1 Action Plan

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1. Introduction

The NHS Constitution commits to provide support and opportunities for staff to maintain their health, well-being and safety. This framework follows on from the Health and Wellbeing strategy 2011 and sets out the current position in relation to health and wellbeing support and activity for staff within the Trust. It describes the Trust's aspirations and details an action plan to improve health and wellbeing and its contribution to the overall staff experience.

2. Trust Commitment

Croydon Health Services NHS Trust (CHS) is committed to developing and enabling a working environment that promotes the health, safety and wellbeing of its employees. The Trust has approximately 3,700 staff (including bank staff). In line with its 'Here for You' promise '*You feel cared for*', the Trust believes that improvement to staff health and wellbeing can help improve morale and motivation of staff, lead to a reduction in sickness absence and turnover, contribute to improved employee engagement and thereby lead to better care for patients and client groups.

The Trust's Workforce Strategy supports this position by stating the Trust will progress the health and wellbeing action plan to become an employer of choice.

3. Background

A healthy workforce is a more productive one. The NHS Health & Wellbeing Report (undertaken in 2009 and resulting in the Boorman Interim Report) revealed that patient care outcomes are influenced by good morale and motivation with 80% of NHS employees surveyed responding that they considered their state of health and wellbeing affected patient care. This is further underpinned by more recent research by the National Nursing Research Unit suggesting that patient experiences are better when staff feel they have a good working environment, support from co-workers and low emotional exhaustion ¹.

A trust that is in the top 10 per cent of organisations in terms of health and wellbeing is also likely to be in the top 20 per cent of trusts in terms of patient satisfaction 2.

There is considerable evidence that health and wellbeing programmes produce business benefits across different sectors and sizes of business.

These benefits include:-

- Reduced sickness absence
- Reduced staff turnover
- Reduced accidents and injuries
- Higher employee satisfaction
- Improved employee engagement
- Increased productivity
- Improved patient satisfaction rating
- Decreased MRSA rates
- Reduction in errors / near misses
- Improved annual health check ratings

In essence supporting the health and wellbeing of staff can improve service quality and productivity and supports positive health and wellbeing of staff. There are large proportion of staff that are part of the local community in the Croydon borough. Therefore this framework further supports the Trust's objective to improve the health and wellbeing of Croydon.

4. Wider National Agenda

In March 2008, Dame Carol Black's review of the health of Britain's working age population was published. The review recognised the beneficial impact that work can have on an individual's state of health and that work is generally good for both physical and mental health. The review set out a vision based on three principles:

- Prevention of illness and promotion of health and well-being;
- Early intervention for those who develop a health condition; and
- An improvement in the health of those out of work

It identified the importance of healthy workplaces designed to protect and promote good health and the central role that such workplaces play in preventing illness arising in the first place. The Department of Work & Pensions (1) concludes that small changes in the workplace, particularly on the part of line managers can make a big difference to the wellbeing of staff.

The Department of Health have produced publications; The NHS Health & Wellbeing Improvement Framework and Healthy Staff, Better Care for Patients. In line with this, the Public Health Responsibility Deal was launched in 2011 to promote the workplace as a vehicle for promoting public health and improve health and wellbeing of staff. The Francis Report released in February 2013 gave clear emphasis that there were links between patient care and staff experience.

In 2012 David Nicholson, NHS Chief Executive challenged the NHS to use the inspirational power of the London Olympic Games to get 2,012 NHS employees actively engaged in sport or physical activity which resulted in the NHS Sport and Physical Activity Challenge. NHS Trusts can be accredited Bronze, Silver and Gold awards for varying levels of participation in physical activity.

In the London region, the Greater London Authority (GLA) provides a framework, the Healthy Workplace Charter which combines a self-assessment and accreditation route to reaching 'Excellence' as a framework for developing good practice.

5. Health & Wellbeing Data – current position

The Trust's sickness absence target for 2011/2012 was 3.5% and reduced to 3% in April 2012 in line with the Department of Health guidance. For 2011/12 the Trust rate averaged 3.45% which was below target and below the NHS sector average of 4.18%. However, the projected average for 2012/13 is 3.25%, above national target and the cost of sickness absence was **£2,949,267.59** for 2011/12. The top reasons for absence are below.

Reason for absence	By no of Days Lost
Other musculoskeletal problems	3207
Cold, Cough, Flu - Influenza	3081
Anxiety/stress/depression/other psychiatric illnesses	2935

Reason for absence	By no of Episodes
Cold, Cough, Influenza	1299
Gastrointestinal problems	905
Headache / migraine	375

Referrals	2011	2012
No. of OH referrals		
No. of Physiotherapy referrals		
No of referrals to staff counselling		

Staff turnover for 2011/12 was 13.37%. The UK national average turnover rate is 15%. Within the public sector the average turnover rate is 11%. Exit surveys do not currently provide meaningful data on health and wellbeing matters due to low response rates and unrelated questions.

5.3 National Staff Attitude Survey

The national staff survey is structured around the four Staff Pledges within the NHS Constitution. Relevant questions relating to health and wellbeing reveal the following outcome for the national staff survey 2012 and are compared to 2011.

Question (last 12mths)	Response score	Comparison to 2011
% staff receiving health and safety training	Highest (best) 20%	Increase (better)
% staff experiencing physical violence from patients, relatives or the public	Lowest (best) 20%	No change
Staff motivation at work	Above (better than) average	No change
% staff experiencing harassment, bullying or abuse from patients, relatives or the public	Average	-
% staff suffering work related stress	Average	No change
Staff feeling under pressure	Average	No change

to attend work when unwell		
% experiencing physical violence from staff	Above (worse than) average	-
Staff recommendation of the trust as a place to work or receive treatment	Lowest (worst) 20%	Increase (better)
% experiencing harassment, bullying or abuse	Highest (worst) 20%	-
% experiencing discrimination at work	Highest (worst) 20%	- No change
Work pressure felt by staff	Highest (worst) 20%	-

5.4 Listening into Action

The Trust launched Listening into Action (LiA) in September 2012 to fundamentally shift how the organisation works and leads by putting staff at the centre of change and seeking ideas on how to make it a better place to work. Responses have not directly indicated health & wellbeing issues but the top five areas of feedback (as below) will clearly impact on the staff experience and feeling of wellbeing:

- Poor communication
- Restrictive and multiple IT systems
- Workload / capacity to provide care
- Lack of Resources / Finance
- Poor staffing Levels

5.5 Patient Survey

(Awaiting release of the National Patient Survey 2012 / Jan Friends & Family Test)

6. Current Health & Wellbeing Support & Activity

Health & Wellbeing Group

The Trust has a dedicated group of multidisciplinary members who meet every two months to provide leadership and direction for

implementing and managing staff health and wellbeing issues across the Trust.

Sickness absence management and support

Managers have a responsibility to effectively manage and monitor sickness absence and support individuals in managing any health conditions in line with the Trust's Sickness Absence Policy. Return to work interviews are in place to support individuals returning to work and to ascertain any reasonable adjustments that may be required and clinical advice and support is sought via occupational health. Absence data is regularly provided to managers, directorate Board meetings and Trust Board to monitor trends, issues and areas of concern.

Stress Management

Staff Survey Results indicate a decrease in recent years of those reporting stress however, it still remains at an 'average' score with no change from the 2011 survey.

Work-related stress accounts for a large proportion of long term absence and it is recognised that individuals are sometimes less able to cope with stress than a physical illness which can lead to other health issues and absence from work and a proportion of Trust absence is reported as 'other/unknown'.

Stress Management training workshops have been delivered within the Trust and are available to managers and staff on an on-going basis. These sessions support the Trust's Stress Management policy. Organisational, departmental and team stress audits are undertaken as and when appropriate and action plans implemented.

Occupational Health Service / Health@Work

Staff can access Occupational Health advice and support via self or management referral, in person or over the telephone. This service includes referrals for dermatology and chest clinic assessments on site at Croydon University Hospital. The service will soon be renamed Health@Work to illustrate its broader remit of health and wellbeing within the Trust.

Mental Health Awareness

Occupational Health work closely with local mental health and drug and alcohol support services. These links are being developed in connection with SLAM for Specialist Mental Health support and Croydon Council DAAT team. The Trust aspires to reduce the stigma attached to mental health issues by pledging its support to the Time for Change campaign to tackle mental health discrimination.

Staff Counselling Service

The Trust provides a free and confidential in-house counselling support service to all staff on request. This can be accessed directly by calling the helpline on ext. 5663 or a referral via Occupational Health.

Respect at Work Support

The Trust provides a mediation service as an intervention for workplace disputes and cases of bullying and harassment in an effort to diffuse matters, support staff and limit the need for escalation to formal processes, where this is appropriate. The Trust also provides confidential advice via a group of Respect at Work advisors to all staff that may wish to access it. The Trust provides staff and management training around respect and dignity at work. The Respect at Work offering is currently under review.

Smoking Cessation Support

The Trust can provide a variety of interventions to staff wishing to stop smoking. The Smoking Cessation counsellor run clinics within the department and occupational health and has a dedicated health promotion board.

Physical Activity

The Trust has a purpose built gym situated in the grounds of Croydon University Hospital with a current membership of 300 (approx. 8.5% of the workforce). Gym membership is £10 per month and includes fitness classes; Boxercise, Circuit Training and Military Boot Camp. There is a concrete table tennis table in the area.

Fitness classes Zumba and Pilates run weekly at Lennard Road. There is an appetite from staff for the Trust to run regular classes at the hospital site where the majority of staff are based. Walking, running and football activities are also organised by individuals within the Trust and advertised on the intranet.

The Trust has provided walking and cycling routes for commuting to the hospital site. A cycle to work loan scheme (salary sacrifice) is available to staff wishing to purchase a bicycle and the Trust has a number of bike racks around the site. Access to showering facilities is available but reported as not always easily accessible.

Healthy Eating

Healthy Eating information is available in occupational health and the Dietetics and catering teams work closely to ensure food available in the restaurant is balanced, gives a range of options and dietary requirements can be catered for on request. The teams are currently working on clearer labelling for allergy advice and regular promote health events in the restaurant area.

Health & Wellbeing Information

The Trust uses the intranet site and What's New all staff email to inform staff of health and wellbeing advice, activities and promotions. Currently an online portal is being developed and customised that will widen the scope of internal and external information and links. Accessible from outside of the Trust, it is hoped that access will also be available via smartphone in the near future.

Health and Wellbeing Champions

The Trust has 10 champions who are available to share information and endorse activities at a local level. The Move for Life health & wellbeing survey conducted in 2012 revealed that 20 staff were interested in becoming a workplace health champion and this interest should be harnessed and utilised.

7. Key Trust improvements identified

The Trust has good foundations to build on improving staff health and wellbeing, the work experience and patient care. Using a Department of Health framework⁴ those improvements have been identified under three key areas:

Positive action *that will help support those with ill-health return to work as soon as possible;*

- Improving attendance at work and reducing cost of absence by reducing contributory factors and improving robust supportive management of absence and health conditions & improve patient care
- Reducing work related stress by assessing the contributing factors and managing it appropriately

Preventative Activity *to reduce ill-health and poor well-being by offering "Fit for Work" activity (lifestyle improvements) and "Healthy Work" activity (to improve well-being through quality work and management practice)*

- Improving information and access to current, prospective and new staff on the wellbeing offering and creating a strong 'brand'
- Raise awareness of support services available to staff for general health, mental health and respect at work
- Utilise the Health & Wellbeing Champions to assist in organising activities
- Increasing opportunities to take part in physical activity available across sites to encourage fitness
- Promote and increase uptake of influenza vaccinations to ensure staff and patients are protected
- Ensure that stress management training is available to managers and staff
- Encourage workforce planning that accounts for work life balance and control over work
- Make readily available information on healthy eating options and promote within the catering facilities on site

- Celebrate and promote national health events to raise awareness of healthy lifestyles, health conditions and referral pathways and inspire public health collaboration

Evaluative Activity *that will help the Trust monitor progress and benchmark*

- Ongoing review of DH H&W organisational assessment/risk tool
- Undertake self-assessment and accreditation for Healthy Workplace Charter
- Undertake evaluation in line with HSE Stress Management Standards
- Progress organisational pledges; Time to Change & Public Responsibility Deal
- Apply for NHS Physical Activity Awards (Bronze, Silver, Gold)
- Undertake focussed health and wellbeing surveys to assess needs
- Improve exit survey process and content to ascertain feedback

8. Key Success Factors:

- **Leadership**

The Director of HR and OD has overall responsibility for the implementation of the health and wellbeing framework and will provide update the Strategy Committee on a six monthly basis. Workforce metrics are supplied to the Trust Board on a monthly basis and sickness absence data is tabled at Executive Management Group and Directorate Performance Meetings. The Trust has a dedicated Health & Wellbeing Group that reports to the People and Organisational Development Committee.

- **Staff Engagement**

For positive health and wellbeing to become a successful reality, staff must be fully engaged in the process by being informed and involved in developing accessible information and support. Health and Wellbeing surveys have provided feedback on satisfaction and desires, albeit a low response rate. The Trust has a number of Health & Wellbeing Champions to promote healthy living initiatives. The Trust informs staff of opportunities through a range of communications including Team

Briefing, Intranet, email and noticeboards. The Listening into Action work will continue to involve staff in decisions and review feedback.

- **Management Practice**

Embedding good management practice across the Trust through good communication, training and performance review is key to staff feeling valued, motivated and happy in their workplace. This includes role design, involvement in key decisions and good communication as well as managing employee issues more effectively such as absence, stress management, bullying and harassment and work-life balance.

The Chartered Institute of Personnel reports that absence surveys consistently suggest poor management style is a top cause of work related stress⁵. The Trust has recently redesigned the PDR process to be more specific about core management competencies and is being rolled out in April 2013.

In line with the Trust's Stress Management policy, managers, HR and OH will continue to manage and support cases relating to work related stress undertaking the appropriate risk assessments, identifying stressors and taking appropriate action to reasonable mitigate against these risks. All line managers should attend relevant training available to them.

- **Working in Partnership**

The Health and Wellbeing Group is chaired by a Clinical Director of the Trust and includes representatives from across the Trust as outlined in the terms of reference. The Chair of Staff Side will be kept involved and informed of progress via People & Development Committee. The Trust will continue to liaise with NHS London, DH Health and Wellbeing Lead for London, London Health and Wellbeing Coordinator, Croydon Council and NHS Croydon's Public Health Wellbeing lead.

- **Occupational Health / Health@Work**

Occupational Health consistently reviews its service provision to ensure it meets the needs of staff and the organisation by participating in internal and external audits. Staff counselling is a key element of the support provided to staff.

- **Public Health Links**

The Trust will continue to liaise with the Public Health Lead for Wellbeing in Croydon and through NHS London and links in with any initiatives being rolled out locally and / or nationally including for example Change4Life, Healthier Food Mark, weight loss clinics, smoking cessation and Cycle to Work.

The Trust will continue to explore and work with those relevant Health and Wellbeing initiatives adopted by the governing health bodies (e.g. DH, NHS London)

9. Monitoring & Evaluation

The Health and Wellbeing Action Plan will be reviewed and progressed by the Health and Wellbeing Group and monitored by the Strategy Committee.

Progress of Health and Wellbeing within the Trust will be measured in line with the following:

- achievement of health & wellbeing pledges and accreditations
- DH organisational self-assessment / risk assessment tool
- on-going monitoring of sickness absence data and costs
- no of ill health retirements and cost
- promotion and uptake of health and wellbeing activities
- usage stats for intranet and portal
- turnover rates and data from exit surveys
- vacancy rates and levels of staffing
- staff attitude survey results
- listening into action feedback
- bespoke health and wellbeing surveys
- stress management audits
- achievement of core competencies within management appraisals
- seasonal flu vaccination uptake
- no of appointments and DNAs at Occupational Health
- Datix and Riddor reports

10. Action Plan

A comprehensive action plan is attached in Appendix 1 detailing actions; timescales, desired outcomes and cost, and this will be reviewed by the Health and Wellbeing Group every two months and reported to People and Organisational Development Committee every six months.

11. References

¹ A study: Exploring the relationship between patients' experiences of care and the influence of staff motivation, affect and wellbeing – National Nursing Research Unit.

² Health & Wellbeing of NHS Staff – A benefit evaluation model (DH)

³ Health, Work and wellbeing: attitudes of GPs, line managers, and the general public - Department of Work and Pensions

⁴ Department of Health Template Health & Wellbeing Strategy Document – Strategic Approach

⁵ Line manager capability: Importance of line managers; wellbeing and performance – CIPD / AXA PPP Healthcare

12. Associated documents

- NHS Health & Wellbeing – The Boorman Review Final Report 2009
- Health at Work – an independent review of sickness absence - Dame Carol Black & David Frost CBE 2011
- Francis Inquiry Report – Robert Francis QC 2013
- Greater London Authority- The London Healthy Workplace Charter Self-Assessment and Accreditation (*This assessment was adapted from the Workplace Wellbeing Charter developed by Liverpool Primary Care NHS Trust*).

Appendix 3

Interview transcripts

Participant 030

Do you have any strong beliefs about workplace libraries?

Yes I think well it depends on personal and professional. Professionally it is absolutely essential for us as a resource.

But personally for me probably the environment that I can come to sometimes and hopefully not interfering with other people. Cos it's quiet and I can read during lunch breaks that is a major reason why I use it. But yes I feel strongly that it is a very important resource. It is not often there is elsewhere, anywhere in the hospital.

Why do you come to this library?

I come mainly to read and to relax. I do a little bit if studying not necessarily work study but different study. The library is an ideal place for it because it is quiet.

What do you use the library for?

Reading, study, thinking

Why do you choose to come to the library rather than go elsewhere?

Because it is quiet and the other good thing of a library because of the culture of the library people are not going there to disturb you. You go somewhere else and particularly in the work environment, I used to use the clinic where I work, there were some consulting rooms but people would come in and interrupt me. So if I come here it is more quiet and comfortable.

Last month, how many times did you come to the library?

It would be nearly every working day so roughly 5 days a week so it's going to be about 18-20 days.

How long do you stay on average?

About half an hour.

Do you come during working hours and / or during your breaks?

I come during lunch break

How would you describe the library environment / physical space?

Comfort yeah is good. Erm, surprised that not more people use it.

Quiet place to come and study.

Do you bring your own books, journals, magazines, reports or do you use library resources – books, journals whilst you are here?

I bring my own things yes.

Do you use library PCs or do you bring your own device?

I have done and I have done that during work time as well because again, no one is going to disturb you here and you can do those mandatory course and not have work colleagues disturb you.

Do you use the library wifi?

No I don't use that.

What would make you come to the library more?

More time but I haven't got that!

How could the Trust encourage you to use the library more?

Well I use it more professionally which I need to anyway which I have just started to do. I think that is a difficult one, I really don't know apart from advertising but then if you're advertised there is so much information on the intranet people don't select it.

Do you think it would be useful if trust policies on the subject of well-being recommended spending time in the library to encourage personal and professional development?

Er, wellbeing. I think again with libraries, its natural selection. People of the character and type of person that will use libraries and you see the same people here all the time using – the doctors, the nurses, they use it as a great resource for study in particular. So they find it very useful, so I think to get people to change their study habits then you might get people to use it more, so it is changing that culture into studying and reflection.

Is the way library staff behave towards you different from other staff in the trust?

Oh yes if people are friendly and open and helpful, you know I have always found it really helpful here. Erm any information I've needed are asked for like how to use Athens etc. you know.

Do you find they are different from other staff in the Trust, in the way they treat people?

People are all different in the Trust. Overall they seem to be helpful here.

There has never been any kinda judgement of the information you're searching for you know.

Would a poor encounter with library staff dissuade you from visiting the library again? If so why?

Erm, if you weren't used to it maybe yeah. If you come along for years and it has been fine but particular if someone has come along for the first or second time then yes I think it would. I think interactions are the most important thing in life. If you get a poor interaction with somebody. You will find a poor interaction will influence somebody generally than a good interaction.

Does your Manager support a learning environment within the workplace where the sharing of knowledge and skills is encouraged?

Yes less than it used to be because of err, staff shortages and the more demands of work. There is less training for in service training etc. There used to be a reasonable amount a few years ago but not now. But say if I wanted to lead a session in something, yes it would be encouraged.

Do you have personal objectives in mind when you use the library?

Yes, personally and professionally. Personally I have said what I want to achieve that day reading. Might be a couple of things that I'm reading and I do come here to use it occasionally. Professionally, oh yes to use have an objective when you come here.

Have you ever used library's fiction collection or books on prescription collection or other resources for your own personal development, not relating to your work?

A few of the self help ones I've looked at. They are quite interesting because they relate to work issues. Things like Positive Outlook, Anxiety is another one.

Do you find the library a social environment where you can meet colleagues on a different level from other places in the workplace?

Yes.

Do you think using the library helps you achieve trust objectives, by giving you a thinking space?

Yes definitely because if there is an article I want to read and it might take only 5-10 mins to read the article, I will deliberately come down here then stay in the work environment which you will be interrupted by something else.

Do you feel the library is part of the networks within the organisation?

Can be. It can be yeah. Certainly with other study partners.

Do you feel the library staff know people in the Trust?

Regular people come here a lot, yeah.

Do you feel that the library knows about other organisations that could support you in your development?

Erm, I haven't really explored that side, I don't know. I would imagine so because even through search engines you can see various journal and institutions that they're coming from.

Have you ever come across things you hadn't set out to find in the library?

Oh yes, I've done that a few times particularly for journals. When it used to be the older system where you had a lot more journals on the shelf. I think society has moved on and you would never store the information that way. You really have to change because it is easier for younger people who really wanna change the culture to work in. But that browsing ability I think is still important but we just don't have that now.

Have you ever asked / would you feel comfortable asking library staff about training on "modern technologies"

I've never of thought of that but yeah, it would be quite useful, especially the Kindle side of things.

Do you trust the library staff? If yes, why?

Yes.

Anything else?

No. I can't really think of anything. I think the library is an essential service to develop thinking because that is what it is about. It's about thinking and moving along in life to develop things. The health service like many other areas, you need that. When you do your portfolio now, it's all electronic now. It's not fantastic but it's ok. You can upload things like videos, media, radio shows. There is a huge resource out here. Radio, 4 there will some item on the news that is personal to health care. And the science programmes. Things like that.

I want to start using the library more, physio is not a passion of my life, it's all good. I will come and get a refresher on Athens.

You definitely need a forum. There is too much faith put in online. Everything's online now but the problem is that the human interaction is very important and the library does provide that environment to interact and exchange information a lot quicker than you can if you are just searching on the web.

I think the other problems as well is encouraging people to study cos when they come to work – it's interesting that you say that physios use the library a lot, I've thought the top people would have been the medics etc. because they are forever having to develop their career, you know exam after exam.

Participant 040

Do you have any strong beliefs about workplace libraries?

They should be accessible and well stocked and er, good, helpful staff makes a difference cos sometimes, from previous experience that somebody who knows their way around the place, it's always very helpful and they know how to access things such as articles because I wasn't too sure how to do that. I think probably that helpful staff is one of the most important things.

Why do you come to this library?

It's quiet. I come here in my lunch break as a member of staff because it's quiet and I can read, I like reading. I come occasionally to get articles. I have in the past but not so much recently. OT books occasionally.

What do you use the library for?

One of the interesting things is the way this particular library as developed and the use of its space. For example putting pictures up, that is an interesting point. I think that has been good. You have the coffee machine there as well and the computers. I have used the computers on occasions.

Why do you choose to come to the library rather than go elsewhere?

It is a quiet space, a designated quiet space. There aren't many of those kinds of spaces available in the hospital. You really can't get that quiet in the work space to read or book or do any studying. It's conducive to study.

Last month, how many times did you come to the library?

I come every day in my lunch break!

How long do you stay on average?

About 40 minutes.

How would you describe the library environment / physical space?

Quietness. It's quite an intimate space. It isn't a large library. It has got multifunctional elements to it. I've also noticed that in the past you've put books out for foreign speaking members of staff which is very good and very interesting. I suppose I know it's a hospital library but I've noticed you have other books.

Do you bring your own books, journals, magazines, reports or do you use library resources – books, journals whilst you are here.

Er, I do occasionally read articles here. We have journal club so I read articles for that. Generally speaking I bring my own books.

Do you use library PCs or do you bring your own device?

I have used the computers.

Do you use the library wifi?

No

What would make you come to the library more?

Cakes! I have used the tea and coffee machine a couple of times. It's very good value. You can't get a tea or coffee cheaper than that in the hospital.

To be perfectly honest I don't think coming to the library is encouraged in our department in a way that it perhaps was. I think the emphasis so much now is on do your job and there is very little scope for study unless you really make your own effort. I think that is a shame in a way. We used to have designated study days. We were encouraged to take those but those days are gone now.

How could the Trust encourage you to use the library more?

More study days, to encourage learning I suppose.

I think advertising that kind of information about the library would be useful so that people would come in and be more likely to dip a toe in.

Do you think it would be useful if trust policies on the subject of well-being recommended spending time in the library to encourage personal and professional development?

Definitely yeah. I mean the whole study issue. I mean so much of our profession is evidence based and to have that sort of time to look at what the evidence is, I don't think you can do that now.

Is the way library staff behave towards you different from other staff in the trust?

Yes definitely. We want people to be helpful and I think you want that in all areas of the hospital. Sometimes you are not aware that things exist so if you are looking for something, I suppose people know their stuff and people can point you in the right direction so that's helpful It is the same when someone comes on to the ward and can you tell me what are the options for my mother for example.

Would a poor encounter with library staff dissuade you from visiting the library again? If so why?

Erm, I think people's attitudes are important. I think, you know, I find anyway that personal rapport with somebody helps, it builds. I've always found the staff here really helpful.

Does your Manager support a learning environment within the workplace where the sharing of knowledge and skills is encouraged?

No.

(Do you think your Manager should?)

Yes

Do you have personal objectives in mind when you use the library?

I'm not doing it for an area of study. I'm doing not any dissertation or private study.

Have you ever used library's fiction collection or books on prescription collection or other resources for your own personal development, not relating to your work?

I haven't no.

Do you find the library a social environment where you can meet colleagues on a different level from other places in the workplace?

Yeah I mean I do meet people here like Alan. I'm really conscious of the fact that you are not supposed to talk in the library. I've seen work colleagues here occasionally.

Do you think using the library helps you achieve trust objectives, by giving you a thinking space?

Yes.

Do you feel the library is part of the networks within the organisation?

Yes, I do. It is always one of the things that when people start, you direct them and introduce them to the library. So it is an important feature.

Do you feel that the library knows about other organisations that could support you in your development?

I don't know if you are or not. I wouldn't know that. Is it advertised? I didn't know there were links like that. I'm sure a lot of other people would be interested to know about it.

Have you ever come across things you hadn't set out to find in the library?

Yes I have, I browse the shelves. There were a couple of books that I got and became so keen on I ordered another book after that so I have.

Have you ever asked / would you feel comfortable asking library staff about training on “modern technologies”?

I would. Does the library have its own twitter account?

(Yes we have. Are you a prolific tweeter?)

I do tweet I mean I have got a twitter account, I've been tweeting for some time. Do you have a Facebook page? (Yes we do)

I didn't know about technology drop-in so it's worth knowing the library does that.

Do you trust the library staff?

Yes. I think there should be confidentiality all around the trust.

Anything else?

I think that having a designated library space is valuable. I think it is not a good idea to get rid of that. I think it is good to have a space and some people want to look at hardcopies of things.

Participant 050

Do you have any strong beliefs about workplace libraries?

I think every workplace should have one, particularly organisations like the NHS and other statutory services.

Er, employers talk a lot about personal development and reflection and yet if they haven't given people a space to do that in or a space to access either computers or journals or books to build on their knowledge or reflect on their knowledge, then the two don't really fix I think, erm, if you're an employer that's promoting that in your staff then you need to create an environment where people can do that.

Why do you come to this library?

It's a quiet space, within a very busy environment, it's nicely laid out, it feels welcoming and I like the addition of a coffee machine, that's nice.

I don't have a work base within the hospital, so this in effect becomes my top desk and also a bit of a retreat for me when I just need to collect my thoughts.

If I go and sit on a ward, or try and sit in someone else's office, erm, I don't get the quiet time I need, or someone will ask me a question or think they have to engage, when actually all I want to do is be quiet.

What do you use the library for?

I come and work, I might look up additional things that build on my work, so I might have had a question off a ward or I might want to check out something erm, Google something that would help, so I can be more informed to go back and answer the question, so I use it for research.

I like flicking through other people's journals, not only my own discipline, so like the Health service journal and the dysphasia journal and things like that I can just have a flick through, and I've been able to influence the purchase of books, which is nice, which then makes me feel that other non-specialists in my field or staff may one day come across a journal or the book and think "oh, that's interesting", and when I do training, I tell people there are books in the library, so they can go and expand their knowledge.

Why do you choose to come to the library rather than go elsewhere?

Yeah, people don't ask me questions, and I'm also conscious that if I want to do some work, so I need to load data for myself around the patients, or look stuff up, if I do that within the context of one of the multi-disciplinary rooms on the wards or in the departments, I'm reducing the access that other staff may need to carry out their activities, so for example, while I'm Googling erm, 'underwear for peg users', someone else can't print off a set of blood results. So erm, I'm very conscious of pressures on our computer systems and er, so if I'm

not doing something that's acutely needed within that environment for a patient on that ward, I'd rather come away to an environment like this and not feel like I'm compromising other people's workloads.

Last month, how many times did you come to the library?

It varies really, because of the amount of time I spend on the site there is so... if I'm on site, Heavy use of the site, then I'll be here at least weekly, if not a couple of times a week, it might be for ten minutes, it might be for an hour and a half, but then I could be not coming onto the site for two weeks for various reasons and not touch it at all.

How long do you stay on average?

Yeah, that varies, it can be ten minutes to flick through a journal or just have ten minutes to collect my thoughts with my diary or I could sit here for two hours logging everything and doing some research.

Do you come during working hours and / or during your breaks?

I don't actually use the library for non-work activities, I'm aware there's a nice set of reading books and things and non-fiction and fiction, er, no I keep that separate, I do my personal social library type things in my local library and this is much more my work.

How would you describe the library environment / physical space?

It's nice having a desk space here, so I've used it a few times, have sat and done something, I'm often much more computer focussed so that's handy, it's nice being able to have a drink, because libraries in the past have always been 'non fluid environments', "you can't have a coffee in the library incase you spill it", that's nice.

And it's nice to have the sofas there, I never really have time to sit on the sofas, but I appreciate lots of other people do and it's nice to come in, and I suppose it's a bit of a challenge for me because it makes me think "maybe I should be sitting on the sofa reading a paper or a non-fiction book", you know, using it as a less 'work' space and more of a relaxation space, but I haven't got that disciplined with it yet.

Do you bring your own books, journals, magazines, reports or do you use library resources – books, journals whilst you are here.

I've usually got my work things that I need to enter or erm, but I'll use the Intranet from here to access, and I suppose I said about I flick through other magazines and stuff like that's here if I'm looking for something in particular

Do you use the library wifi?

No.

What would make you come to the library more?

The times where I've come in and then gone away again, have been when all of the computers have been taken and there are only four or five in that corner, erm, and I notice that it is being used very regularly by people like me who don't have a space anywhere in the world or like me have found their MDT rooms just too frantic. Looking over other people's shoulders, I can see them entering often the same sort of data and stuff I'm doing on patients, so I think it's being used in that way, er, so the only reason where I'd use it more would be in the times that I've come and it's been full, would be just to have some more computers.

How could the Trust encourage you to use the library more?

I don't think many people, I know this sounds crazy, I'm not sure people really realise it's here, it's in the PGMC and it's stuck out of the way, erm, I'm not sure you could kind of place it above front of reception or something, but I think for lots of staff it's a long way from their working space and so popping in for ten minutes if you're on Fairfield One or you're in the Eye department, it's quite a walk, down here, so I think location might do, might improve it's usage. Yeah, because people kind of pass it by on the way to training, or somewhere else.

Do you think it would be useful if trust policies on the subject of well-being recommended spending time in the library to encourage personal and professional development?

Not sure staff particularly spend a lot of time reading policies. Per se, I think lots of staff find it difficult to find time to read policies that they need to use on an absolute daily basis, like Health policies, so I think you could put wonderful ideas like that in well-being policy, but I'm not sure how many people would think "ooh, I must read the well-being policy and it says I should spend more time in the library" within their busy day.

Is the way library staff behave towards you important?

Yeah, Any environment that's er, public facing needs to be welcoming and you need to feel like you can ask questions and you're not going to be tutted out or told to come back in three hours or whatever.

I've never experienced that here, I have experienced people not being around and happened to search for people, I'm conscious sometimes I'm disturbing somebody because of the staffing levels, but I'm not sure, and I think that's got worse, which is a sadness for the library because I'm sure the library staff then have to, you know, try and do ten things at once, and the layout of the office space within the library may be, if you're going to have much less staff, then it needs to be maybe, nick some of the office space, create some more computer banks in and make the office staff more visual if they are going to have to do three things at once and that, you know, might help.

Is the way library staff behave towards you different from other staff in the trust?

I think we try as a trust really hard to offer it, I think within the space limitations we've got and the age of the building, we're sometimes restricted.

That makes me think "I wonder how easy it would be to get a wheelchair round the library"

I think it may be quite tight, and if you've got one of the really flashy all-singing, all-dancing wheelchairs with power packs and things, I think your turning circle at the end of some of the big library stands would be quite difficult, and certainly if you were to want to use a computer maybe, and again, you were in a wheelchair, your use of the one computer would probably restrict the access to somebody else, or certainly impinge on people, you might find you were all a bit squashed in one corner, and so that might be a challenge, but it is a limited space.

I think the trust would be responsive if they had an increase in people who raised concerns about the space, in terms of wheelchair access, I think they'd have a go, but it would then, there might be some losses to the library as well in terms of "what have we got to take out then, in order to create that space?"

Would a poor encounter with library staff dissuade you from visiting the library again? If so why?

If I had a bad experience, I'd do something about it, because I think, erm, I'd give someone that came in one day and someone's a bit off or doesn't make very good eye contact or whatever, I'd say, we all have our tough days.

But if every time I came in, someone sighed at me or didn't make eye contact or could clearly see I was waiting and still didn't come, then I'd probably, well I would, I'd give some feedback, because I think it's...there's no point in moaning about things if then no one knows, it might be that the person doesn't realise they have a mannerism that means that they tut without realising it, or maybe they do need to be told that actually "That's not acceptable, 16 people say that you sighed heavily when you took the books off them" whatever.

I've not found that, but if I did, I would do something about it because I think it's not only me, it's a whole range of people that come in here, whole range of other professions, and we take away comments about our trust.

Does your Manager support a learning environment within the workplace where the sharing of knowledge and skills is encouraged?

Yes, we share stuff within team meetings and in our own speciality meetings, he was keen to support the request for particular publications

that we'd asked for, um, I think he would have tried to have funded it internally if we hadn't have been able to get some of the books published by the trust for those to be held by the library, um and certainly keen for us to research and be reflective in our work, so.

Do you have personal objectives in mind when you use the library?

Absolutely, I couldn't do my job without accessing, I couldn't stay, clinically within the requirements in terms of time, of entering data and stuff if I didn't have the library space here when all the other spaces are taken because I come here as well, and I know that foolishly I've told other people about it more recently and I'm thinking "that's very foolish" because when I get there basically there will be no desks left, you know, again others like me who don't have a desk space, are desperately trying some to find somewhere to sit.

Do you think using the library helps you achieve trust objectives, by giving you a thinking space?

Yes

Do you feel the library is part of the networks within the organisation?

I'm not really sure I can comment on that, I've always, since I could read been a library user in my own community, so I kind of seek them out in a way, so, I'm not sure if I wasn't already a library convert how and when I would network it into my day, so I'm not sure.

Do you feel that the library knows about other organisations that could support you in your development?

I've not tested it out for that, it's not something I use it for, only so much as being able to use the internet here.

Have you ever come across things you hadn't set out to find in the library?

Yes, the thing that tempts me, which is awful, is the, where I sit to do the computer work, there's a rack of changing books and themes, and I've often reached back and dipped into something..."Oh no no, must put that back", erm, so yeah, that's quite nice because of where it's situated.

Is there anything you'd like to add?

Only something you raised about "do you think other trust staff know it's here and use it and are given time to", as I said, they probably don't, partly because of where it's situated, the distance and the time aspect, and I think that's um, quite sad, when I come in I personally don't see what I think are nurses in here, and that might be because they're not in their uniforms or whatever, but that's a shame really because there's such an encouragement for people to keep learning and do more qualifications and go on this course and go on that course, and so this is an ideal space for them to access all those journals that are terribly expensive to buy, or they can't access at home because they're not on the right internet package and stuff, but I think in the working day, there's just not the space given to do that here. It would be interesting to see who's using it and whether that changes depending on advertising or a push within the trust around the trust focus on health and safety that 16 health and safety books been accessed that month, yeah, would just be interesting to see what the effect is.

Yeah maybe, I know we have a thing about putting things on walls and notice boards and stuff, and I see your point that if you put a poster up in here that said 20% of users were nurses and 50% were doctors, the only people seeing that would be the people already using it, whereas, I think that if you could put it in a space that was more general, or on the trust focus or something that people are asked to share and would cascade down, it might stimulate people to think "ooh 20% are nurses, ooh, are you using the library?, where's the library? You know, it might make a connection to your peer group and you might use it more.

Have you ever used library's fiction collection or books on prescription collection or other resources for your own personal development, not relating to your work?

Yeah, tempted me terribly, but I just thought "ooh, I'll have them and I'll get very confused, at least my workbooks are my workbooks and they belong to this library and my non-fiction and other things, yeah, and I'll end up with a big stack and muddle

Have you ever asked / would you feel comfortable asking library staff about training on "modern technologies" e.g. social media Twitter, Facebook, apps, Kindle?

I hadn't realised you did, and I think my children are desperately wishing I would get that training, because I can't even work the new system in the car, um, so yeah I hadn't even realised, if that's on offer I may well come and ask for some time. I certainly didn't know those services were on offer and I know the trust 'Tweets' and I remember someone saying to me "oh, you need to Twitter more, you need to put

on when something really good's happened" like, "I just met my 'can do lady' and had a great time in eye out patient", that would be in my number of characters, but I wouldn't know where to start to do that and if it meant I need that and could use the training from the library to do that...

Do you find the library a social environment where you can meet colleagues on a different level from other places in the workplace?

I don't come to be sociable in the library, and I like libraries to be quiet, I'm very traditional on that, so if I came in and found lots of people chatting, I'd find that quite off-putting because, especially where this library is located, literally round the corner is an open area where sometimes there's hot drinks and things, and where you can go and chat to your hearts content.

I'm afraid I'd be somebody who would be like um, ask someone to be quiet, or go and ask the librarian, just go over and say "every time I come here it's like, you know?"...I need that space.

And certainly, often when I've been here, there's people that I know in the library, so, like doctors I've worked with or other therapists who have come in and there's a kind of a nod "hello" and then we get down to business and people carry on with whatever they're doing, whether it's sitting on the sofa reading a book, um, and I've gone and got a journal out and I think "ooh hello" to a girl or whether it's a doctor who's desperately loading data like I am, who goes "ooh hi, nice to see you on the ward and then off we go, to our respective work

Again, maybe I've just been fortunate that the people that I've known that have been in the library with me appear to have the same approach, they've come for the quiet and the space, and not to come and talk about work or er, share personal stuff, they come and sort this space for a reason

Absolutely, and maybe I think it's a generational thing, er, having said that, some of the younger doctors still seem to be quite respectful, but then they will have come through education systems where their libraries will have "shh silence", you know, I think sometimes it's a challenge in other libraries where, with the need to encourage younger people to come into them, they've maybe lost some of the quietness that other bit, other generations of the library users would benefit from.

And in those bigger libraries, having just done a whole load of university visits with Jake, we've gone round libraries and, fabulous, fabulous ones, but because they've got the space, and I think that's an issue, they've been able to designate one area as private study area, where the expectation will be that you're quiet and then they've got rooms with doors, which may have glass in them and may still be in the

library context, which are for shared study, the idea being the door is shut and you and your three colleagues that are writing your end of term project can do that with accessing the books and talking without disturbing the others.

I think that when your space is restricted, I'd like to see this library stay a quiet library, not a project library.

And having, and coming in like you know, flicking through the dysphasia thing, and seeing the journals and thinking "wow", you know, um, physio have got their own journal and there's a dysphasia journal, a whole journal, how did they create enough words to fill a journal? For me, it gives me a degree of increased respect I suppose, for those other disciplines and that there are so many other things, other disciplines working within the trust.

Participant 060

Do you have any strong beliefs about workplace libraries?

It's a quiet calm place to come and de-stress yourself amongst a whole lot of knowledge around with a number of books that you find.

Why do you come to this library?

Again this library a few reasons. One obviously is the books that you have, the journals, especially given that they are here so I do come here for my course books quite a lot. Also I have been using the library quite a lot for the meeting rooms. It is quite a good space with the technology available and given IT skill levels here in the organisation (What do you mean by that?) I mean the IT standards I would say generally in our meeting rooms across the Trust. I think you have meeting rooms across the Trust without the amount of technical capability that probably the library meeting rooms have, you know things like the big screens, wifi and then you have the join-in or linked meetings you can do, you can link screens and those are things you can't do in a usual meeting room or anywhere else in the trust so I like it for that. And then generally people are quite friendly and so I've made a few friends so I come here and just talk to people.

Why do you choose to come to the library rather than go elsewhere?

Facilities and the equipment and obviously the place being quiet and calm yes that it what it is.

Last month, how many times did you come to the library?

I would probably say...I can't really well I would say almost every day but in the last month altogether perhaps 2 days a week. I use the library a lot more than I would generally do.

How long do you stay on average?

On average I would spend about 3 hours on an average. That is what we are looking at.

Do you come during working hours and / or during your breaks?

I come during working hours rather than break times.

How would you describe the library environment / physical space?

Again it is very comfortable, it's again quiet. Again because of the PCs and that, the kind of equipments that you've got, it is very capable in terms of meeting my requirements. Erm it is not informal, it is quite formal in that sense. As I am saying that I am trying to explain what I mean. It is not a place where I can come and just say hello how are you because

A) It is very quiet. People are just sitting here and probably studying as well so it is not fair to be loud and chatty in this place so you are always a bit, you would talk only when you have to talk so in that sense it is quite formal so in that sense I am saying it is not informal.

And yeah again it is attractive, it is comfortable, it's quiet.

Do you bring your own books, journals, magazines, reports or do you use library resources – books, journals whilst you are here?

I must say I generally use the library journals and resources when I come here.

Do you use library PCs or do you bring your own device?

I think a combination of both. If the library PCs are available then yes absolutely or sometimes I bring our own laptop, our comms laptop because yours is in use.

Do you use the library wifi?

I haven't used the library wifi a lot I must say.

What would make you come to the library more?

I think I am already coming to the library a lot. I don't think if you do anything more or less it would change the behaviour of mine. I quite enjoy coming here it is a nice environment.

Is it different from other environments in the Trust?

Yeah because it doesn't feel busy, it feels quite relaxed when you come down here. That is the first thing that I see. The thing is it is quiet and peaceful and everybody is with their head down doing their own thing so it makes you feel relaxed when I am walking into this library. Coming from the communication department where people are walking in any time in any minute so I probably get a lot of my work done here if I am logged on to pc here so yeah in that sense it is quite different.

How could the Trust encourage you to use the library more?

By thinking that probably if they opened the library, extending the library opening hours maybe? Because sometimes I am thinking if you are too busy in the working day you probably haven't got the time to sit down and have that thinking time. And that thinking time is sometimes good to have. As a staff member that would probably be quite nice to do at slightly later in the evening. Right now it closes at 5pm but I am guessing that a lot of members of staff work a lot longer than 5pm. With that I think having library staff as well as access to the space after 5pm it's nice. It will make you feel as though you are not the only one here and someone else is responsible for this place and I am here to get what I need whereas when you are on your own you become responsible for that place so again not very relaxing.

Do you think it would be useful if trust policies on the subject of well-being recommended spending time in the library to encourage personal and professional development?

Yes I think absolutely, absolutely. I haven't read the trust policy of wellbeing and I don't know what is there, but if it isn't then I think it should be there. Right now I don't think I can, unless I have a meeting in the library I don't think I will come from my working PC to this office and just sit down because I want some me time here. I don't think I can say very openly in my team that anybody has ever said anything that "I am quite tired, I am quite stressed and I just want to come and sit in the library for a while" because I am not sure how people will react to that so yes if that become part of the trust policy then you can. It's the same thing like if you have flexible working hours and you leave at 3pm because of child care you can get up and leave because that is your right and you can do it whereas coming to the library, I don't have a right to do that so it is always open to criticism and comment.

Is the way library staff behave towards you important?

Yes extremely important absolutely.

Is the way library staff behave towards you different from other staff in the trust?

Yes I mean again I do think it comes back to the library being a very quiet and calm place. It is very much reflected the way the staff behave in the library as well. You can see them extremely calm in the way in the way they ask in help, there is not rush whatsoever, and there is no rush, not in a negative way it is absolutely in a positive sense and they are very friendly, they want to help and they go out of their way to help us in what we want whereas if you go to other areas people are always busy, running and rushing so if you are asking or seeking help it comes in that form, rushed or quickly, so you can feel that stress in that environment and again I think it is that de-stressed environment that helps I guess.

Would a poor encounter with library staff dissuade you from visiting the library again?

Err, if it happens once then maybe not but it happens again and again but at the same time this is the only place, this is the only source to come and get my journals and books I will probably still be coming but might probably speak to the manager and make them aware that this member of staff is not behaving too well. But yes if it is a one off thing I can understand you know? It's a human thing.

Do you have personal objectives in mind when you use the library?

No I don't think I am coming to the library right now to meet my personal objectives. I think I am coming here to meet my professional objectives. And maybe if it becomes part of the trust policy like you said I probably could meet some of my personal objectives.

Have you ever used library's fiction collection or books on prescription collection or other resources for your own personal development, not relating to your work?

Yes I have read some of the self-help books

Do you find the library a social environment where you can meet colleagues on a different level from other places in the workplace?

I don't think so. Again because people come here and the environment is such that is quiet and they just sit down and do what they need to do. So I don't think this is the place you can network with people. That is not what I think this place is for. This is where you network with the books. That is how I see it. And if you have to network with people then you go outside the library and network with the people there. If you know someone then you smile, but you are free to walk away. There is no expectation that you should be talking to that person.

Do you think using the library helps you achieve trust objectives, by giving you a thinking space?

Again I personally have not used the library for thinking space. I have used the library to meet my professional objectives so coming back to what we said earlier it is because I want to get the training done, it is because I can get the meeting room to talk to people or I can get the certain books to read, so I am doing it for that so the thinking time is not there at that time because once you have finished your purpose here you leave. But yes it would be quite nice to actually sit down and have some thinking time. In other areas of the trust, maybe if it is a nice sunny day then sitting outside on one of the benches near the chapel probably. But I haven't used the library to do this.

Do you feel the library is part of the networks within the organisation?

I think you know it is possible like with the knowledge management group. It can be used a lot more. The knowledge within the library is extremely critical. Right now I think it is used more for the clinical people, for the clinicians, you know junior doctors and the consultants. Those are the people who are generally using the library more, I could be wrong but I think that is how I see it. I don't think the management or the admin side of people use the library as much as they should. Your presence in a lot of those meetings like the knowledge management group is extremely important because people need to know a bit more. I am not sure everybody understands that.

Do you feel the library staff know people in the Trust?

Ooh that is an interesting one. If people know the library staff, I think people know your name really and people know, I don't think people know other members of the team unless they come unless they really come here and talk to so their visibility outside the library might be useful.

Do you feel that the library knows about other organisations that could support you in your development?

I think yes.

Have you ever come across things you hadn't set out to find in the library?

Yes I think I have done this a few times with the self help books I think. It isn't that I came for a self help book but came for something else and then I see this nice book let's say on stress management.

Have you ever asked / would you feel comfortable asking library staff about training on "modern technologies"?

Yes probably that would be useful. I don't think that people generally think that they should come to the library to check that. People generally think that they would think of IT and then immediately think of 'they would not be able to help us' and leave it at that.

Do you trust the library staff?

Oh yes absolutely.

Does your Manager support a learning environment within the workplace where the sharing of knowledge and skills is encouraged?

Yes I think so.

Participant 070

Why and how workplace library users utilise library space for non-library activities?

Do you have any strong feelings about workplace libraries?

That they are necessary, really necessary. In terms of here, and where I am, I don't think the library is utilised as much and that is a shame because I think it makes a lovely divide between work and having somewhere to go to whether it is for work purposes or just to take time out. Public libraries are just that, public libraries and so they will stock a whole range of things to cater for the public whereas here it is quite specific although there is lots of introduction to erm, fiction books now which is great and there are specific racks catered for little things and interests of the week let's say. So for work based libraries a lovely idea that it's here, that it is specific to work but this a little bit of public in it too. I just don't feel that this Trust gives it enough resources and utilises it a lot more so it's incorporated in the working day.

Why do you come to this library?

Erm, sometimes I want to look at things on the internet and although I have access at my work station the phone will go and somebody will tap my shoulder and want something. Here it is because its private and no one will bother me and that is the excellent thing about libraries. You will say hello to somebody but they know that you're there for you, probably one of the few spaces that is just for you. So I come here for privacy, to browse, you just have that opportunity to browse. I guess it's a bit of a haven from work.

What do you use the library for?

Surfing the internet, going online but also making use of some of the resources, the self-help books

Why do you choose to come to the library rather than go elsewhere?

Erm, sometimes I find public libraries quite impersonal. Er and I think there has been such a change. Croydon Library was my local one as well as Upper Norwood Library. Both of them have gone through such a change because of cuts that there is something that's lost within them at the moment.

(Could you describe what that is?)

Er, certainly the staffing levels have been reduced and there were some people that I knew who worked there or were familiar and they seem to have all moved on and that has made a difference.

(Did you feel you had a relationship, even a nodding)

Oh yes even if it was just a hello and how are you and it's all gone. I don't know what has changed. It just kind of a feeling about them. Upper Norwood Library, there are a lot volunteers, its run by an initiative now which is great and it's lovely to see that people have got together to get a library and keep it going but, I don't know, there is just a change about them and I can't put my finger on it whereas as here there is some

continuity. If staff so come and go there's still that level of, perhaps because they know that you work here you feel as though they know you in a way. Your time limited in a way because you may come here in your break or you may have an assignment. When I've been using the computers, people have just till the end of the week to finish this assignment and staff have been really going out of their way to think of journals for them or resources online, or help them with the photocopying. So I'm aware they're aware some of us are on a quota of time when were are here. It is different.

Last month, how many times did you come to the library?

Actually that can depend, that can depend on whether. It can be anything from 5 mins; I might be over the PGMC way. I say one of the biggest problems with this library is its distance from where I am. I am over in anaesthetics so by the time I walk over here, er, it changes my dynamic towards it. But I can be here 5-6 times a month or if I am doing something where I might need a bit of research, completely separate from the medical side of things but I just want a space to come in, I will choose to come here rather than a public library so that may increase. It definitely isn't as busy as a public library. It is a really calming space and Upper Norwood and Croydon Library don't seem to have that, although it's quiet, it doesn't feel as peaceful as it used or calming and there is a sense of just being able to sit and take stock for a while here. And whether that's because it is over on this side which is a less busy side of the hospital, I don't know.

How long do you stay on average?

Oh it can vary, 5 mins to longer depending on what I am here for.

Do you come during working hours and / or during your breaks?

I am lucky enough that when an anaesthetist hasn't sat in my seat to have a computer and desk and work from that desk. But I will come over in a break, if I had something that has brought me over this way like an appointment today it is great to come in here afterwards as I have done and just be able to take stock for a while because it is lovely and calming. I would say it is mainly in breaks or after certain appointments.

How would you describe the library environment / physical space?

Really calming. I mean even now in here is exactly how I feel when I am out in the library space. I'd say is one of its downfalls though is, especially in summer is the heat. Also when I have been locked in too there isn't ventilation.

Do you bring your own books, journals, magazines, reports or do you use library resources – books, journals whilst you are here?

I tend to use what is here and that's the great thing about it you don't hav to come with anything.

Do you use library PCs or do you bring your own device?

No, library PCs.

Do you use the library wifi?

No

What would make you come to the library more?

Probably later opening hours. Sometimes I have to leave work early to catch the 5pm thing and get locked because I don't have key access. I would consider the 24 access but didn't know, I thought it had to be relevant in that you were doing a dissertation or something. I thought the 24 hour thing was for doctors and nurses.

How could the Trust encourage you to use the library more?

Again I don't know if its distance and whether placing the library in a more central space. Maybe library sessions for people in the day perhaps being allowed to have a half hour library time off their work whether that would be of any use on top of their break? If they are especially doing course, to have that incorporated in their course time. Extended times where people can come and go could make a difference. Perhaps the trust putting talks on here, they would utilise the space so there was I don't know, yoga sessions over here instead of it being in the gym. Some entertainment, talks or perhaps a drive that is going on in the trust.

Do you think it would be useful if trust policies on the subject of well-being recommended spending time in the library to encourage personal and professional development?

Even though I think there is a wellbeing policy somewhere, that probably in all honestly a lot of us don't read or do anything with. Erm, I think the trust needs to invest a lot more in the well-being of staff anyway. I think this is one of the spaces where wellbeing can be incorporated in a working day because it is calming. In comparison to work and what we have to go through in work, busy, full on and some of the areas are really busy, this is a perfect space for well-being because it's the opposite of that

Is the way library staff behave towards you different from other staff in the trust?

Yes it is. Anywhere where you have had a bad experience with some of the staff it can put you off coming again. I think they are quite respectful here. And whether you are a doctor or admin I don't feel there is a differentiation in treatment whereas in other areas of the trust as an admin person you are sometimes not treated equally because managers, doctors and nurses are treated on a higher level and that is also receiving it too from doctors, nurses and managers, so here everybody is a library user, end of. That is one of the reasons that keeps you coming back.

Would a poor encounter with library staff dissuade you from visiting the library again? If so why?

I think if it was encounters then yes. As a manager you are very approachable so I think if anyone had an issue they could come to you direct and you would deal with it openly and honestly. An encounter, er it depends on the encounter but on the whole even I've come in here and been a bit grumpy as a user. We just have those days.

Does your Manager support a learning environment within the workplace where the sharing of knowledge and skills is encouraged?

I'm in an area that is full of doctors. They are constantly going on study leave or keep up their learning and also studying for exams so for them there is learning in their job and they are actively encouraged to attend things, go to things. I haven't received that kind of push from my managers. So no for me in my post, other than mandatory training.

Do you have personal objectives in mind when you use the library?

Yes, open to using the library for personal development, books on prescription, self-help that kind of thing.

Do you find the library a social environment where you can meet colleagues on a different level from other places in the workplace?

I don't know about meeting, as in meeting up here. I know when I have been here there will be people that I know and we exchange some pleasantries but we get on with our work because it's not the place to have a load conversation. It is unfair on other users. Even the people I say hello are a lot calmer here too. You see a different side to people. I've seen people fall asleep. That is how calming it is.

Do you think using the library helps you achieve trust objectives, by giving you a thinking space?

I'd say the trust has ticked a box in providing a space although it is undervalued and it isn't incorporated in your working day.

Do you feel the library is part of the networks within the organisation?

Er yes and no about networks. I think the staff connect us here but I am not sure if other areas connect it well. Staff would know other people and who you were talking about. The staff are part of the organisation.

Do you feel that the library knows about other organisations that could support you in your development?

Because I haven't asked for that I don't know but I am sure from when I have been sat outside at a PC that they will point people in the right direction.

Have you ever come across things you hadn't set out to find in the library?

I'd say it was the books on prescription now. I've been here for years and it is only now I've started to stumble on. Whether that is for personal reason I am unsure and I have sought them. It is great to see arts and medicine being represented here which I didn't think it would be. You'll start with one thing here and end up with another rack!

Have you ever asked / would you feel comfortable asking library staff about training on "modern technologies"?

Actually if I knew it was available I would because sometimes there is a fear with new technology. If I knew that resource was there I would probably ask for it.

(Do you feel that you know enough about what goes on in the library?)

No, I'm sorry to say it. I'd love a more informal session. IT are IT here. The sessions are not informal. So a drop in session which would take into account that, whereas IT doesn't, you have this amount of time, pop in when you can. People learn differently and I think the library would give a wider variety of learning styles.

Do you trust the library staff?

I think so. I've been on the wards and heard nurses gossiping about some of the visitors. I don't feel that would happen here in that "so and so has just asked for this journal". None of that. This is the request, let me try and deal with it and off we go.

It's calming; there is no element of judgment. It is your time. You don't feel as though you are wasting trust time or money and staff giving me judgmental looks to that effect, no none of that.

Anything else?

In terms of online resources I don't think the trust lets everybody know what is and what isn't available. This is just I guess, our space and you know you can go to the canteen and have a quiet cup of coffee but somebody will join you. You can stay here for the day; you can stay here for 5 mins. It is that kind of area. As a user it would be great to have more space and perhaps the sofas in a different area so people don't fall asleep in front of a PC user! Ventilation but I think most areas of the trust that is a problem. The area I work in is a really fortunate area; it has a common room, PC room, a tiny library at the back, an office and then a consultant's office. Unfortunately I'm in the reception part so eat my lunch, answer the phone, do my work in this area and I don't have half an hour where I can switch off.

Our anaesthetists though, if their lists have finished early, or their not being bleeped will go into one of those rooms and they can be there for 2 hours, eat, drink, watch TV, be merry and it is purely for them and anaesthetist only really. So coming here for 5 mins, 10 mins or half an hour is the equivalent for me. I think their roles and they too consider themselves higher than my role. They can be quiet selfish with space and they can't be here like every other library user because you are treated in the same way, this is everyone's equal space. This is purely subjective in that they are very selfish with space because even though they have all

that space they will still come and stand behind me or behind my colleague and chat, and you are trying to answer the phone, you are trying to do typing and I don't think they have that right here. When I am trying to do typing, having a full on conversation behind me is distracting. One of our former anaesthetists came in yesterday to get some paperwork signed off. We asked him how things were going at his new hospital. He said it was great except we don't have this common room and it really makes a difference so imagine how me and my colleague feel.

In Outpatients when I worked there was a common room for the admin team but it really wasn't a space away from work because the other admin staff would be there and you were obliged to make conversation. In Training there wasn't until we moved into a bigger area which has a lovely common room with a TV but again you are sharing it with colleagues. Retinal screening wasn't great because your retinal screening room was also your break room so in those areas I wasn't getting away from work, department or from patients. If patients saw you sitting in there with the door open for ventilation there would be lots of huffing and puffing why can't you do me now because I'm early and I can see you sitting in there. And you did you felt obliged to stop your lunch. You felt you didn't have that right to have a break. And here no one can judge, you are in a mixed environment, mixed as in lots of different staff, not your colleagues who will defer to asking you things even though everything is in front of them. Sometimes with common rooms, ok I am going to speak to speak about my common room as it's the bit I know the best, it is a very selfish environment because the upkeep and the cleanliness of it will go back to me. I feel they are very lucky with the space they have. Now the consultant can have utter privacy which 9 out of 10 of them won't use they will either come and sit at my computer and I mean I have just gone to the kitchen and they have sat at my desk. They've got so many resources and they come and sit at this reception part. I might want to go and sit in the consultant's office of which I can't, and get on with my typing; they will choose to come and sit in my seat and chat to my colleague or come and quickly use the internet on my PC. Maybe it's social but I have an issue with the way I am seen in my work environment. There is an element of like it, or if you don't like it, leave which is something I have heard often. There isn't "let's look at your working environment, oh gosh yes, there is no air coming in, what can we do to make it more pleasant experience" it's disappointing. It's a tick box exercise all this wellbeing and I am sure they will have wellbeing groups that doesn't filter through to the everyday.

Participant 080

Do you have any strong beliefs about workplace libraries?

Yes, I mean, I use the library personally as respite from the hectic work of the ward, and more importantly for a reflection on my activities, so in a way I do it on a daily basis, the library is first friendly atmosphere and I do this at least once a month, and in between, I use the library as a more relaxing, although I am reading and trying to find information on the internet, I could find other places, but the library is the best, more relaxing to be in.

Last month, how many times did you come to the library?

I almost come three times a week, if not sometimes four times a week.

How long do you stay on average?

I stay on average, two hours if I have time, but sometimes just ten minutes if I have to see patients, then I'll come back and I do some of this reflection on the internet and books, it works for me as a focus for further ongoing reflections.

How would you describe the library environment / physical space?

The environment is quite friendly, the personnel in the library, they are very helpful, almost to invite you to ask them and to do all the library services for you, and also the copies are always ready and they also have this service of selling old books and things and it's quite enriching especially for people who like to collect these things.

Do you bring your own books, journals, magazines, reports or do you use library resources – books, journals whilst you are here.

I only bring some material if I want to do copying, because this is, as far as I know, the only place for people like me to have the scanning of material.

Do you use library PCs or do you bring your own device?

Do you use the library wifi?

I haven't started yet, not for any particular reason.

What would make you come to the library more?

I think to have access to material that would help me in my everyday practice.

How could the Trust encourage you to use the library more?

I think there will be a record of the attendance somehow, logged automatically that could be subject to checking, that would be one of the encouragements.

Secondly if they expand on the number of the computers and also to use one of the computer only for library purposes rather than for education.

I think they should provide an educational venue somewhere else rather than the library

Do you think it would be useful if trust policies on the subject of well-being recommended spending time in the library to encourage personal and professional development?

For sure, I mean, one of my profession requirements is to have the CPD and part of it is how much you spend time exploring literature and reading journals and so on, I think because of the financial constraints these days, I think we have to share these resources.

Is the way library staff behave towards you important?

Of course, it is the most important.

I have had an experience in the past that will be some intimidation because if you ask for a book and things and the attitude in a way that intimidates you, then you feel you are asking too much, and that you are asking people to do more work and so on, I think in this library particularly, it's so friendly, as I said before, they almost invite you to ask.

Is the way library staff behave towards you different from other staff in the trust?

I think nowadays there is a universal good behaviour everywhere, thanks to direction and training and so on, but in particular the staff - I don't have work relation as such, it is indirect - that's why the attitude...I think mutual attitudes, more friendly, more relaxed.

Would a poor encounter with library staff dissuade you from visiting the library again? If so why?

Of course, we are human after all, and er, whatever we push through to achieve our goal, the emotional side of it is important, and as I say, intimidation and indirect intimidation and not being friendly of course.....

Does your Manager support a learning environment within the workplace where the sharing of knowledge and skills is encouraged?

There is no agenda but I am sure when it comes nitty gritty, with the direction of the trust, the training, education, interactions, it would be encouraged.

Do you have personal objectives in mind when you use the library?

Yes, to get informed, gain more information.

Have you ever used library's fiction collection or books on prescription collection or other resources for your own personal development, not relating to your work?

Yes, I did use them just to see what is there and what my colleagues are reading and it would be great if you could have some information on how many of which publications are used.

Do you find the library a social environment where you can meet colleagues on a different level from other places in the workplace?

Not really, I'm of the opinion that in spite of not putting constraints on people communicating and things, whatever, I think there should be quietness, this is important, so people should not really use the library as a social environment, especially when they whisper that's fine, beyond that it gets very irritating

Do you think using the library helps you achieve trust objectives, by giving you a thinking space?

As I said before, reflection, informed reflection obviously is very important, and I think being in the library reflecting on patient care with access to standards and what other people do is a great

Do you feel the library is part of the networks within the organisation?

Definitely, because I see general doctors, I see nurses, I see midwives, I see administrator coming into the library and that's a very good thing, of course, when they go out of the library, they refer to these activities and thus will be part of the network.

Do you feel the library staff know people in the Trust?

Yes

Do you feel that the library knows about other organisations that could support you in your development?

Yes, I mean, recently because I'm attending the course on public health the library have responded very beautifully to bring all the material that's needed, or most of it, that's needed, and they are helping you thinking about how to do analysis, to redirect you to books, websites, which is really, by itself is a fair thing.

Have you ever come across things you hadn't set out to find in the library?

So often I come for something and I see something else, it's stimulating, it is appetising, it is almost like going to the high street to have some food and you would choose from different things to which you had not thought of initially

Have you ever asked / would you feel comfortable asking library staff about training on “modern technologies” e.g. social media Twitter, Facebook, apps, Kindle?

Definitely, yes, I trust them very generally, and their helpfulness and general information that they supply, so they are very honest in that sense, and then the way they provide the facilities is really great, I could see at times when the ceiling is dripping water and how quickly they put the bucket and asked people to take care, in that sense, also they sympathise with the customer, it is very important.

Do you trust the library staff? If yes, why?

Yes

Anything to add?

I admire the people who work in the library who work to improve the library and always asking and discussing ways to fulfil this.

I have seen libraries in small villages in Scandinavian countries. I think, in that sense, there is a lot changing the atmosphere, but hopefully, when the economic crisis finishes. The ways I look at libraries and book shops and public libraries with the different functions and different populations, though nowadays, I mean, medical library used to be for doctors, but nowadays you will find students, managers, which is really good, it's expanded the role of the medical library, but in the public libraries of course but there is an overlap I think, and er, which is great, and now it's a very sensitive issue, people want to close them, but I think there will be a reaction to that, because people are getting isolated and lonely in spite the connection with the faceless whatever, so the library firstly, gives you a sense of belonging, you would know who is reading and what information is shared by who and that's why and it's important, and I think the pendulum will swing back to more interaction, more library interaction from people because though you are dependent on internet and books, classroom and that and this, that's the way nowadays people educate themselves, action, learning, online and library, so we learn as we go, and that's one way of touching shoulders with other people, to see what they sometimes have interaction, depth and insight.

(Interviewer asks about wifi & internet training)

Indeed, I'm sure you are approaching people that are new, or in training, and perhaps you would presume people like me that are old in the business, but that's the other thing, this is the place where we are

not very conscious about what we lack and possibly I think I would be less intimidated to approach for help. lets face it the population changed and are practicing in modern ways, and they need this unconscious sort of lack of confidence and learning and education, and I think, as one of those people, I would appreciate to be told about what's available

Participant 090

Do you have any strong beliefs about workplace libraries?

Yes, they're really necessary, it's where you can get some solace instead of the hustle bustle of your work place. It's the reason I came and when members of my family and myself started having problems, it was a good place to sit down and read and take it all in quietly, so yeah, I think they're essential to be perfectly honest.

Why do you come to this library?

Because it's the only one in the hospital. And it's the closest, we deal with each other every day and it seems a natural place to come and spend your dinner hour.

What do you use the library for?

For quiet contemplation and to learn what's wrong and what can be done, when, like I had both knees replaced, was a really good place to come and ask people if they could put you onto the literature, and if they had an article that they knew about, that they could get it for you, and you had a lot more understanding about what was going to happen to you when you were under the surgeon's knife, which I found extremely helpful.

Why do you choose to come to the library rather than go elsewhere?

I could have sat in the car which I have done for several years, but um, once somebody had told me how quiet and relaxing it was up here, before they left the hospital, I thought I'd give it a go and I've been doing it for about four and a half years now. For quiet, you can't get it anywhere else, literally, if you go to a canteen or whatever, it's just hustle bustle, and people walking past saying "hello" or whatever, where, there's only about three people that say "hello" when you're here.

The only time I interact is when people are next door and they start making use of their mobile phones or they're just talking too loud, so you just say "I'm closing the door because I don't want to hear what you're talking about".

Last month, how many times did you come to the library?

If I'm not working downstairs, basically every day.

How long do you stay on average?

Three quarters of an hour to an hour.

Do you come during working hours and / or during your breaks?

Yes.

How would you describe the library environment / physical space?

It's comforting to have a place that...I suppose it's a bit like the chapel, you can go there, just relax and gather your thoughts, but you can do that in a totally different way here.

Recently, I found out my brother needs two heart valves and it was comforting to know that you could go to a section, pick out a book, and you could read what it was about, and it was just so quiet you could think about what you were reading and how it would affect you after, you told them because they're scared stiff, but if you can get a photocopy or whatever, pass it on, it's just a natural process.

Do you bring your own books, journals, magazines, reports or do you use library resources – books, journals whilst you are here.

I do both to be honest, a young lady lends me her paper every day, but when I need to go and use the library, for magazines books whatever, I know they're readily available. Probably once a week I'll read the journals.

Do you use library PCs or do you bring your own device?

No

Do you use the library wifi?

No, simply because we've not been trained to use them downstairs, and they've only just after twenty years decided that we can have a PC. They didn't see any point in us having one before, now we've got one, I tried to get onto it last week and it wouldn't even let me in.

(Interviewer asks about communicating with rest of the hospital)

People come and ask, the chief exec comes and asks you what's going on in the hospital, because as you're walking round, everybody's telling you their woes and whatever.

I think I've actually talked one woman out of committing suicide three times, which was quite an interesting...you kind of did it without knowing you did it, just through talking to her and listening to her and thoroughly getting involved in a way you didn't know you were doing.

I suppose in a way you'd call it a kind of counselling, but talking to people that do use the library, you find that you can pick up on bits and pieces that you can use in your own life and help other people.

What would make you come to the library more?

Not having to work so long, to be perfectly honest.

How could the Trust encourage you to use the library more?

I think you could do with a slightly bigger library, where it's situated isn't the ideal situation. You could probably do with one of the old type of wards that's long and not really used any more to give you the extra space, but you really could do with being on the ground floor.

Do you think it would be useful if trust policies on the subject of well-being recommended spending time in the library to encourage personal and professional development?

Yeah. Definitely.

Is the way library staff behave towards you important?

Oh yeah, but you should be behaving the same way as you would expect them to behave toward you.

Is the way library staff behave towards you different from other staff in the trust?

I hope not, I have had quite a decent rapport over the years I've been coming here with all the staff, and I'd hope to think they treat me exactly the same as they would treat anybody else.

I mean, that volunteer you had grief with a few weeks ago...that woman is impossible, but the way you handled it or whatever, er, seemed perfectly adequate for what she was griping about, which was nothing. Was just a shame, because she can be a very pleasant woman, but she just gets a bee in her bonnet if somebody hasn't said "thank you" or the right way to her, in her thinking.

You can't help people like that, you really can't.

Would a poor encounter with library staff dissuade you from visiting the library again? If so why?

No. Because it's become part of my life, and we are so hectic downstairs 24/7 basically, I've found recently, that when I go home, I use the sleep apnea machine and, although I know I'm asleep, you know your brain is still active and it doesn't actually switch off, so when you can come to a place like this, which is moderately quiet at times...does drive me up the wall people hitting the keys on the computers too hard, because they are loud, but if you can shut your eyes for ten minutes in an environment like this, a lot of strain and stress just seems to ebb away that you don't seem to be able to do while you're at work or while you're asleep at home, it's a totally different environment.

Well I've only ever found any of them (*library staff*) would only approach you if they needed something from you like picking your brains because

they didn't know X, Y or Z, which is exactly the same if I ask, but no, I find them very helpful

Does your Manager support a learning environment within the workplace where the sharing of knowledge and skills is encouraged?

I haven't got a clue. I'll be perfectly honest, I've never had a manager turn round and say, other than what you have to do for courses to keep your wages...I've never had one that has turned round and said, "I think this would be an advantage to you".

Like the computers, they didn't want us to basically have a computer because that would put us on the next grade.

Do you have personal objectives in mind when you use the library?

Just to unwind. As I say, there's two or three people that you interact with as you come in, you acknowledge they're there, you obviously say "Hello" to the library staff, but it's just to unwind.

Have you ever used library's fiction collection or books on prescription collection or other resources for your own personal development, not relating to your work?

Yes. I haven't used books on prescriptions, but I have used the other library books as well. I'm not a particularly fiction person, so I do find, if I haven't got something to read, you've got that piece of the library you can go to and find something that's worth reading, even if you just read a chapter or two a day, it is worth acquiring.

Do you find the library a social environment where you can meet colleagues on a different level from other places in the workplace?

Yeah, I mean, you can actually talk to doctors where you couldn't...Where we used to have the social club, if you felt like having a pint after work, you could go in and physically sit in the same room as a consultant and you'd end up talking to one another, the same thing is similar here, I've never met a consultant or doctor that wouldn't say "Hello" or wouldn't enquire how you are and whatever, but um, it does get up my bosses noses that I can actually interact with 95% of the consultants on first name terms, they always think it should be Mr / Mrs whatever ...

There's probably 3,500 people in this hospital, I probably know over 500 by their first names and probably 2,000 by sight alone that you would acknowledge one another as you're walking past, except junior

doctors, they seem to think they're above everybody else and they just ignore you...until they want something.

Do you think using the library helps you achieve trust objectives, by giving you a thinking space?

Um, A lot of the trust objectives, I don't actually don't get round to using, because I'm not interactive with the patients and whatever, but we do probably about 50 times a day, get asked where X,Y & Z are, and even doctors, consultants, managers come up to us and say "you should know where so and so is" and 99 times out of a hundred, we do. I mean, I was the only person here who knew where every photocopier was.

Recently, they had a new contract with all the water suppliers, and I knew where all the only ones that weren't being used were being stacked away, because you walk past them every day, and finance came down and asked us where we thought X, Y & Z were and we could give them 80/90% of where they were just by walking past and observing what's going on...which most people don't you know, in an environment like this.

When I think someone's looking for somewhere, you normally watch their heads and they're going like that (assumes motion) and there's a good chance if you turn round and say "Are you looking for somewhere", they're going to say "Yes", as you say, most people walk along and they are in tramlines.

Do you feel the library is part of the networks within the organisation?

I think it's a totally necessary part of the fabric of the hospital, because without it, most of the doctors wouldn't get where they are today. The likes of me and other people like me, who need information, get a very good result by just being able to ask. It's like the post room, it's like a heartbeat in the hospital that you need.

Do you feel the library staff know people in the Trust?

Probably not as well as they could do, nor should do, because you're fairly isolated, where, if I'm stuck in the post room, I'm fairly isolated. I've got a 20ft area to walk around in where..you've got a bit more space, but you don't really get out and about to see where places are.

Do you feel that the library knows about other organisations that could support you in your development?

I would hope so, I'd be very surprised and worried if you haven't.

Have you ever come across things you hadn't set out to find in the library?

Yeah, the interactive bit with the fiction and the other stuff with other libraries, I did find that strange at first, but there are times when you just

want a space and you don't want to be indulged in heavy reading, and it has to be said that the medical library is heavy reading to say the least, where light relief is enjoyed, greatly I think.

Well, a while ago, I actually saw somebody walking along, that I knew someone wanted to speak to and they walked past that persons office, and the door was open, and I thought to myself "It's much nicer to talk to somebody", e-mails are so non interactive, and that's half the trouble in this place, there's not enough interaction between managers and what people do, there's too many managers that are coming in and trying to work this place like a factory, and it's not a factory, it's a hospital, and I think we've lost that sign that we're here to help people and not rush people through the system.

(interviewer dialogue about library use / hospital interaction)

Oh yes, pace is a lot slower, but you interact when you want to interact, you're not forced to interact and that makes a big difference in the minimum time that you've got for yourself. I normally start at say, quarter past eight, and leave at quarter to five, and other than that hour, you're pressurised to do X, Y & Z and I've just had a row this week with the admissions people because my boss says he'll do one thing, you know he's not doing it, but he doesn't want to rock the boat, and I find that very awkward because I would just turn round and say, "no, there's a cut off time for that size of letter", and we have to take figures and he will...if they turn up 20 minutes later say Yeah, I'll do that for you" but you know he's going to put it on the side, so yeah when they come down and say "oh, the other guy does it, why can't you do it?".

Oh, it has to be, I mean, when I had the chief exec supposedly walking round with me doing the rounds, he was so negative, saying "we haven't got the money for this, we haven't got the money for that", but a new manager will turn up and when we mention this to a certain manager, she turns round and says I haven't got enough managers to manage the managers, and I just thought "how Dads Army is that?".

Have you ever asked / would you feel comfortable asking library staff about training on “modern technologies” e.g. social media Twitter, Facebook, apps, Kindle?

I hadn't even thought about it, but that would probably be a very good way of upgrading to be a 'silver surfer' on mobile phones, and I've got part of the technology, but it would be very helpful if there was somebody else who could tell you "well, this is what you can do with your phone to pick up this information and all of this, that and the other, without having to go to a PC and whatever.

(interviewer dialogue about policy and development)

Yeah, that would be tremendously helpful.

That would be an absolute godsend, to me personally, but because I didn't know you could ask, I never thought about it.

Well at the moment, you've got a radiographer out here and you've got somebody from the path lab and they're interacting, you do get an awful lot of nurses, even nurses that have retired that come in and do voluntary work or whatever, are keeping up with whatever's going on by spending an hour or two a week in the library.

You do notice, there's probably a hard core of about 50 people that you see on a regular basis, that spend a lot of time here.

Do you trust the library staff? If yes, why?

I've never found them anything other than trustworthy, and there are places in this place that do a similar sort of service that you think to yourself "Yeah, am I asking the right questions of the right person?"

It's a nicer atmosphere here, I think a lot of things that go on in this place are down to atmosphere, and the people that are there are producing that atmosphere, I know you've lost half of your staff recently, but you've never stopped having that atmosphere where, even if they were stretched to the limit, you can ask something, and you come back with a polite answer, and it makes all the difference.

Anything to add?

Yes, you've given me with an insight into some of the stuff that I didn't know you provided, so I shall try and use it to the best of my ability.

Participant 100

Do you have any strong beliefs about workplace libraries?

My personal opinion of libraries is that they've been extremely useful throughout my whole academic career, it's helped me with studies, basically everything.

Why do you come to this library?

Currently I'm using it for my dissection course and now I've transferred to St George's, I still come over because some of my work is here and I know the staff who are extremely friendly and they're willing to help, so that's why I come back, another reason is that, for me, with the computer system, it's always available for me, usually at the medical school, the students have taken the computers.

What do you use the library for?

Why do you choose to come to the library rather than go elsewhere?

For me, because it's convenient, I know the staff well, they're always willing to bend over backwards just to help me and it's also to visit other staff from other departments, it's just a friendly atmosphere.

Last month, how many times did you come to the library?

It was every day. As you probably know, you've seen me every day.

How long do you stay on average?

Do you come during working hours and / or during your breaks?

On average, it's usually my lunch break, so you're talking just under one hour.

How would you describe the library environment / physical space?

Physical space? Now that I can compare and contrast with another hospital, I personally think this library should invest a lot more money into what's available, because certain books that are used, I've noticed are either out of date, or some of them were actually missing, which I don't know the reason why, even though we've looked for them.

Much more computer space. I also disagree with blocking certain e-mail access because, for me, I need to send information from one hospital to another, or from home and I find it inconvenient with USB encrypted, I can appreciate why, because of patient confidentiality, but that is the only thing I would say negatively about the CUH library, because sometimes, you just can't get your work done, I'm not the only one to say that, some of my colleagues have said that.

Do you bring your own books, journals, magazines, reports or do you use library resources – books, journals whilst you are here.

I use the hospital and I also use the internet, bringing my own material, I can't because it's encrypted, so there's no point me bringing items over, and some of the books I do have to use in the hospital library, or even the medical school because CUH just doesn't have the information which I require or that have actually been missing.

One example is, I did a case study on a prostate cancer patient, and the volume I wanted, it was 1234, I wanted 2 and volume 2 was actually missing, so that's one example.

And I also noticed, from my own experience, the medical school has about 20 copies, while this hospital has just the one, and I think there should be at least 2, if there's one on loan, at least there is one for staff.

Do you use library PCs or do you bring your own device?

I use library PC because some of my work is on hospital net, but unfortunately, I have considered bringing my own PC, at the medical school, they supply staff with PC's and I've noticed that, with even more students, they have about 20 plus laptops for their students, and I would recommend that here, because the amount of times I hear, "why do you have to bring your own", so that's one example.

Do you use the library wifi?

That is a no, because we know we're being charged, I know it's only pounds, but it's the principle of the matter, whereby ,at St George's, it's completely free throughout the whole hospital, NHS & medical school and it really is a place of learning, so why are we paying to use a service when we're actually working here, so it's out of principle, not out of costs, I really think, and my colleagues say the same, why are we paying for something that we work here, and now we go to another hospital, everything's completely free.

What would make you come to the library more?

What I've just mentioned, for me, I live in South Croydon, actually going to the public library where you have to queue, here it's just distance wise, it's just so convenient. Unfortunately, there's a lot of barriers stopping staff such as myself using it to it's full capacity really.

How could the Trust encourage you to use the library more?

I think from what I've just said, because, without being too rude, I don't think higher management understand what staff of all levels here require, they just think, it's a PGMC or a UGMC, that's great, but I think they'd have to use it, or be on an actual course to understand what we require, because a lot of what I require, isn't available to me, so that is one factor.

I only come here because I know the people, the PC, and you guys are willing to help me, you're always here to help me, so I think really it's more of an issue not of staff, yes there could be more staff, because you guys are stressed, but the staff are, what can I say? they're perfect,

it's really the infrastructure what goes into the library which is the biggest problem, and again, going back to what I've said before, it is just what everyone says.

People who I know who are of consulting levels don't even use the library anymore because it's just...they're wasting their time coming over here, so that's another thing, and these are consulting level, let alone my level.

Do you think it would be useful if trust policies on the subject of well-being recommended spending time in the library to encourage personal and professional development?

Yes

Is the way library staff behave towards you important?

Well, I've never had...the staff here have always been great to me, they treat me like one of the family, I can't see any complaints to be honest with you, I've been here for ten years plus and it's just been such a...I come back here just to say 'Hi' sometimes, I don't know if you've noticed, and it's again, staff wise is not a problem, yes there could be more staff because that's for your benefit, but it's just...just looking round now compared to the medical school, it's just...even my own department in my own block probably has more books than here, I'm not exaggerating, because sometimes you just think...I know it could be better, it's just possibly higher management will have to come down and have a look themselves.

Is the way library staff behave towards you different from other staff in the trust?

No, because you guys are great, and possibly, I know a lot of other people in different departments, they treat me the same, even now if I needed some help...I was going to go to my department, (inaudible) you've actually saved me time, luckily the work was there so I was able to do this, but yeah, the books, they were just there wasted, you helped me with that one...so yeah.

Would a poor encounter with library staff dissuade you from visiting the library again? If so why?

Yes, I mean, yes and no, because if you get a negative image, you will always have a negative opinion of the person or the persons, but I don't think it would stop me because at the end of the day, I'm still on the course, I do still need library resources, but I think it's still important, I think very important.

Does your Manager support a learning environment within the workplace where the sharing of knowledge and skills is encouraged?

My manager didn't, she actually deterred, because she didn't want to spend money, and we all got very frustrated. It took me forever just to get on my course and it's wasted some people's time when they didn't even have the opportunity, luckily for me, but once the manager left, things started rolling, so

my old manager sort of stopped people from learning because she didn't want to spend money, which is, we just thought...we were just shaking our heads. and it took HR and managers higher up to say "this is getting silly, none of your staff are X,Y,Z," and a lot of people have been frustrated from my own department and, I was just shaking my head..."you need us, why are you stopping us?"

But then we knew why so then yes ,I didn't have much support I'd say.

My new manager, yes, she's great, she bent over backwards, forever grateful for that, so yeah.

Have you ever used library's fiction collection or books on prescription collection or other resources for your own personal development, not relating to your work?

No I haven't. I was really concentrating on my course.

Do you think using the library helps you achieve trust objectives, by giving you a thinking space?

Yes, everyone is entitled to knowledge, I've not noticed anything since I've been here, yes you see some consultants studying here as well, but I wouldn't know how it worked if it did.

Do you feel the library is part of the networks within the organisation?

I've made many friends through the library, so in a way, beside learning and gaining knowledge here, you also make friends here.

Do you feel the library staff know people in the Trust?

Yes, I've had experience where certain library staff have asked for help from other department.

Do you feel that the library knows about other organisations that could support you in your development?

I would say yes, you guys advised me to go to the British library when you didn't have a book, so you guys know your stuff, yeah.

Have you ever come across things you hadn't set out to find in the library?

Yes.

Have you ever asked / would you feel comfortable asking library staff about training on “modern technologies” e.g. social media Twitter, Facebook, apps, Kindle?

No, I know how to do that.

Do you find the library a social environment where you can meet colleagues on a different level from other places in the workplace?

Yep.

Do you trust the library staff? If yes, why?

Yes, because, I think it's built on years of trust really, and years of seeing each other. I come in to learn, you guys actually give me the trust, you guys are willing to help me etc, get me journals in the past, I would say it's more you guys putting towards me rather than the other way round, so yes.

Participant 110

Do you have any strong beliefs about workplace libraries?

No.

Why do you come to this library?

It depends really, if you look historically, I would perhaps be prompted to come to the library because I'd been doing a course, so there were reasons there, those reasons aren't applicable now because I'm not currently studying, so they were important reasons why I came because your team are always so helpful when I was doing study part-time and didn't have very easy access to the university library, so this was convenient, and also there were very big libraries when you're doing things part-time, you don't get to know the library so well, the people there, so everything takes much longer, this was a smaller library, people knew me, so it's much easier to come in and access people, talk to people, express what I needed and get a response.

What do you use the library for?

It's very unpredictable because I'm so busy in my work. I often start the day and think "I must pop by the library" and I'll bring something that I want to read and I'll come here because it's a quiet space, I like the low chairs, they're a bit more comfortable on the legs, sometimes I put my feet up, and read something work related, so that's kind of an unplanned visit. I quite like coming and dipping into things like the health service journal, might pick up the one on dementia, so again, unplanned, trying to do something that's not work unrelated, but just gives my brain a bit of a different space, it's sort of relaxing.

Why do you choose to come to the library rather than go elsewhere?

Because there aren't very many spaces, I would go somewhere like the chapel because that's another quiet space where there aren't too many people, but the chairs aren't so low and I like the sense that the chair is comfortable when my legs are down all the time, makes me sound very unfit, I'm not really, but when they're hanging down all the time, you know, your legs don't feel so comfortable, at least when you're lower, you're more comfortable.

And other places, if you got to the main restaurant, they don't want you to sit in the main restaurant in the comfy chairs which are lower and unless you've bought something....You can go down to main reception, again, there's sort of more standard chairs there, I have gone down there as a different space as well, but I tend to feel I ought to be buying something, so the library is quiet...

I think in general, you're not interrupted about work, although one time I was, someone spotted me and it made me think twice about where I sat in the library because they spotted me, and they came in and told

me to do something and I went back and I immediately did that thing for that person because they were senior and that individual never did anything with it, and I thought, that's interesting.

(Interviewer dialogue regarding 'private space')

I think that's right, now you know me, and I think you're always very respectful of me, and I appreciate that. Sometimes I come in with the Bible sometimes, and I come in and take my shoes off and I put my feet up, never have any kind of breaks because we eat at our desk, and I get to half two in the afternoon and I think I need to just try and relax a little bit for a few minutes, so I come in and do that, and I appreciate the way you don't interrupt me, I know that if I came knocking, you'd say "ooh, no, no, come on in" so that's really what I'm saying...there's that sense that...and I see other people in here and I would never ask them about work matters, you know, I wouldn't even interrupt them to say "hello" unless they looked at me and smiled and quietly said "Hello" Yes, that's right because if I went to the main restaurant, everybody...that's kind of like a space where people can come up to you and interrupt you and say "I'm really glad I've seen you here, can I just mention X or Y?"

Last month, how many times did you come to the library?

I've probably only been four or five times, and I want to come, but when you're so busy, and sometimes you're under so much pressure that you aren't come, and I brought in a book this morning that's about... it's called 'Brilliant Manager', and I've read it in the past, but I wanted to read it again, but here we are, and it's ten past three and I actually had to ring you at two to say "I won't make it for two" because I brought that book and thought "if I can only get ten minutes, I'm going to go and sit in the library" I knew I was going to get into work really early, and I debated about reading at home and I thought "No, you've got so much to do, get in early" because that book, you can read when you're feeling tired later in the day, but I won't get in here today. But it's not through lack of will, it's like a reward almost. In some respects.

How long do you stay on average?

Between ten minutes and half an hour.

Do you come during working hours and / or during your breaks?

Yes.

How would you describe the library environment / physical space?

Calm. Peaceful.

I think it's quite difficult to describe because I could sit in my office, I could lower my chair a bit, I could shut the door and the team wouldn't

disturb me, but I'd be surrounded by all this work I've got to do and the computer screen, it's not the same, it's that different physical location and quietness.

And you can have space around you, because there are less people in here in a way, so you feel a sense of space, and it just takes you away somehow from the intensity and strain of what your working in, even if you actually haven't got people physically at you all the time, um, it feels like that.

Do you bring your own books, journals, magazines, reports or do you use library resources – books, journals whilst you are here.

Mostly I'm bringing my own, occasionally I think "ooh, I'm now interested in this or that" and I will come in and get a book, but I don't necessarily generally read them here, I tend to get them here and take them away. So when I'm coming here, I might, because I know I've got my journal with me, I can bring it and sit in another space, it's something I don't have to sit and look at a computer.

Do you use library PCs or do you bring your own device?

Rarely, and on the occasion when I've used them, I've used them to try and get a bit of space away from the intensity of the environment that I'm working in, I have an office within an office, it's quite a small office, I've got no complaints, I'm grateful for it, but it feels...some of it's almost psychological, you can be interrupted at any point, phone can ring, e-mails are coming through, even if you try and switch e-mails off, um, hours and hours and hours of that. It's a lot for the brain to cope with, so if I can come here, it's almost as if I can sit and look at all my e-mails and try and read through some of them and clear some of them, respond to them, but I don't have all the other sense of stimuli coming in quite the same way, so that may be a help for me to concentrate on a job that needs doing.

Do you use the library wifi?

No, on occasion I come into you and have talks to you about it, about using it, I think it's one area that I haven't really mastered that I would like to and that would be to be able to come in here at any time and be able to look at webinars, there's lots of material available, especially in the States, where I'm a membership of the professional body, I could never sign in at the right time because of the time-zone difference, but to be able to just come in and be able to sit and read webinars...I mean, it would be lovely to do from the desk in my office if I could do that, and I think, partly again, it's the time, because as I've said to you, my visits here are so unpredictable and there are so many competing requirements on my time, that again is almost like a luxury.

What would make you come to the library more?

If I was less busy. If I was less busy, I would come and bring work that I would like to work on to maybe do some more of that innovation development that often I can't do because I'm pushing paper around that has to be done at a desk because there's so much kind of e-mail work involved and maybe accessing different files that are in a shared drive.

So I feel I would come here more for innovation, for moving on and progressing, not me personally, but actually me and infection control.

How could the Trust encourage you to use the library more?

I think it's a; about the whole time/pressure thing, all the sort of short staffing in different areas, sometimes people have such a huge workload that it doesn't permit you to use the library more.

Do you think it would be useful if trust policies on the subject of well-being recommended spending time in the library to encourage personal and professional development?

I think from what I've said, in terms of it helping my well-being, I come here to help my well-being, so when I feel I've had seven/eight intense hours, this can help my well-being because it's just some place I can just sit and process things in a different way, maybe not work related, so that's important for my well-being. Helps manage stress, helps cope with stress.

Everybody should be doing personal and professional development.

Much of it, to be fair, can be accessed from a computer and that's the way you're expected to access it, but speaking personally, it's quite difficult to do it when, at your work environment, you're under so much pressure in the here and now. If that makes sense?

Yeah, and I'll tell you what I'm debating about at the moment, I feel so under pressure at work, and the volume of e-mails, part of my professional development and updating, and partly for the benefit for infection control here, or very much so, is I have the Croydon house service journals link that comes through that gives me feeds from infection control journals.

I have another one as well, the IV forum, and I'm under leadership one and I'm...infact I thought I'd cancelled the leadership because I just couldn't um...(inaudible) e-mails, but I'm seriously thinking about cancelling both of them because I'm not able to deal with them and look at them which I want to and it worries me that I haven't cancelled them yet because, professionally and for the good of the organisation and the way I work, I should be keeping up to date, but I'm bombarded with so many other e-mails, that I'm in danger of not responding to the trust

e-mails because of these other e-mails that are there almost getting in the way.

Is the way library staff behave towards you different from other staff in the trust?

I don't know how to answer that really because the library staff are always polite and friendly, but there is wide variation around the trust in how people behave to you there, and people can be nice and friendly to you there, but you can also deal with people that are not nice and friendly, behave in different ways

But that's a requirement of every member of trust staff, part of our registration as a health care organisation is about quality and diversity, and many many staff like nurses have their code of conduct, so people may not be adhering to it, but...

Would a poor encounter with library staff dissuade you from visiting the library again? If so why?

Yes. If I felt somebody was unhelpful and a bit abrupt with me, yes.

I suppose to be fair, it might affect me not in terms of coming and putting my feet up and reading a piece of work I've brought, it would affect me in whether I asked the library for help for anything in particular that I thought they might be able to help me with.

If someone wasn't being particularly helpful and then I came in and asked them if they've got a book about something then I wouldn't bother to go back, I think that's probably true in many walks of life, if somebody's not very nice to you in a restaurant then you don't go back there.

Does your Manager support a learning environment within the workplace where the sharing of knowledge and skills is encouraged?

No idea. My relationship with my line manager has always been quite distant and I'm not sure if this is in their mind or not.

I would go and have one to one's, explain any difficulties, they would help me unblock them, we haven't talked about this though. So I couldn't really answer fairly on their behalf.

Do you have personal objectives in mind when you use the library?

There's that unconscious objective to help me cope with the stress and the strain, so much about coping when you stay and work in this environment.

So that's my objective.

Have you ever used library's fiction collection or books on prescription collection or other resources for your own personal development, not relating to your work?

I never realised there were books on prescription, I'd noticed there were lots of books on depression and things like that and I wondered why there were so many of them.

No I've picked them up because I've never struggled with things like depression and they didn't particularly attract me those books, and I've noticed the fiction, but I'm just too busy to read fiction, but I have noticed it with "ooh, that's interesting, some fiction", but life doesn't allow fiction.

Do you find the library a social environment where you can meet colleagues on a different level from other places in the workplace?

I don't regard it as a social environment, I almost come here to be alone.

I come here for peace and there are one or two people in here, and I see them regularly, maybe at lunchtime, and I think maybe they've come here for peace as well, I can relate to that, I'm not going to disturb them. I respect them.

Do you think using the library helps you achieve trust objectives, by giving you a thinking space?

No, not directly, I think it probably helps the trust in a sense by helping people to cope and have the stamina to stay in the job, then the trust wants to retain its nurses, that's good.

Do you feel the library is part of the networks within the organisation?

No, not particularly, It's not that I mean I don't think you're not part of us, I don't see you as part of the network in the sense of when I come in you're somehow helping me to network, because I think what I like is the separateness, and it's the separateness that's the attraction. In fact, you're quite convenient for my office, if you were in a different building, it might make it even better, but I don't think it would because I often want to go to the chapel and play the piano, but the distance of having to go outside stops me, so no, I like almost the sense of separateness.

Do you feel the library staff know people in the Trust?

I know that *you* do, but I don't know about your colleagues. That's because we chat informally about things and it's clear to me that you interact with different people and you do know people.

Do you feel that the library knows about other organisations that could support you in your development?

I'm not sure you do, but I'm not sure that's necessarily a right kind of assessment to make. You helped me get books for my masters, but that's all really, it's something about the space, the separate space that I think is the real mark for me.

Have you ever come across things you hadn't set out to find in the library?

Often in the past, not so much recently, I've picked up books about management and other topics, sometimes I've taken them and I haven't really read them, but I think they've kind of floated through my mind, maybe dipped into them briefly, so yes, especially if things aren't on the shelf but new books are out and visible.

Have you ever asked / would you feel comfortable asking library staff about training on "modern technologies" e.g. social media Twitter, Facebook, apps, Kindle?

Yes, I would always feel happy about asking. I've never asked because of time, I've got so much to cope with and so much to do I'm struggling, so I didn't want anything more to do

Yes, It's so exhausting, I've got an i-Pad, and I use the it a lot for work related studies, well, not work related, but for my university and I find that quite an effective way of reading things, I'm not using it for Twitter accounts, that sort of thing, It's for reading electronically, and I can read better in that form, but when I'm at work there is just so much electronic stuff, it is exhausting, I can't cope with any more.

It's not necessarily face to face interaction with a person, it's stepping away from the myriad of computer generated information and material. It's too exhausting, there's so much of it in different forms, on so many different topics, that you're almost distracted by one so you're trying to do so much multi-tasking, each one needs you to dedicate time to it, but you're surrounded by bits of paper you've printed off, you have a telephone which can bring more messages, potentially a bleep, but I'm trying to put that t one side, so it's this combination of information coming through on e-mail, information that's electronic that you have to review, comment on, darting about on the internet, darting onto the intranet, looking in the shared drive, I mean, I'm not thick, but the pace you're dealing with is hour after hour after hour...

One of the things I do like to do, and I don't do it here really because of the lack of space, is that on my own days off, when I've not got work to do, I would go to a coffee shop and I would have a bit of paper with me, I might have my i-Pad and notebook, but I actually haven't got that computer screen there, I'm not sat in that upright position looking at the computer screen, again, it's a different space, and perhaps you are relying on technology, but not quite with the same intensity.

You're absolutely right, because it's not home, and there's some drawbacks in being at home, there are other distractions there, it's not work, it's that third space, available for work, but not available anywhere else in the hospital. So no pressure can move you on in the same way...

Do you trust the library staff? If yes, why?

Yes, I would trust them, I would never have thought of the idea that you might particularly tell other people what I'm looking for, but then I suppose I never come about things that you told anybody about. So in terms of trust, it's not something I'd ever regard.

Anything further you'd like to add?

Only really I guess to say that my colleagues have said what a valuable space it is, and the organisation would be unwise to say we don't need this space, it's not a good utilisation of space when I really think the whole well-being thing, for those of us who know it's here, it is a valuable way to help well-being. That may not be why the library is here, but that's why some of us are using it.

Even with the WebEx and things like that, and that discourages you when you haven't got the time to learn all these things, if you're not naturally 'techy', or respond to the technology and you're not sure if it's the technology or you...

I would perceive IT here very much as busy, stressed, short staffed, appear to solve, to focus on the here and now, can we access patient data? Rather than actually having the capacity or time in their brain to innovate and help with those types of aspects, that'll be the cherry on the cake, they might want to, but realistically, I think there's more likelihood that the library has the potential, not that you're not busy.

It probably helps your staff that you're working so hard that probably helps you to feel calm, because you've got the space and the quietness, so people aren't coming in and having intense conversations about problems.

I'd love to work in this environment all the time. It's not the place for managers to come in having spotted somebody.

Participant 130

Do you have any strong beliefs about workplace libraries?

I think they are important. I think they offer resources that probably aren't available in other areas of the trust and expertise which aren't available elsewhere. And I think they are quite central if we are a learning organisation, it's quite important that we offer that resources which should be quite extensive and it needs to be for all staff not just nurses and doctors.

Why do you come to this library?

This is the only library I am aware of in the trust. It is positioned quite near a public eating area so I think a lot of staff are aware that it is here if they use that area but then it is only on one side of the trust. So in a way a lot of staff may be totally ignorant that there is a library on this side of the Trust. I know where it is. Sometimes have to request journals and articles for my boss who is a senior director in the trust. I sometimes come to use it for my own learning if I am doing a course. I come to use the pcs. And I have used it for WebEx as well as this is the only facility that I am aware of that is easily accessible. The trust only has 2-3 areas and 2 of those are in director's offices and is very hard to set up but here is it easy and you are supported by the library staff and yes, it's a quiet room for you to hold it.

Last month, how many times did you come to the library?

Erm, I think I would like to come a lot more to be honest. I think I should be using it a lot more. I would probably come between 3-4 times a month.

How long do you stay on average?

It really depends on what it is for. If it for WebEx I'll be here for at least an hour, an hour and a half. If it is just to pick up a book or return a book then it will be very quick. If I am looking for a book I might stay half an hour. It is variable.

Do you come during working hours and / or during your breaks?

I never come out of hours. Erm, I don't tend to come here to take a break but it is a lovely space in which to take a break because it is quiet and peaceful.

How would you describe the library environment / physical space?

It is maybe what you've got in here for such a small space really. It is informal I think and comfortable for staff. It's quiet, peaceful. It is welcoming cos you have lots of information by the door. You have a really helpful team. It is somewhere you feel you can come and just be yourself and not be watched and you have a bit of freedom.

Do you bring your own books, journals, magazines, reports or do you use library resources – books, journals whilst you are here.

Generally to use resources but actually I have done that before if I have needed to edit a film I have come here because it is quiet. It's great here to concentrate.

Do you use the library wifi?

Yes, actually that is a very strong drive to come here but on several occasions it hasn't worked and that has put me off from coming back which is a real shame. I think it is a massive draw for me to use the wifi especially to do a lot of uploading of videos to YouTube and things that we can't do in the normal trust, you know high security trust internet uploading things.

(How did you feel when you couldn't access the wifi?)

The only other place is at home. I end up doing it in my own hours at home so that is a bad thing. It's just disappointing because I know when it works its brilliant. It is a brilliant space to use it in. Just to add that the wifi anywhere else in the trust that you have to pay for so this is the only free source of wifi in the trust. And for staff there needs to be some spaces that offer this. Come on this is 2015 there should be places where you can have free wifi; it is not really fair that staff have to pay to get full access.

What would make you come to the library more?

If I knew the wifi was definitely working then I would come more! It is on the wrong side of the site. I am based opposite. I think it is a long way to come over here for my break, that is half my break gone when I get here. If there were more events I would definitely come to the library and that might spill over into my work life that I just use this space and see it as my space that I come to and use.

Does your Manager support a learning environment within the workplace where the sharing of knowledge and skills is encouraged?

They don't but they do encourage my self-development so maybe management need to be promoting the library more and engage with them more about the resources available. I mean only recently I found out just from chatting with the library manager about some things that you do in the library which I was totally oblivious to and some of that was on staff wellbeing and since then I have definitely taken books out that are of interest to me. I think you don't remember the library is here unless you've got reminders to use it.

I don't know how you feel about this but I sometimes think that if you are seen to be in a library just reading a book that you are seen as skiving and the fact that it is very essential in your role to be researching or picking up a book and reading especially as some users use it as a rest area it does reinforce that the library is not somewhere where you do your stuff you do extra stuff outside your job.

How could the Trust encourage you to use the library more?

Maybe, I don't know really. Flagging up different resources that are in the library at induction or on particular course that we do or health and wellbeing. You know just feeding it into more of the trust structurally.

Do you think it would be useful if trust policies on the subject of well-being recommended spending time in the library to encourage personal and professional development?

Yeah definitely. I mean I know the trust has to document the work we do around wellbeing for staff so are we not feeding into that already? There is something the environment of the library, it is not corporate it is more stimulating and somewhere where you come to get away. For the environment we are in it is a very unique space.

Is the way library staff behave towards you important?

Oh definitely, it's all about your customer experience, coming to the library and how welcome you feel. I think some of your staff are more friendly and engaging than others and it really comes across and it does let the experience down sometimes.

Is the way library staff behave towards you different from other staff in the trust?

Those codes etc you mention, you encompass those. When I come into the library you immediately engage me in things about what's going on and what do I need whereas some of your other team members don't do that so much. I suppose I have partitioned you off from other staff and you are right it should be the same values that should apply. We do see you separately I think.

(Why is that?)

I guess you are like neutral aren't you actually. You are a bit separated from the politics and also bound by your own values that is for the greater good.

Would a poor encounter with library staff dissuade you from visiting the library again?

Erm yes potentially I think it would cos if they're are not helpful or I might choose to do my work at home instead of coming up to speak to someone who isn't helpful or defiantly in terms of showing me what is

available in terms of resources. I would probably come up on a different day.

Do you have personal objectives in mind when you use the library?

It isn't a space you come to talk is it really. I personally use it if I have a learning objective for myself but how often I do that I can't say I don't do that very often, I should do that. More professional than personally.

Have you ever used library's fiction collection or books on prescription collection or other resources for your own personal development, not relating to your work?

I don't think I would use the personal ones although I would be encouraged to go in my own library and seek them out because I would be too embarrassed to be honest. But I think it is great you are doing that for health and wellbeing. I probably wouldn't take them out because of the lack of confidentiality.

The fiction too I probably wouldn't to be honest. I have a kindle; I download everything on the kindle. I don't tend to carry books around with me.

(You know we can send articles to your kindle)

No I didn't know that! That's great! Do staff know about these things? Unless you seek this out you wouldn't know about this.

Do you find the library a social environment where you can meet colleagues on a different level from other places in the workplace?

I don't because it isn't an area where you can talk. Not really. There is a small meeting room so it's very useful to use the WebEx. So social through WebEx.

Do you think using the library helps you achieve trust objectives, by giving you a thinking space?

Oh yeah definitely; absolutely.

Do you feel the library is part of the networks within the organisation?

Oh yes, you are very attached to education, medical, clinical groups more so than other staff groups so not so much admin. My previous roles have been admin and clerical and I don't think I came up here particularly.

Do you feel the library staff know people in the Trust?

They probably know a lot of people, yeah. You seem to integrate yourself and team in other things as well.

Do you feel that the library knows about other organisations that could support you in your development?

I'm sure you do I am sure you've got all that information! If I needed to find anything out I would probably here as a starting point.

Have you ever come across things you hadn't set out to find in the library?

No not really. I think on a notice board there are all these interesting stuff and I probably would have a wander around every time I come up here just to see what's happening around the area. It would be helpful if things were highlighted more then I would be more likely to use the library more.

Have you ever asked / would you feel comfortable asking library staff about training on "modern technologies"?

Oh yes obviously Kindle!

Now I know you have that resource I will definitely be asking more advice on it. I am fairly literate on most of the other things. I wouldn't necessarily see that as your role though actually to advise on IT. Our trust policy sort of discourages us to use a lot of social media without it getting signed off first. You have to be very careful and stuff. I think a lot of people know what Twitter is but they don't know how to use it properly and well.

Do you trust the library staff? If yes, why?

I think it's just personal; there is no privacy and dignity in the library.

Everyone can see what you are doing. It's quite open the library isn't it.

I would trust any staff member whether you are a library member or not but I wouldn't share with any member of staff.

Participant 140

Do you have any strong beliefs about workplace libraries?

Erm I do because I think they are a really important part of the NHS as it is a learning organisation and so I see the library as you know, one particular aspect of that. It's got a lot it can offer in that sense. So it should be place where people can come and learn and share really.

Why do you come to this library?

Because I find the staff welcoming. It's on route to where I go and take lunch usually. I am reassured, for me it's like a quiet space so I see a synergy between the library quiet space and a time to reflect so that is why it's important to me. My diary is marked out usually between 1-2pm saying where I am going be which is PGMC.

What do you use the library for?

It's looking at the health service journal, er and in particular just around some of the reflective bits just to get a bigger picture of what is happening within the NHS generally. So the health service journal arguably is the most widely read of all. I would choose that above the nursing times.

Why do you choose to come to the library rather than go elsewhere?

I see the PGMC, because this is a university hospital site, I see this very much linked with, and I suppose it's just about the learning aspect which I'm really passionate about. The NHS learning as a learning organisation, we might say we are a learning organisation but how does that translate in practice? It's about behaviours, so I like to be visible, I come into the library.

Last month, how many times did you come to the library?

I come in pretty regularly maybe once or twice a week. It's face to face contact.

How long do you stay on average?

Erm it depends actually. If I pick up the HSJ it's going to be a minimum of fifteen to twenty minutes. Erm, sometimes if I get more involved then it might actually be a longer period. Occasionally it might be a shorter interaction, it depends really. I might be looking for this journal, can you locate this article and I know you very kindly sign post for me. It really can be variety so the time I am here depends on the time I've got and the nature of the particular project I'm working on.

Do you come during working hours and / or during your breaks?

It can be any actually cos if I'm coming through the library, I see the library as no different from any other department in other words I can in and I don't differentiate between coming in the library and having interaction with the staff in here to any other aspect of my work so, for me it's quite perfectly legitimate for me to come in as I have come in today. I'm a senior manager and I am quite happy to take a seat on the comfy chairs in visible

full view of whoever is walking by and they can see I'm looking at a journal and I'd be more than happy to be challenged on that because I will give a clear and concise reason. If others want to see it as skiving I will give them a clear and concise reason that I am not and thus far no one has asked me but I am mindful of that. I suppose that is why I sometimes deliberately sit in a prominent position because it is quite legitimate for me to be there. I do it in that way rather than hide away outside.

How would you describe the library environment / physical space?

Erm, I visit libraries at the weekend and spend typically half an hour in there choosing some sort of material and also looking at the newspapers and the like. I've got a real empathy and endearment towards libraries; I think they have a valuable, societal benefit. It's a really good idea that libraries exist and not, if you like, become extinct because I know a lot of libraries are because of the changes in technology. So in this case here I just see it as a natural thing. I know candidly that a lot of money is going to be spent on this library and it is pretty obvious. You only have to look at the environment to say well, if you were to score it let's say, out of 10, er you would probably be hard pushed to give more than 5 out of 10. It's got to affect the way people use the space. Is it fit for purpose? A library environment which is now in part currently as we talk today 2015, we've got basins on the floor ready to collect water which are a health and safety hazard. 5 out of 10 is pushing it really. We do need to make the environment safe, we do need make it fit for purpose, and we do need to bring it up to the 21 century. There is a lot more that can be done really.

The business case has been approved and looked at so from my perspective it can't come soon enough really. The money being spent will really transform the service. LIA will suggest something, when doing a business case, what will the end user want and then you build your thing around that really. What is the opinion about our services? How will we know we have a better facility so questionnaires will be useful? We should be aiming for 10 out of 10 and if we fall short then how will we know we've fallen short?

Do you bring your own books, journals, magazines, reports or do you use library resources – books, journals whilst you are here?

If I come in here I want to be seen to be using library resources rather than bring my own in because it will almost be, I'm not saying this as a slight, I am thinking why would I want to be bringing in a Guardian or a Times let's say and sit and read those in here when they have not been provided by this service.

Do you use library PCs or do you bring your own device?

I think only on one occasion and that was basically to log on to the resource which escapes me. The clinical one, the clinical resources that's available.

Do you use the library wifi?

No. I wouldn't naturally think of that erm, what might encourage me to use that is if we move towards tablets. Some of peers are trundling around with technology that is enabled and they can get wifi wherever they are, and they are already logged on and I'm not in that bit. I think the roll out of IT, ipads to senior managers and the like, I think it should be rolled out more. What would be quite interesting is, think about this one for a second, is that I was offered to do a webinar (?) recently because of the software package that we have and the organisation that provided, we pay a fee to this organisation but it looks as though I'm going to have to cancel the webinar because we haven't got a pc or laptop that is enabled. Our IT systems block it.

(You can probably do it here) Oh maybe this is another conversation I could have then about trying to enable it, so if I can say that I want you to do a webex maybe for Friday (you can book it in, the IT room or you can book that room opposite as well). I might make some contact about the webex.

What would make you come to the library more?

I think maybe more the environment. Maybe and just see, the whole thing needs reconfiguring really just to open it all out and make it more welcoming. It needs the wow factor. You want a library that is vibrant and used and you know, encourage people. I see you've got the drinks thing going there but there's probably some other things that could be done to make it just, you know, a little bit more, maybe more of a message from the director level as well. Does visible Wednesday include coming to the library?

How could the Trust encourage you to use the library more?

I think there needs to be more of a steer, there needs to be an engagement by the Board, clear statement within a policy document, within the annual report, within the Board agenda to say what a valuable resource if they haven't already done it.

How does that too work in the community if we are an integrated care organisation what is the relationship, is this library about CUH site, how does the other sites, they may not be able to visit but can they draw on the resources? You can engage with them and about communication side of things.

Do you think it would be useful if trust policies on the subject of well-being recommended spending time in the library to encourage personal and professional development?

Most definitely yes however I would probably use a different narrative which is not how much time you want to spend in the library but what a valuable resource it is, this is what it offers and then some examples of how it is helped other professionals. We do so much around the physicality of people but the emotional needs are important and they need to be met and arguably the most important resource we have is the library to do that.

Is the way library staff behave towards you important?

Most definitely. So you have a bad interaction as you do in life, you tend to avoid especially if it's a negative reaction, you tend to avoid that situation that might actually mean avoiding that location, so it's crucial is the long and short of it.

Is the way library staff behave towards you different from other staff in the trust?

I think I'm pretty well placed to give a view about that. I currently do audits of all the departments so I know exactly the nature of those departments. Then library is all about not being rushed, not being fazed, the staff don't rush me. Contrast that with an audit or inspection where it is for a precise amount of time, it is much more time bound whereas coming to the library, you know, I'll come to library for as long as I need. That kind of answers things in that bad experiences are rare here. And days happens, I have poor encounters on the wards but return nonetheless. Time and pressure factor into things. People change under pressure and without resource. Contrast that to here, sense of calm and wellbeing.

Does your Manager support a learning environment within the workplace where the sharing of knowledge and skills is encouraged?

I've got a new director so I don't actually know what he really thinks about that. Erm, they need to be a bit more appreciative is that there is elements of my job that would lend itself to home working, using a PC to do evidence based practice, so ok, so er, that's again part of the learning thing so let's look at work as also not just about CUH and the community, but I've often done work from 2 hours before I come in to work and then pinged in on an email. We need to look at how people work. It depends on who the manager is but some staff work from home and others don't. There ought to be more of an understanding around flexi working. The culture of the organisation, are we a learning organisation? We might say anecdotally that we are or where's the hard evidence to support it, so learning is an integral part and a fascination of what I am about, understand more.

Do you have personal objectives in mind when you use the library?

There can be both but I suspect...the real drivers to use the library are understanding more holistically what is going on in the NHS. I don't do it intrinsically for CUH, I think you put yourself first. I put myself first before everyone else on the basis that if I can put myself first I'm better placed to look others really, whatever that might be. Everyone is different of course.

Have you ever used library's fiction collection or books on prescription collection or other resources for your own personal development, not relating to your work?

Never used those. It raises the point though that who is the principle users of the library? And I know that all junior doctors for example they all have to do audit. They all should be doing audit and revalidation. Rightly or wrongly there might be a sense of it's a university so we need to be clear

in that what's that about. Is it about medical and nursing colleagues principally? I dip in because I consider myself loosely as an allied health professional. As long as my needs are met, then I'm quite happy to use the library really.

Do you find the library a social environment where you can meet colleagues on a different level from other places in the workplace?

Not really no. I don't see how that would evidence itself now. Hopefully that's an objective for the new library.

Do you think using the library helps you achieve trust objectives, by giving you a thinking space?

It does in that sense but I think it needs to do more.

Do you feel the library is part of the networks within the organisation?

I've no sense that you do, but that said looking at who is in the library I get a sense of who is coming in and why they are here. I get a sense that it's probably a spike in the matrix of people doing these Postgraduate diplomas that might encourage them to come here. I know a lot of staff get management days in the wards. Now how that relates and translates, it may be an opportunity to understand who benefits from that.

Do you feel the library staff know people in the Trust?

I think you do

Do you feel that the library knows about other organisations that could support you in your development?

I would have said yes, obviously though our professional liaison that I can draw upon you as a well-grounded and well informed resource about I might tackle things differently so yeah in that sense I know you network.

Have you ever come across things you hadn't set out to find in the library?

Yes I have. There have been times I have come in looking for, er books on a piece of research on something and when I was going through the hardcopy library, the sections, because the library is indexed in such a way you can find links to other resources and linked information in different parts of the library.

Have you ever asked / would you feel comfortable asking library staff about training on "modern technologies"?

Not particularly. I mean I've got a twitter account, don't use it very often. I would probably be more inclined to use family than ask. So not necessarily. I know the trust has a social networking type policy stance on the use of social media, erm, about using it responsibly. So beyond that, no. I know John's got a blog and stuff like that but I sense it's still in its infancy and I suppose really we know that people make faux pas with putting stuff on social media it is probably its best to err on the side of

caution rather than get heavily involved in that. It's rather stick with the traditional email rather than go to social networking

Do you trust the library staff? If yes, why?

Yes, yeah, yeah. All that track record and evidence is that you've been able to sign post me a lot quicker than I've ever got there. Erm and that freed up my time more and yep, the bond of trust is there. So that is the expectation and it's fully realised really.

Participant OH

Do you think it would be useful if trust policies on the subject of well-being recommended spending time in the library to encourage personal and professional development?

Yes, I would agree with that, people do need time to unwind, they don't often get enough time to take breaks anyway, and when they do, they need to maximise the time that they have in the best possible way they can, sometimes being able to download and just chill out, but also they might have business things they need to do that relate to stuff that they're worried about at home, they might need to make phone calls or private texts which they can't do anywhere else, and also they may be doing studying and need time to chill out or somewhere to actually do some research.

But also getting away from the working environment is quite a good idea in the middle of the day and a lot of people can cope better with the rest of their working day if they can chill out somewhere and somewhere quiet where they can gather their thoughts more easily. When people find it, it's like a sanctuary.

...That was very much what was coming across and also the fact that there wasn't the expectation that they had to talk, so although there was no uniform, when they were there, they were just a library user, and where someone might nab them in the corridor and say "don't forget to send me that report", but there was almost an unspoken understanding that once you're in the library, you don't, you lose your authority almost...

Bit like being in church

...and they were saying exactly the same thing, that they either go to the chapel or the library and that some people said that the chairs weren't very comfortable in the chapel...

Can't imagine pews are particularly comfortable.
I'd imagine, when people find it, it's a bit like a sanctuary.

...Yeah, that's what they were saying, and my question really is, I've looked at all the, er, I've read the well-being policy & framework, and I know we used to have quite a lot around wellbeing ...

We had a well-being group which unfortunately, about the time that I started in the trust, which is September 2012, the chairman left and we did have trouble finding a new chair.

We did get a new chair from one of the surgical teams, but due to pressure of work it was actually quite difficult for them to chair, and we couldn't get any other buy in, so basically, I was advised by my director, deputy director, that there didn't appear to be an appetite for well-being at this time in the trust because of the pressure from, er, all other directions,

particularly in respect to winter pressures and the recruitment processes that were ongoing and the fact that we were struggling to keep staff etc, the health and well-being agenda has fallen off the horizon, because I did rewrite the health and well-being improvement framework policy / guidance and there were some things in there I needed to update and I was advised basically not to worry about it at the moment.

...And how do you feel about that? Are you able to comment on how you feel about that?...

Privately? Between you and I, it's one of the reasons I'm leaving, that the trust doesn't take health and well-being, doesn't take health and safety, doesn't take...

I just don't feel that they're investing in the staff in the way that they should and the only thing that they have invested in is the flu campaign, which has been for me and my team, has been an issue where we spend nine months of the year here bullying and harassing people to have something they don't want, and then I feel I'm bullying and harassing my team to deliver something that people don't want, then I'm being bullied and harassed to deliver something that I can't deliver because I can't get management to buy into it because there's no commitment.

There's no commitment from the trust to do it at all, and not in real terms, not to deliver it to the 75% clinical staff they want it to be, so under those circumstances, actually trying to deliver something that's completely undeliverable and then being bullied for not delivering it, I mean I haven't told anybody that I feel I'm being bullied for it because there's no point to be honest, and that's because there's a financial penalty if you don't deliver on 75%, but there's no financial penalty for not investing in health and well-being, which if the trust were demonstrating that more effectively, then maybe people would be more inclined to take on board the other initiatives that they've got.

...That's so interesting, because I looked at the figures, which I think I got correctly about days lost due to stress last year, and that's the biggest absence reason...

Far overtaken musculoskeletal, used to always be musculoskeletal, was the top one, but it's not now.

...And from my limited view, which is very limited, I can see that people that are coming in, they're not coming in because they want to get a library book out, and that's what I'm trying to measure...

They need downtime.

...the intangible things, because when people say everything's online, actually that's not what people want and what people are saying is that the library staff take control of that area, so you've got a relationship, and

someone else is in charge and you don't have to do anything, it's controlled...

That's right, can't be interfered with.

...Exactly, and we don't measure that in any way...

It's just a perception.

...Exactly. And the people that come there have that perception, and I was curious of your take on that, that's definitely what's coming out. And to take it to the trust, and say, you know, an investment, however small, is beneficial to staff and there's not a lot for staff...

No, there's not, and what we tried to put into place hasn't really materialised, obviously we have the gym, they did invest in the table tennis table, and that kind of thing and they are supposed to be enlarging the gym etc, and as far as I'm aware, that's still in the process because I was in the gym committee up until last year and they did have plans in place and funding to enlarge the gym, but we do have things like the Pilates class and things like that and other health and well-being things that are available, but we're not very good at promoting that kind of thing, I was in the process of doing an accreditation with the mayor of London on health and well-being but part and parcel of that is having a health & well-being improvement framework which we don't have in..it wasn't ratified, the things that I wanted to put in it, expand in it, I was basically told to focus on other stuff, so, that's been a bit unfortunate, what I still plan to do before I go, is get the things that I want to get in, in and I'm very happy to add the library into it, if you can come up with something in terms of what you see it needs to be within that framework, I'm very happy just to add it, because it's still got to go to consultation anyway, so.

...When's the date for that?...

There's no date, because up until before I leave, which is end of April, yeah

...Because one of the questions I didn't ask you, we have books on prescription, what GP's can prescribe, and they're in the public library, about stress, anxiety, self help books, you know, and some people do take advantage of those books on prescription, we also have fiction books at the library, just to give people a kind of different perspective, for a bit of downtime.

I sent some stuff through to Sally last week on what is occupational health and what occupational health does for organisations, and said could we promote this so that people have a better understanding of what occupational health is because I don't think may do, and I just got back "well, we'll do that when we get a new manager".

...I would agree with you, I don't really know what occupational health is and it's of huge interest to me, as I say all the reading that I've done around public libraries, everything, just shows, that if you use your public library it can improve your well-being, and it's good to be part of the network, and that's the other thing that I'm looking at, that when you come to our library, obviously it's a much smaller space, but you're seeing things in a different perspective, and you're maybe connecting with people on a different level which is beneficial...

Well, we did have, the trust have bought health and well-being program that never quite made it onto the intranet because it only ran at the time, it only ran on Chrome which we couldn't host, so there was quite a lot of problems, somebody bought it and, I don't know, it was before I arrived at quite a lot of expense, and there was quite a lot of work to be done on it which never made it in the end, Emma Jones was helping to push that forward as well from HR, and then she went on maternity leave and then the chap that invented it, a doctor in occupational health, and a lot of the information was great, but it never really happened, another investment that died a death really, unfortunately.

...Is that still available

It's still something that I'm sure he would be willing to redevelop, but we haven't heard from him in ages and because there's been so much other stuff going on I mean, I had a period not long after I started, I lost my band seven, took me a year to get a new band seven, just before she came, a band six went off sick, she was off for a year so some days, very rarely, but occasionally, it's just been me here.

. that happens to me, with losing my staff, and you just have to do everything...

Doing the day to day stuff.

...And do you feel that the health and well-being agenda is one of the first things that goes when times are tight...

And yet, you've got Epsom & St Helier, I was talking to the occupational health manager there and the director of HR put a massive business case forward for them to have a whole new post at just dedicated to health and well-being

...That's great, has that gone through?...

Yes, it's all done, they've advertised the job. I know it's a bigger trust, but it's all proportionate isn't it, and there isn't the appetite for that kind of...and I think it's penny wise and pound foolish in the fullness of of time, because it's all very well saying "we've got an

occupational health department, that's it", but if you don't let me get on and do the things that need to be done, or I'm actually disabled from doing the thing that needs doing, and all I'm allowed to do is focus on things that are non statutory, like flu is a non statutory requirement, whereas statutory stuff, where we're required by law to do certain things, there are certain things that we haven't been able to do that have gone by the wayside, which is completely wrong.

... It's a long day for staff and I'm very conscious of the fact that we try to support personal development like you say " they may need advice about things that aren't just related to work...

Well, occupational health is about keeping people at work, but for me, it's about whatever is impacting on that person's ability to work, a lot of occupational health authorities don't see it like that, but I see it as completely holistic inasmuch as "I've had people I've looked after in the past where they've not been able to work, so I've had a situation where a lady was struggling to come to work, she was really in a difficult position, and part of the problem was that she was worried about her daughter, she couldn't give up smoking because she was worried about her daughter, because her daughter couldn't get a job, so while she was in the department with me, we went on the NHS job site, and there was a job there that her daughter could do, and as it turned out, her daughter got that job and she and her daughter gave up smoking, so it's not just about looking at that individual, it's about...

...It's the blockages isn't it? and I think often we have people that come into the library, their IT skills aren't brilliant, they've been told to do this, it's all online, people still have to negotiate, it's stressful, and they get stressed about that because they can't face it...

One of my big issues, one of the biggest issues I've had are the commitments to health and safety, the commitment to health and well-being, the IT infrastructure here which is a complete balls up, and things like, I've been going on about the lack of health and safety risk assessment training managers, because the whole underpinning risk assessment process for the trust just doesn't exist, it's not there.

And the problem has been a real headache, and because of my position, I actually do have some responsibility for that, but trying to get somebody to take responsibility for that because it underpins everything else that's going on in the trust, all of the risks are dependent on managers performing risk assessment which they don't have any idea what they're doing, they don't know what they're doing, they don't know when they're supposed to do...when they're supposed to commit it, there's no training to do that, there's an e-learning package, just done my head in to be honest, it's taken two and a half years to get it, and I've been banging on about the fact that there should be a rolling, continuous programme to train all managers how to do risk assessment.

It's a fundamental part of their job role, a fundamental legal requirement within the trust structure, risk management, and it's not happening, and it means that we are not compliant, and whether we're papering over the cracks all the time, day in, day out, which is what we're doing, sooner or later it'll go off with a big bang.

.. Lack of staffing, higher targets, whatever it might be...

Yeah, Could be anything, that's perceived to be a risk, because it's not just about health and safety risk, infection control risk, manual handling risks, it's about the financial risks, it's about the stress risks, it's about whatever is a risk to the organisation or to the individual should be on there, and it should be recorded because we've got a system that will manage it all, and that will give us data, that's what it's designed to do, but there's nothing in it.

And do you think that...

We have a datix but they give you really broad things, there's no indication how you got there in the first place

To break it down into stream... because I think staff engagement is so important

Part and parcel of the process, something happens, there's an outcome and there's a resolution and somebody comes up with a solution, none of that happens.

I do worry about staff who do 12 hour shifts, there is no break for them, no restrooms like there was in the old days, no restaurant that will sell them hot food, there's a machine that will spit a cold sandwich at them if they forget to bring any food if they're lucky, there's nowhere for them to go and eat that quietly, there's a cold hard chair in a dingy restaurant, there's no comfortable place to go and get away from it all, just let everything...I don't use it (the library) because I'm lucky enough to have my own quiet space here.

And I think that's reflected with the consultants as well, and the doctors they have their own space

(General thanks & sign off)

Appendix 4

Coding frame

Code number	Occurance	Code segment	Frequency of segment occurring at least once in a reply
1	030 q14 080 q1, q3, q22 050 q1, q18 090 q3 140 q3	Reflection / Reflective	8
2	090 q1, q4 080 q1 070 q2, q29 130 q18, q20 050 q2, q4 110 q8, q10	Respite from work / Haven from work / Rest area	11
3	030 q15 080 q1, q4, q15, q16, q17 060 q2, q15 100 q2, q3, q24 110 q	Friendly	12
4	030 q2 080 q1 060 q12, q13 050 q8 090 q4, q8 110 q2, q4	Relaxing / Relaxed	9
5	030 q1, q2, q3 040 q2, q4, q9 080 q1, q19, q30 060 q20, q22 090 q1, q8, q9, q20, q27 130 q18 050 q7, q8, q14, q21 110 q2, q5, q27, q28	Reading / Read	25
6	030 q15, q16 040 q1, q15, q17 080 q4, q25, q28 060 q16 130 q8, q17 100 q1, q25, q29 110 q1	Helpful / Helping	15
7	080 q3 130 q9	Focus	3

	110 q10		
8	030 q1 080 q5, q30 060 q15, q17 090 q2 130 q1, q2, q11	"the only place" / "this is the place"	9
9	080 q8 070 q12	"record of library attendance"	2
10	080 q8 100 q8 050 q12, q15	"expand number of computers"	4
11	080 q9, q18, q30 130 q24	Education	4
12	030 q1, q19, 080 q10 060 q22 130 q18, q19 110 q14	Professional requirements / objectives, development	7
13	080 q1 070 q18, q27 130 q19 050 q1 110 q14	Personal requirements / objectives, development	6
14	030 q18 080 q18, q30 060 q22 050 q3, q30	Training	6
15	030 q13, q16, q30 040, q13 080 q19, q20, q30 090 q24, q28 110 q28 130 q26	Information	11
16	030 q1, q2, q4, q8 040 q2, q4, q8 080 q21 060 q1, q3, q7, q12, q15, q21 090 q1, q3, q4, q8 130 q2, q5, q8, q9 050 q2, q21 110 q2, q4, q8, q21 140 q2	Quiet / Peaceful	29
17	080 q24 060 q21	Network	2
18	030 q3, q30 080 q26	Thinking	5

	060 q13 090 q8		
19	080 q28 100 q29	Trust	2
20	080 q30 050 q30	"Sense of belonging"	2
21	080 q30 050 q21, q30 140 q1	Sharing / Shared	4
22	080 q30 070 q18, 130 q1, q2, q19, q28 100 q12, q24, q29 050 q30 140 q1, q4, q18	Learning	13
23	060 q1, q3, q15 070 q5, q7, q8, q14, q21, q29 110 q8 140 q16	Calm	11
24	060 q1, q15 090 q17, q19 110 q22	De-stress	5
25	060 q2, q22 130 q21	Meeting rooms	3
26	040 q3, 060 q2, q7, q10, q28 070 q4 130 q2, q28 050 q1, q4, q8, q12 090 q17, q18 110 q28, q30 140 q11	Technology / IT / PCs	17
27	060 q2	Facilities and equipment	1
28	030 q4, q8 060 q7 130 q8	Comfortable	4
29	060 q7	Formal	1
30	060 q7 070 q28 130 q8	Informal	3
31	030 q2, q8, q14, q23 040 q4, q12, q13, q14, q19 060 q7 050 q21, q30 100 q20	Study / Studying	16

	110 q1, q28 140 q24		
32	060 q7 130 q8, q16 100 q2 050 q15 140 q2, q12	Attractive / Welcoming	7
33	060 q13 070 q12	"Longer opening hours"	2
34	060 q14, q27 110 q14, q30	Stress / Stressed	7
35	130 q8, q28, q30	Privacy	3

Appendix 5

Coded transcripts

Participant 030

Do you have any strong beliefs about workplace libraries?

Yes I think well it depends on **personal and professional**. Professionally it is absolutely essential for us as a resource.

Comment [MC1]: 12

But personally for me probably the environment that I can come to sometimes and hopefully not interfering with other people. Cos it's **quiet** and I can **read** during lunch breaks that is a major reason why I use it. But yes I feel strongly that it is a very important resource. **It is not often there is elsewhere,** anywhere in the hospital.

Comment [MC2]: 16

Comment [MC3]: 5

Comment [MC4]: 8

Why do you come to this library?

I come mainly to **read** and to **relax**. I do a little bit if **studying** not necessarily work study but different study. The library is an ideal place for it because it is **quiet**.

Comment [MC5]: 5

Comment [MC6]: 4

Comment [MC7]: 31

Comment [MC8]: 16

What do you use the library for?

Reading, study, thinking

Comment [MC9]: 5

Comment [MC10]: 31

Comment [MC11]: 18

Why do you choose to come to the library rather than go elsewhere?

Because it is **quiet** and the other good thing of a library because of the culture of the library people are not going there to disturb you. You go somewhere else and particularly in the work environment, I used to use the clinic where I work, there were some consulting rooms but people would come in and interrupt me. So if I come here it is more **quiet** and **comfortable**.

Comment [MC12]: 16

Comment [MC13]: 16

Comment [MC14]: 28

Last month, how many times did you come to the library?

It would be nearly every working day so roughly 5 days a week so it's going to be about 18-20 days.

How long do you stay on average?

About half an hour.

Do you come during working hours and / or during your breaks?

I come during lunch break

How would you describe the library environment / physical space?

Comfort yeah is good. Erm, surprised that not more people use it.

Comment [MC15]: 28

Quiet place to come and study.

Comment [MC16]: 16

Comment [MC17]: 31

Do you bring your own books, journals, magazines, reports or do you use library resources – books, journals whilst you are here?

I bring my own things yes.

Do you use library PCs or do you bring your own device?

I have done and I have done that during work time as well because again, no one is going to disturb you here and you can do those mandatory course and not have work colleagues disturb you.

Do you use the library wifi?

No I don't use that.

What would make you come to the library more?

More time but I haven't got that!

How could the Trust encourage you to use the library more?

Well I use it more professionally which I need to anyway which I have just started to do. I think that is a difficult one, I really don't know apart from advertising but then if you're advertised there is so much **information** on the intranet people don't select it.

Comment [MC18]: 15

Do you think it would be useful if trust policies on the subject of well-being recommended spending time in the library to encourage personal and professional development?

Er, wellbeing. I think again with libraries, its natural selection. People of the character and type of person that will use libraries and you see the same people here all the time using – the doctors, the nurses, they use it as a great resource for **study** in particular. So they find it very useful, so I think to get people to change their **study** habits then you might get people to use it more, so it is changing that culture into **studying** and **reflection**.

Comment [MC19]: 31

Comment [MC20]: 31

Comment [MC21]: 31

Comment [MC22]: 1

Is the way library staff behave towards you different from other staff in the trust?

Oh yes if people are **friendly** and open and **helpful**, you know I have always found it really **helpful** here. Erm any **information** I've needed are asked for like how to use Athens etc. you know.

Comment [MC23]: 3

Comment [MC24]: 6

Comment [MC25]: 6

Comment [MC26]: 15

Do you find they are different from other staff in the Trust, in the way they treat people?

People are all different in the Trust. Overall they seem to be **helpful** here.

Comment [MC27]: 6

There has never been any kinda judgement of the **information** you're searching for you know.

Comment [MC28]: 15

Would a poor encounter with library staff dissuade you from visiting the library again? If so why?

Erm, if you weren't used to it maybe yeah. If you come along for years and it has been fine but particular if someone has come along for the first or second time then yes I think it would. I think interactions are the most important thing in life. If you get a poor interaction with somebody. You will find a poor interaction will influence somebody generally than a good interaction.

Does your Manager support a learning environment within the workplace where the sharing of knowledge and skills is encouraged?

Yes less than it used to be because of err, staff shortages and the more demands of work. There is less training for in service training etc. There used to be a reasonable amount a few years ago but not now. But say if I wanted to lead a session in something, yes it would be encouraged.

Comment [MC29]: 14

Do you have personal objectives in mind when you use the library?

Yes, personally and professionally. Personally I have said what I want to achieve that day reading. Might be a couple of things that I'm reading and I do come here to use it occasionally. Professionally, oh yes to use have an objective when you come here.

Comment [MC30]: 12

Have you ever used library's fiction collection or books on prescription collection or other resources for your own personal development, not relating to your work?

A few of the self help ones I've looked at. They are quite interesting because they relate to work issues. Things like Positive Outlook, Anxiety is another one.

Do you find the library a social environment where you can meet colleagues on a different level from other places in the workplace?

Yes.

Do you think using the library helps you achieve trust objectives, by giving you a thinking space?

Yes definitely because if there is an article I want to read and it might take only 5-10 mins to read the article, I will deliberately come down here then stay in the work environment which you will be interrupted by something else.

Do you feel the library is part of the networks within the organisation?

Can be. It can be yeah. Certainly with other study partners.

Comment [MC31]: 31

Do you feel the library staff know people in the Trust?

Regular people come here a lot, yeah.

Do you feel that the library knows about other organisations that could support you in your development?

Erm, I haven't really explored that side, I don't know. I would imagine so because even through search engines you can see various journal and institutions that they're coming from.

Have you ever come across things you hadn't set out to find in the library?

Oh yes, I've done that a few times particularly for journals. When it used to be the older system where you had a lot more journals on the shelf. I think society has moved on and you would never store the information that way. You really have to change because it is easier for younger people who really wanna change the culture to work in. But that browsing ability I think is still important but we just don't have that now.

Have you ever asked / would you feel comfortable asking library staff about training on "modern technologies"

I've never of thought of that but yeah, it would be quite useful, especially the Kindle side of things.

Do you trust the library staff? If yes, why?

Yes.

Anything else?

No. I can't really think of anything. I think the library is an essential service to develop thinking because that is what it is about. It's about thinking and moving along in life to develop things. The health service like many other areas, you need that. When you do your portfolio now, it's all electronic now. It's not fantastic but it's ok. You can upload things like videos, media, radio shows. There is a huge resource out here. Radio, 4 there will some item on the news that is personal to health care. And the science programmes. Things like that.

Comment [MC32]: 18

Comment [MC33]: 18

I want to start using the library more, physio is not a passion of my life, it's all good. I will come and get a refresher on Athens.

You definitely need a forum. There is too much faith put in online. Everything's online now but the problem is that the human interaction is very important and the library does provide that environment to interact and exchange information a lot quicker than you can if you are just searching on the web.

Comment [MC34]: 15

I think the other problems as well is encouraging people to study cos when they come to work – it's interesting that you say that physios use the library a lot, I've thought the top people would have been the medics etc. because they are forever having to develop their career, you know exam after exam.

Participant 040

Do you have any strong beliefs about workplace libraries?

They should be accessible and well stocked and er, good, helpful staff makes a difference cos sometimes, from previous experience that somebody who knows their way around the place, it's always very helpful and they know how to access things such as articles because I wasn't too sure how to do that. I think probably that helpful staff is one of the most important things.

Comment [MC35]: 6

Comment [MC36]: 6

Comment [MC37]: 6

Why do you come to this library?

It's quiet. I come here in my lunch break as a member of staff because it's quiet and I can read, I like reading. I come occasionally to get articles. I have in the past but not so much recently. OT books occasionally.

Comment [MC38]: 16

Comment [MC39]: 5

Comment [MC40]: 5

What do you use the library for?

One of the interesting things is the way this particular library as developed and the use of its space. For example putting pictures up, that is an interesting point. I think that has been good. You have the coffee machine there as well and the computers. I have used the computers on occasions.

Comment [MC41]: 26

Comment [MC42]: 26

Why do you choose to come to the library rather than go elsewhere?

It is a quiet space, a designated quiet space. There aren't many of those kinds of spaces available in the hospital. You really can't get that quiet in the work space to read or book or do any studying. It's conducive to study.

Comment [MC43]: 16

Comment [MC44]: 16

Comment [MC45]: 16

Comment [CM(M46)]: 5

Comment [CM(M47)]: 31

Comment [CM(M48)]: 31

Last month, how many times did you come to the library?

I come every day in my lunch break!

How long do you stay on average?

About 40 minutes.

How would you describe the library environment / physical space?

Quietness. It's quite an intimate space. It isn't a large library. It has got multifunctional elements to it. I've also noticed that in the past you've put books out for foreign speaking members of staff which is very good and very interesting. I suppose I know it's a hospital library but I've noticed you have other books.

Comment [CM(M49)]: 16

Do you bring your own books, journals, magazines, reports or do you use library resources – books, journals whilst you are here.

Er, I do occasionally read articles here. We have journal club so I read articles for that. Generally speaking I bring my own books.

Comment [CM(M50)]: 5

Comment [CM(M51)]: 5

Do you use library PCs or do you bring your own device?

I have used the computers.

Comment [CM(M52)]: 26

Do you use the library wifi?

No

What would make you come to the library more?

Cakes! I have used the tea and coffee machine a couple of times. It's very good value. You can't get a tea or coffee cheaper than that in the hospital.

To be perfectly honest I don't think coming to the library is encouraged in our department in a way that it perhaps was. I think the emphasis so much now is on do your job and there is very little scope for study unless you really make your own effort. I think that is a shame in a way. We used to have designated study days. We were encouraged to take those but those days are gone now.

Comment [CM(M53)]: 31

How could the Trust encourage you to use the library more?

More study days, to encourage learning I suppose.

Comment [CM(M54)]: 31

I think advertising that kind of information about the library would be useful so that people would come in and be more likely to dip a toe in.

Comment [CM(M55)]: 15

Do you think it would be useful if trust policies on the subject of well-being recommended spending time in the library to encourage personal and professional development?

Definitely yeah. I mean the whole **study** issue. I mean so much of our profession is evidence based and to have that sort of time to look at what the evidence is, I don't think you can do that now.

Comment [CM(M56): 31

Is the way library staff behave towards you different from other staff in the trust?

Yes definitely. We want people to be **helpful** and I think you want that in all areas of the hospital. Sometimes you are not aware that things exist so if you are looking for something, I suppose people know their stuff and people can point you in the right direction so that's **helpful** It is the same when someone comes on to the ward and can you tell me what are the options for my mother for example.

Comment [CM(M57): 6

Comment [CM(M58): 6

Would a poor encounter with library staff dissuade you from visiting the library again? If so why?

Erm, I think people's attitudes are important. I think, you know, I find anyway that personal rapport with somebody helps, it builds. I've always found the staff here really **helpful**.

Comment [CM(M59): 6

Does your Manager support a learning environment within the workplace where the sharing of knowledge and skills is encouraged?

No.

(Do you think your Manager should?)

Yes

Do you have personal objectives in mind when you use the library?

I'm not doing it for an area of **study**. I'm doing not any dissertation or private **study**.

Comment [CM(M60): 31

Comment [CM(M61): 31

Have you ever used library's fiction collection or books on prescription collection or other resources for your own personal development, not relating to your work?

I haven't no.

Do you find the library a social environment where you can meet colleagues on a different level from other places in the workplace?

Yeah I mean I do meet people here like Alan. I'm really conscious of the fact that you are not supposed to talk in the library. I've seen work colleagues here occasionally.

Do you think using the library helps you achieve trust objectives, by giving you a thinking space?

Yes.

Do you feel the library is part of the networks within the organisation?

Yes, I do. It is always one of the things that when people start, you direct them and introduce them to the library. So it is an important feature.

Do you feel that the library knows about other organisations that could support you in your development?

I don't know if you are or not. I wouldn't know that. Is it advertised? I didn't know there were links like that. I'm sure a lot of other people would be interested to know about it.

Have you ever come across things you hadn't set out to find in the library?

Yes I have, I browse the shelves. There were a couple of books that I got and became so keen on I ordered another book after that so I have.

Have you ever asked / would you feel comfortable asking library staff about training on “modern technologies”?

I would. Does the library have its own twitter account?

(Yes we have. Are you a prolific tweeter?)

I do tweet I mean I have got a twitter account, I've been tweeting for some time. Do you have a Facebook page? (Yes we do)

I didn't know about technology drop-in so it's worth knowing the library does that.

Do you trust the library staff?

Yes. I think there should be confidentiality all around the trust.

Anything else?

I think that having a designated library space is valuable. I think it is not a good idea to get rid of that. I think it is good to have a space and some people want to look at hardcopies of things.

Participant 050

Do you have any strong beliefs about workplace libraries?

I think every workplace should have one, particularly organisations like the NHS and other statutory services.

Er, employers talk a lot about **personal development** and **reflection** and yet if they haven't given people a space to do that in or a space to access either **computers** or journals or books to build on their knowledge or reflect on their knowledge, then the two don't really fix I think, erm, if you're an employer that's promoting that in your staff then you need to create an environment where people can do that.

Comment [MC62]: 13

Comment [MC63]: 1

Comment [MC64]: 26

Why do you come to this library?

It's a **quiet** space, within a very busy environment, it's nicely laid out, it feels **welcoming** and I like the addition of a coffee machine, that's nice.

I don't have a work base within the hospital, so this in effect becomes my hot desk and also a bit of a **retreat** for me when I just need to collect my thoughts.

If I go and sit on a ward, or try and sit in someone else's office, erm, I don't get the **quiet** time I need, or someone will ask me a question or think they have to engage, when actually all I want to do is be **quiet**.

Comment [MC65]: 16

Comment [MC66]: 32

Comment [MC67]: 2

Comment [MC68]: 16

Comment [MC69]: 16

What do you use the library for?

I come and work, I might look up additional things that build on my work, so I might have had a question off a ward or I might want to check out something erm, Google something that would help, so I can be more informed to go back and answer the question, so I use it for research.

I like flicking through other people's journals, not only my own discipline, so like the Health service journal and the dysphasia journal and things like that I can just have a flick through, and I've been able to influence the purchase of books, which is nice, which then makes me feel that other non-specialists in my field or staff may one day come across a journal or the book and think "oh, that's interesting", and when I do **training**, I tell people there are books in the library, so they can go and expand their knowledge.

Comment [MC70]: 14

Why do you choose to come to the library rather than go elsewhere?

Yeah, **people don't ask me questions**, and I'm also conscious that if I want to do some work, so I need to load data for myself around the patients, or look stuff up, if I do that within the context of one of the multi-disciplinary rooms on the wards or in the departments, I'm reducing the access that other staff may need to carry out their activities, so for example, while I'm Googling erm, 'underwear for peg users', someone else can't print off a set of blood results. So erm, I'm very conscious of pressures on our **computer systems** and er, so if I'm

Comment [MC71]: 2

Comment [MC72]: 26

not doing something that's acutely needed within that environment for a patient on that ward, I'd rather come away to an environment like this and not feel like I'm compromising other people's workloads.

Last month, how many times did you come to the library?

It varies really, because of the amount of time I spend on the site there is so... if I'm on site, Heavy use of the site, then I'll be here at least weekly, if not a couple of times a week, it might be for ten minutes, it might be for an hour and a half, but then I could be not coming onto the site for two weeks for various reasons and not touch it at all.

How long do you stay on average?

Yeah, that varies, it can be ten minutes to flick through a journal or just have ten minutes to collect my thoughts with my diary or I could sit here for two hours logging everything and doing some research.

Do you come during working hours and / or during your breaks?

I don't actually use the library for non-work activities, I'm aware there's a nice set of **reading** books and things and non-fiction and fiction, er, no I keep that separate, I do my personal social library type things in my local library and this is much more my work.

Comment [MC73]: 5

How would you describe the library environment / physical space?

It's nice having a desk space here, so I've used it a few times, have sat and done something, I'm often much more **computer** focussed so that's handy, it's nice being able to have a drink, because libraries in the past have always been 'non fluid environments', "you can't have a coffee in the library in case you spill it", that's nice.

Comment [MC74]: 26

And it's nice to have the sofas there, I never really have time to sit on the sofas, but I appreciate lots of other people do and it's nice to come in, and I suppose it's a bit of a challenge for me because it makes me think "maybe I should be sitting on the sofa **reading** a paper or a non-fiction book", you know, using it as a less 'work' space and more of a **relaxation** space, but I haven't got that disciplined with it yet.

Comment [MC75]: 5

Comment [MC76]: 4

Do you bring your own books, journals, magazines, reports or do you use library resources – books, journals whilst you are here.

I've usually got my work things that I need to enter or erm, but I'll use the Intranet from here to access, and I suppose I said about I flick through other magazines and stuff like that's here if I'm looking for something in particular

Do you use the library wifi?

No.

What would make you come to the library more?

The times where I've come in and then gone away again, have been when all of the computers have been taken and there are only four or five in that corner, erm, and I notice that it is being used very regularly by people like me who don't have a space anywhere in the world or like me have found their MDT rooms just too frantic. Looking over other people's shoulders, I can see them entering often the same sort of data and stuff I'm doing on patients, so I think it's being used in that way, er, so the only reason where I'd use it more would be in the times that I've come and it's been full, would be just to have some more computers.

Comment [MC77]: 26

Comment [MC78]: 10

How could the Trust encourage you to use the library more?

I don't think many people, I know this sounds crazy, I'm not sure people really realise it's here, it's in the PGMC and it's stuck out of the way, erm, I'm not sure you could kind of place it above front of reception or something, but I think for lots of staff it's a long way from their working space and so popping in for ten minutes if you're on Fairfield One or you're in the Eye department, it's quite a walk, down here, so I think location might do, might improve it's usage. Yeah, because people kind of pass it by on the way to training, or somewhere else.

Do you think it would be useful if trust policies on the subject of well-being recommended spending time in the library to encourage personal and professional development?

Not sure staff particularly spend a lot of time reading policies. Per se, I think lots of staff find it difficult to find time to read policies that they need to use on an absolute daily basis, like Health policies, so I think you could put wonderful ideas like that in well-being policy, but I'm not sure how many people would think "ooh, I must read the well-being policy and it says I should spend more time in the library" within their busy day.

Comment [MC79]: 5

Is the way library staff behave towards you important?

Yeah, Any environment that's er, public facing needs to be welcoming and you need to feel like you can ask questions and you're not going to be tutted out or told to come back in three hours or whatever.

Comment [MC80]: 32

I've never experienced that here, I have experienced people not being around and happened to search for people, I'm conscious sometimes I'm disturbing somebody because of the staffing levels, but I'm not sure, and I think that's got worse, which is a sadness for the library because I'm sure the library staff then have to, you know, try and do ten things at once, and the layout of the office space within the library may be, if you're going to have much less staff, then it needs to be maybe, nick some of the office space, create some more computer banks in and make the office staff more visual if they are going to have to do three things at once and that, you know, might help.

Comment [CM(M81): 26

Is the way library staff behave towards you different from other staff in the trust?

I think we try as a trust really hard to offer it, I think within the space limitations we've got and the age of the building, we're sometimes restricted.

That makes me think "I wonder how easy it would be to get a wheelchair round the library"

I think it may be quite tight, and if you've got one of the really flashy all-singing, all-dancing wheelchairs with power packs and things, I think your turning circle at the end of some of the big library stands would be quite difficult, and certainly if you were to want to use a computer maybe, and again, you were in a wheelchair, your use of the one computer would probably restrict the access to somebody else, or certainly impinge on people, you might find you were all a bit squashed in one corner, and so that might be a challenge, but it is a limited space.

I think the trust would be responsive if they had an increase in people who raised concerns about the space, in terms of wheelchair access, I think they'd have a go, but it would then, there might be some losses to the library as well in terms of "what have we got to take out then, in order to create that space?"

Would a poor encounter with library staff dissuade you from visiting the library again? If so why?

If I had a bad experience, I'd do something about it, because I think, erm, I'd give someone that came in one day and someone's a bit off or doesn't make very good eye contact or whatever, I'd say, we all have our tough days.

But if every time I came in, someone sighed at me or didn't make eye contact or could clearly see I was waiting and still didn't come, then I'd probably, well I would, I'd give some feedback, because I think it's...there's no point in moaning about things if then no one knows, it might be that the person doesn't realise they have a mannerism that means that they tut without realising it, or maybe they do need to be told that actually "That's not acceptable, 16 people say that you sighed heavily when you took the books off them" whatever.

I've not found that, but if I did, I would do something about it because I think it's not only me, it's a whole range of people that come in here, whole range of other professions, and we take away comments about our trust.

Does your Manager support a learning environment within the workplace where the sharing of knowledge and skills is encouraged?

Yes, we share stuff within team meetings and in our own speciality meetings, he was keen to support the request for particular publications that we'd asked for, um, I think he would have tried to have funded it

internally if we hadn't have been able to get some of the books published by the trust for those to be held by the library, um and certainly keen for us to research and be **reflective** in our work, so.

Comment [MC82]: 1

Do you have personal objectives in mind when you use the library?

Absolutely, I couldn't do my job without accessing, I couldn't stay, clinically within the requirements in terms of time, of entering data and stuff if I didn't have the library space here when all the other spaces are taken because I come here as well, and I know that foolishly I've told other people about it more recently and I'm thinking "that's very foolish" because when I get there basically there will be no desks left, you know, again others like me who don't have a desk space, are desperately trying some to find somewhere to sit.

Do you feel the library is part of the networks within the organisation?

I'm not really sure I can comment on that, I've always, since I could read been a library user in my own community, so I kind of seek them out in a way, so, I'm not sure if I wasn't already a library convert how and when I would network it into my day, so I'm not sure.

Do you feel that the library knows about other organisations that could support you in your development?

I've not tested it out for that, it's not something I use it for, only so much as being able to use the internet here.

Have you ever come across things you hadn't set out to find in the library?

Yes, the thing that tempts me, which is awful, is the, where I sit to do the computer work, there's a rack of changing books and themes, and I've often reached back and dipped into something..."Oh no no, must put that back", erm, so yeah, that's quite nice because of where it's situated.

Is there anything you'd like to add?

Only something you raised about "do you think other trust staff know it's here and use it and are given time to", as I said, they probably don't, partly because of where it's situated, the distance and the time aspect, and I think that's um, quite sad, when I come in I personally don't see what I think are nurses in here, and that might be because they're not in their uniforms or whatever, but that's a shame really because there's such an encouragement for people to keep **learning** and do more **qualifications** and go on this course and go on that course, and so this is an ideal space for them to access all those journals that are terribly expensive to buy, or they can't access at home because they're not on

Comment [MC83]: 22

Comment [MC84]: 31

the right internet package and stuff, but I think in the working day, there's just not the space given to do that here.

It would be interesting to see who's using it and whether that changes depending on advertising or a push within the trust around the trust focus on health and safety that 16 health and safety books been accessed that month, yeah, would just be interesting to see what the effect is.

I know we have a thing about putting things on walls and notice boards and stuff, and I see your point that if you put a poster up in here that said 20% of users were nurses and 50% were doctors, the only people seeing that would be the people already using it, whereas, I think that if you could put it in a space that was more general, or on the trust focus or something that people are asked to share and would cascade down, it might stimulate people to think "ooh 20% are nurses, ooh, are you using the library?, where's the library? You know, it might make a connection to your peer group and you might use it more.

Comment [MC85]: 21

Comment [MC86]: 20

Have you ever used library's fiction collection or books on prescription collection or other resources for your own personal development, not relating to your work?

Yeah, tempted me terribly, but I just thought "ooh, I'll have them and I'll get very confused, at least my workbooks are my workbooks and they belong to this library and my non-fiction and other things, yeah, and I'll end up with a big stack and muddle

Have you ever asked / would you feel comfortable asking library staff about training on "modern technologies" e.g. social media Twitter, Facebook, apps, Kindle?

I hadn't realised you did, and I think my children are desperately wishing I would get that training, because I can't even work the new system in the car, um, so yeah I hadn't even realised, if that's on offer I may well come and ask for some time.

Comment [MC87]: 14

I certainly didn't know those services were on offer and I know the trust 'Twitters' and I remember someone saying to me "oh, you need to put on when something really good's happened" like, "I just met my 'can do lady' and had a great time in eye out patient", that would be in my number of characters, but I wouldn't know where to start to do that and if it meant I need that and could use the training from the library to do that...

Do you find the library a social environment where you can meet colleagues on a different level from other places in the workplace?

I don't come to be sociable in the library, and I like libraries to be quiet, I'm very traditional on that, so if I came in and found lots of people chatting, I'd find that quite off-putting because, especially where this library is located, literally round the corner is an open area where sometimes there's hot drinks and things, and where you can go and chat to your hearts content.

Comment [MC88]: 16

I'm afraid I'd be somebody who would be like um, ask someone to be quiet, or go and ask the librarian, just go over and say "every time I come here it's like, you know?"...I need that space.

And certainly, often when I've been here, there are people that I know in the library, so, like doctors I've worked with or other therapists who have come in and there's a kind of a nod "hello" and then we get down to business and people carry on with whatever they're doing, whether it's sitting on the sofa reading a book, um, and I've gone and got a journal out and I think "ooh hello" to a girl or whether it's a doctor who's desperately loading data like I am, who goes "ooh hi, nice to see you on the ward and then off we go, to our respective work. Again, maybe I've just been fortunate that the people that I've known that have been in the library with me appear to have the same approach, they've come for the quiet and the space, and not to come and talk about work or er, share personal stuff, they come and sort this space for a reason and.

Comment [MC89]: 5

Comment [MC90]: 16

Comment [MC91]: 21

I think it's a generational thing, er, having said that, some of the younger doctors still seem to be quite respectful, but then they will have come through education systems where their libraries will have "shh silence", you know, I think sometimes it's a challenge in other libraries where, with the need to encourage younger people to come into them, they've maybe lost some of the quietness that other bit, other generations of the library users would benefit from.

Comment [MC92]: 16

And in those bigger libraries, having just done a whole load of university visits with Jake, we've gone round libraries and, fabulous, fabulous ones, but because they've got the space, and I think that's an issue, they've been able to designate one area as private study area, where the expectation will be that you're quiet and then they've got rooms with doors, which may have glass in them and may still be in the library context, which are for shared study, the idea being the door is shut and you and your three colleagues that are writing your end of term project can do that with accessing the books and talking without disturbing the others.

Comment [MC93]: 16

Comment [MC94]: 21

Comment [MC95]: 31

I think that when your space is restricted, I'd like to see this library stay a quiet library, not a project library.

Comment [MC96]: 16

And having, and coming in like you know, flicking through the dysphasia section, and seeing the journals and thinking "wow", you know, um, physio have got their own journal and there's a dysphasia journal, a whole journal, how did they create enough words to fill a

journal? For me, it gives me a degree of increased respect I suppose, for those other disciplines and that there are so many other things, other disciplines working within the trust.

Participant 060

Do you have any strong beliefs about workplace libraries?

It's a quiet calm place to come and de-stress yourself amongst a whole lot of knowledge around with a number of books that you find.

Comment [MC97]: 16

Comment [MC98]: 23

Comment [MC99]: 24

Why do you come to this library?

Again this library a few reasons. One obviously is the books that you have, the journals, especially given that they are here so I do come here for my course books quite a lot. Also I have been using the library quite a lot for the meeting rooms. It is quite a good space with the technology available and given IT skill levels here in the organisation (What do you mean by that?) I mean the IT standards I would say generally in our meeting rooms across the Trust. I think you have meeting rooms across the Trust without the amount of technical capability that probably the library meeting rooms have, you know things like the big screens, wifi and then you have the join-in or linked meetings you can do, you can link screens and those are things you can't do in a usual meeting room or anywhere else in the trust so I like it for that. And then generally people are quite friendly and so I've made a few friends so I come here and just talk to people.

Comment [MC100]: 25

Comment [MC101]: 26

Comment [MC102]: 26

Comment [MC103]: 26

Comment [MC104]: 25

Comment [MC105]: 25

Comment [MC106]: 3

Why do you choose to come to the library rather than go elsewhere?

Facilities and the equipment and obviously the place being quiet and calm yes that it what it is.

Comment [MC107]: 16

Comment [MC108]: 23

Last month, how many times did you come to the library?

I would probably say...I can't really well I would say almost every day but in the last

month altogether perhaps 2 days a week. I use the library a lot more than I would generally do.

How long do you stay on average?

On average I would spend about 3 hours on an average. That is what we are looking at.

Do you come during working hours and / or during your breaks?

I come during working hours rather than break times.

How would you describe the library environment / physical space?

Again it is very comfortable, it's again quiet. Again because of the PCs and that, the kind of equipment that you've got, it is very capable in terms of meeting my requirements. Erm it is not informal, it is quite formal in that sense. As I am saying that I am trying to explain what I mean. It is not a place where I can come and just say hello how are you because it is very quiet. People are just sitting here and probably studying as well so it is not fair to be loud and chatty in this place so you are always a bit, you would talk only when you have to talk so in that sense it is quite formal so in that sense I am saying it is not informal. And yeah again it is attractive, it is comfortable, it's quiet.

- Comment [MC109]: 28
- Comment [MC110]: 16
- Comment [MC111]: 26
- Comment [MC112]: 30
- Comment [MC113]: 29
- Comment [MC114]: 16
- Comment [MC115]: 31
- Comment [MC116]: 30
- Comment [MC117]: 31
- Comment [MC118]: 32
- Comment [MC119]: 28
- Comment [MC120]: 16

Do you bring your own books, journals, magazines, reports or do you use library resources – books, journals whilst you are here?

I must say I generally use the library journals and resources when I come here.

Do you use library PCs or do you bring your own device?

I think a combination of both. If the library PCs are available then yes absolutely sometimes I bring our own laptop, our comms laptop because yours is in use.

- Comment [MC121]: 26

Do you use the library wifi?

I haven't used the library wifi a lot I must say.

What would make you come to the library more?

I think I am already coming to the library a lot. I don't think if you do anything more or less it would change the behaviour of mine. I quite enjoy coming here it is a nice environment.

(Interviewer: Is it different from other environments in the Trust?)

Yeah because it doesn't feel busy, it feels quite relaxed when you come down here. That is the first thing that I see. The thing is it is quiet and peaceful and everybody is with their head down doing their own thing so it makes you feel relaxed when I am walking into this library. Coming from the communication department where people are walking in any time in any minute so I probably get a lot of my work done here if I am logged on to pc here so yeah in that sense it is quite different.

Comment [MC122]: 4

Comment [MC123]: 16

Comment [MC124]: 16

Comment [MC125]: 4

How could the Trust encourage you to use the library more?

By thinking that probably if they opened the library, extending the library opening hours maybe? Because sometimes I am thinking if you are too busy in the working day you probably haven't got the time to sit down and have that thinking time. And that thinking time is sometimes good to have. As a staff member that would probably be quite nice to do at slightly later in the evening. Right now it closes at 5pm but I am guessing that a lot of members of staff work a lot longer than 5pm. With that I think having library staff as well as access to the space after 5pm it's nice. It will make you feel as though you are not the only one here and someone else is responsible for this place and I am here to get what I need whereas when you are on your own you become responsible for that place so again not very relaxing.

Comment [MC126]: 33

Comment [MC127]: 18

Comment [MC128]: 18

Comment [MC129]: 4

Do you think it would be useful if trust policies on the subject of well-being recommended spending time in the library to encourage personal and professional development?

Yes I think absolutely, absolutely. I haven't read the trust policy of wellbeing and I don't know what is there, but if it isn't then I think it should be there. Right now I don't think I can, unless I have a meeting in the library I don't think I will come from my working PC to this office and just sit down because I want some me time here. I don't think I can say very openly in my team that anybody has ever said anything that "I am quite tired, I am quite stressed and I just want to come and sit in the library for a while" because I am not sure how people will react to that so yes if that become part of the trust policy then you can. It's the same thing like if you have flexible working hours and you leave at 3pm because of child care you can get up and leave because that is your right and you can do it whereas coming to the library, I don't have a right to do that so it is always open to criticism and comment.

Comment [MC130]: 34

Is the way library staff behave towards you important?

Yes extremely important absolutely.

Is the way library staff behave towards you different from other staff in the trust?

Yes I mean again I do think it comes back to the library being a very quiet and calm place. It is very much reflected the way the staff behave in the library as well. You can see them extremely calm in the way in the way they ask in help, there is not rush whatsoever, and there is no rush, not in a negative way it is absolutely in a positive sense and they are very friendly, they want to help and they go out of their way to help us in what we want whereas if you go to other areas people are always busy, running and rushing so if you are asking or seeking help it comes in that form, rushed or quickly, so you can feel that stress in that environment and again I think it is that de-stressed environment that helps I guess.

Comment [MC131]: 16

Comment [MC132]: 23

Comment [MC133]: 23

Comment [MC134]: 16

Comment [MC135]: 3

Comment [MC136]: 16

Comment [MC137]: 34

Would a poor encounter with library staff dissuade you from visiting the library again?

Err, if it happens once then maybe not but it happens again and again but at the same time this is the only place, this is the only source to come and get my journals and books I will probably still be coming but might probably speak to the manager and make them aware that this member of staff is not behaving too well. But yes if it is a one off thing I can understand you know? It's a human thing.

Comment [MC138]: 8

Do you have personal objectives in mind when you use the library?

No I don't think I am coming to the library right now to meet my personal objectives. I think I am coming here to meet my professional objectives. And maybe if it becomes part of the trust policy like you said I probably could meet some of my personal objectives.

Have you ever used library's fiction collection or books on prescription collection or other resources for your own personal development, not relating to your work?

Yes I have **read** some of the self-help books

Comment [CM(M139): 5

Do you find the library a social environment where you can meet colleagues on a different level from other places in the workplace?

I don't think so. Again because people come here and the environment is such that is **quiet** and they just sit down and do what they need to do. So I don't think this is the place you can **network** with people. That is not what I think this place is for. This is where you network **with** the books. That is how I see it. And if you have to **network** with people then you go outside the library and **network** with the people there. If you know someone then you smile, but you are free to walk away. There is no expectation that you should be talking to that person.

Comment [MC140]: 16

Comment [MC141]: 17

Comment [MC142]: 17

Comment [MC143]: 17

Comment [MC144]: 17

Do you think using the library helps you achieve trust objectives, by giving you a thinking space?

Again I personally have not used the library for thinking space. I have used the library to meet my **professional objectives** so coming back to what we said earlier it is because I want to get the **training** done, it is because I can get the **meeting room** to talk to people or I can get the certain books to **read**, so I am doing it for that so the thinking time is not there at that time because once you have finished your purpose here you leave. But yes it would be quite nice to actually sit down and have some thinking time. In other areas of the trust, maybe if it is a nice sunny day then sitting outside on one of the benches near the chapel probably. But I haven't used the library to do this.

Comment [MC145]: 13

Comment [MC146]: 14

Comment [MC147]: 25

Comment [MC148]: 5

Do you feel the library is part of the networks within the organisation?

I think you know it is possible like with the knowledge management group. It can be used a lot more. The knowledge within the library is extremely critical. Right now I think it is used more for the clinical people, for the clinicians, you know junior doctors and the consultants. Those are the people who are generally using the library more, I could be wrong but I think that is how I see it. I don't think the management or the admin side of people use the library as

much as they should. Your presence in a lot of those meetings like the knowledge management group is extremely important because people need to know a bit more. I am not sure everybody understands that.

Do you feel the library staff know people in the Trust?

Ooh that is an interesting one. If people know the library staff, I think people know your name really and people know, I don't think people know other members of the team unless they come unless they really come here and talk to so their visibility outside the library might be useful.

Do you feel that the library knows about other organisations that could support you in your development?

I think yes.

Have you ever come across things you hadn't set out to find in the library?

Yes I think I have done this a few times with the self help books I think. It isn't that I came for a self help book but came for something else and then I see this nice book let's say on stress management.

Comment [CM(M149):

Have you ever asked / would you feel comfortable asking library staff about training on "modern technologies"?

Yes probably that would be useful. I don't think that people generally think that they should come to the library to check that. People generally think that they would think of IT and then immediately think of 'they would not be able to help us' and leave it at that.

Comment [MC150]: 26

Do you trust the library staff?

Oh yes absolutely.

Does your Manager support a learning environment within the workplace where the sharing of knowledge and skills is encouraged?

Yes I think so.

Participant 070

Why and how workplace library users utilise library space for non-library activities?

Do you have any strong feelings about workplace libraries?

That they are necessary, really necessary. In terms of here, and where I am, I don't think the library is utilised as much and that is a shame because I think it makes a lovely divide between work and having somewhere to go to whether it is for work purposes or just to take time out. Public libraries are just that, public libraries and so they will stock a whole range of things to cater for the public whereas here it is quite specific although there is lots of introduction to erm, fiction books now which is great and there are specific racks catered for little things and interests of the week let's say. So for work based libraries a lovely idea that it's here, that it is specific to work but this a little bit of public in it too. I just don't feel that this Trust gives it enough resources and utilises it a lot more so it's incorporated in the working day.

Why do you come to this library?

Erm, sometimes I want to look at things on the internet and although I have access at my work station the phone will go and somebody will tap my shoulder and want something. Here it is because its private and no one will bother me and that is the excellent thing about libraries. You will say hello to somebody but they know that you're there for you, probably one of the few spaces that is just for you. So I come here for privacy, to browse, you just have that opportunity to browse. I guess it's a bit of a haven from work.

Comment [MC151]: 2

What do you use the library for?

Surfing the internet, going online but also making use of some of the resources, the self-help books

Why do you choose to come to the library rather than go elsewhere?

Erm, sometimes I find public libraries quite impersonal. Er and I think there has been such a change. Croydon Library was my local one as well as Upper Norwood Library. Both of them have gone through such a change because of cuts that there is something that's lost within them at the moment.

(Could you describe what that is?)

Er, certainly the staffing levels have been reduced and there were some people that I knew who worked there or were familiar and they seem to have all moved on and that has made a difference.

(Did you feel you had a relationship, even a nodding)

Oh yes even if it was just a hello and how are you and it's all gone. I don't know what has changed. It just kind of a feeling about them. Upper Norwood Library, there are a lot volunteers, its run by an initiative now which is great and it's lovely to see that people have got together to get a library and keep it going but, I don't know, there is just a change about them and I can't put my finger on it whereas as here there is some

continuity. If staff so come and go there's still that level of, perhaps because they know that you work here you feel as though they know you in a way. Your time limited in a way because you may come here in your break or you may have an assignment. When I've been using the computers, people have just till the end of the week to finish this assignment and staff have been really going out of their way to think of journals for them or resources online, or help them with the photocopying. So I'm aware they're aware some of us are on a quota of time when were are here. It is different.

Comment [MC152]: 26

Last month, how many times did you come to the library?

Actually that can depend, that can depend on whether. It can be anything from 5 mins; I might be over the PGMC way. I say one of the biggest problems with this library is its distance from where I am. I am over in anaesthetics so by the time I walk over here, er, it changes my dynamic towards it. But I can be here 5-6 times a month or if I am doing something where I might need a bit of research, completely separate from the medical side of things but I just want a space to come in, I will choose to come here rather than a public library so that may increase. It definitely isn't as busy as a public library. It is a really calming space and Upper Norwood and Croydon Library don't seem to have that, although it's quiet, it doesn't feel as peaceful as it used or calming and there is a sense of just being able to sit and take stock for a while here. And whether that's because it is over on this side which is a less busy side of the hospital, I don't know.

Comment [MC153]: 23

How long do you stay on average?

Oh it can vary, 5 mins to longer depending on what I am here for.

Do you come during working hours and / or during your breaks?

I am lucky enough that when an anaesthetist hasn't sat in my seat to have a computer and desk and work from that desk. But I will come over in a break, if I had something that has brought me over this way like an appointment today it is great to come in here afterwards as I have done and just be able to take stock for a while because it is lovely and calming. I would say it is mainly in breaks or after certain appointments.

Comment [MC154]: 23

How would you describe the library environment / physical space?

Really calming. I mean even now in here is exactly how I feel when I am out in the library space. I'd say is one of its downfalls though is, especially in summer is the heat. Also when I have been locked in too there isn't ventilation.

Comment [MC155]: 23

Do you bring your own books, journals, magazines, reports or do you use library resources – books, journals whilst you are here?

I tend to use what is here and that's the great thing about it you don't have to come with anything.

Do you use library PCs or do you bring your own device?

No, library PCs.

Do you use the library wifi?

No

What would make you come to the library more?

Probably later opening hours. Sometimes I have to leave work early to catch the 5pm thing and get locked because I don't have key access. I would consider the 24 access but didn't know, I thought it had to be relevant in that you were doing a dissertation or something. I thought the 24 hour thing was for doctors and nurses.

Comment [MC156]: 33

How could the Trust encourage you to use the library more?

Again I don't know if its distance and whether placing the library in a more central space. Maybe library sessions for people in the day perhaps being allowed to have a half hour library time off their work whether that would be of any use on top of their break? If they are especially doing course, to have that incorporated in their course time. Extended times where people can come and go could make a difference. Perhaps the trust putting talks on here, they would utilise the space so there was I don't know, yoga sessions over here instead of it being in the gym. Some entertainment, talks or perhaps a drive that is going on in the trust.

Comment [MC157]: 9

Comment [MC158]: 33

Do you think it would be useful if trust policies on the subject of well-being recommended spending time in the library to encourage personal and professional development?

Even though I think there is a wellbeing policy somewhere, that probably in all honestly a lot of us don't read or do anything with. Erm, I think the trust needs to invest a lot more in the well-being of staff anyway. I think this is one of the spaces where wellbeing can be incorporated in a working day because it is calming. In comparison to work and what we have to go through in work, busy, full on and some of the areas are really busy, this is a perfect space for well-being because it's the opposite of that

Comment [MC159]: 23

Is the way library staff behave towards you different from other staff in the trust?

Yes it is. Anywhere where you have had a bad experience with some of the staff it can put you off coming again. I think they are quite respectful here. And whether you are a doctor or admin I don't feel there is a differentiation in treatment whereas in other areas of the trust as an admin person you are sometimes not treated equally because managers, doctors and nurses are treated on a higher level and that is also receiving it too from doctors, nurses and managers, so here everybody is a library user, end of. That is one of the reasons that keeps you coming back.

Would a poor encounter with library staff dissuade you from visiting the library again? If so why?

I think if it was encounters then yes. As a manager you are very approachable so I think if anyone had an issue they could come to you direct and you would deal with it openly and honestly. An encounter, er it depends on the encounter but on the whole even I've come in here and been a bit grumpy as a user. We just have those days.

Does your Manager support a learning environment within the workplace where the sharing of knowledge and skills is encouraged?

I'm in an area that is full of doctors. They are constantly going on study leave or keep up their learning and also studying for exams so for them there is learning in their job and they are actively encouraged to attend things, go to things. I haven't received that kind of push from my managers. So no for me in my post, other than mandatory training.

Comment [MC160]: 22

Comment [MC161]: 22

Do you have personal objectives in mind when you use the library?

Yes, open to using the library for personal development, books on prescription, self-help that kind of thing.

Comment [MC162]: 13

Do you find the library a social environment where you can meet colleagues on a different level from other places in the workplace?

I don't know about meeting, as in meeting up here. I know when I have been here there will be people that I know and we exchange some pleasantries but we get on with our work because it's not the place to have a long conversation. It is unfair on other users. Even the people I say hello are a lot calmer here too. You see a different side to people. I've seen people fall asleep. That is how calming it is.

Comment [MC163]: 23

Comment [MC164]: 21

Do you think using the library helps you achieve trust objectives, by giving you a thinking space?

I'd say the trust has ticked a box in providing a space although it is undervalued and it isn't incorporated in your working day.

Do you feel the library is part of the networks within the organisation?

Er yes and no about networks. I think the staff connect us here but I am not sure if other areas connect it well. Staff would know other people and who you were talking about. The staff are part of the organisation.

Do you feel that the library knows about other organisations that could support you in your development?

Because I haven't asked for that I don't know but I am sure from when I have been sat outside at a PC that they will point people in the right direction.

Have you ever come across things you hadn't set out to find in the library?

I'd say it was the books on prescription now. I've been here for years and it is only now I've started to stumble on. Whether that is for personal reason I am unsure and I have sought them. It is great to see arts and medicine being represented here which I didn't think it would be. You'll start with one thing here and end up down another rack!

Comment [MC165]: 13

Have you ever asked / would you feel comfortable asking library staff about training on "modern technologies"?

Actually if I knew it was available I would because sometimes there is a fear with new technology. If I knew that resource was there I would probably ask for it.

(Do you feel that you know enough about what goes on in the library?)

No, I'm sorry to say it. I'd love a more informal session. IT are IT here. The sessions are not informal. So a drop in session which would take into account that, whereas IT doesn't, you have this amount a time, pop in when you can. People learn differently and I think the library would give a wider variety of learning styles.

Comment [MC166]: 28

Comment [MC167]: 28

Comment [MC168]: 22

Comment [MC169]: 22

Do you trust the library staff?

I think so. I've been on the wards and heard nurses gossiping about some of the visitors. I don't feel that would happen here in that "so and so has just asked for this journal". None of that. This is the request, let me try and deal with it and off we go.

It's calming; there is no element of judgment. It is your time. You don't feel as though you are wasting trust time or money and staff giving me judgmental looks to that effect, no none of that.

Comment [MC170]: 23

Anything else?

In terms of online resources I don't think the trust lets everybody know what is and what isn't available. This is just I guess, our space and you know you can go to the canteen and have a quiet cup of coffee but somebody will join you. You can stay here for the day; you can stay here for 5 mins. It is that kind of area. As a user it would be great to have more space and perhaps the sofas in a different area so people don't fall asleep in front of a PC user! Ventilation but I think most areas of the trust that is a problem. The area I work in is a really fortunate area; it has a common room, PC room, a tiny library at the back, an office and then a consultant's office. Unfortunately I'm in the reception part so eat my lunch, answer the phone, do my work in this area and I don't have half an hour where I can switch off.

Comment [MC171]:

Our anaesthetists though, if their lists have finished early, or their not being bleeped will go into one of those rooms and they can be there for 2 hours, eat, drink, watch TV, be merry and it is purely for them and anaesthetist only really. So coming here for 5 mins, 10 mins or half an hour is the equivalent for me. I think their roles and they too consider themselves higher than my role. They can be quite selfish with space and they can't be here like every other library user because you are treated in the same way, this is everyones equal space. This is purely subjective in that they are very selfish with space because even though they have all

that space they will still come and stand behind me or behind my colleague and chat, and you are trying to answer the phone, you are trying to do typing and I don't think they have that right here. When I am trying to do typing, having a full on conversation behind me is distracting. One of our former anaesthetists came in yesterday to get some paperwork signed off. We asked him how things were going at his new hospital. He said it was great except we don't have this common room and it really makes a difference so imagine how me and my colleague feel.

In Outpatients when I worked there was a common room for the admin team but it really wasn't a space away from work because the other admin staff would be there and you were obliged to make conversation. In Training there wasn't until we moved into a bigger area which has a lovely common room with a TV but again you are sharing it with colleagues. Retinal screening wasn't great because your retinal screening room was also your break room so in those areas I wasn't getting away from work, department or from patients. If patients saw you sitting in there with the door open for ventilation there would be lots of huffing and puffing why can't you do me now because I'm early and I can see you sitting in there. And you did you felt obliged to stop your lunch. You felt you didn't have that right to have a break. And here no one can judge, you are in a mixed environment, mixed as in lots of different staff, not your colleagues who will defer to asking you things even though everything is in front of them. Sometimes with common rooms, ok I am going to speak to speak about my common room as it's the bit I know the best, it is a very selfish environment because the upkeep and the cleanliness of it will go back to me. I feel they are very lucky with the space they have. Now the consultant can have utter **privacy** which 9 out of 10 of them won't use they will either come and sit at my computer and I mean I have just gone to the kitchen and they have sat at my desk. They've got so many resources and they come and sit at this reception part. I might want to go and sit in the consultant's office of which I can't, and get on with my typing; they will choose to come and sit in my seat and chat to my colleague or come and quickly use the internet on my PC. Maybe it's social but I have an issue with the way I am seen in my work environment. There is an element of like it, or if you don't like it, leave which is something I have heard often. There isn't "let's look at your working environment, oh gosh yes, there is no air coming in, what can we do to make it more pleasant experience" it's disappointing. It's a tick box exercise all this wellbeing and I am sure they will have wellbeing groups that doesn't filter through to the everyday.

Comment [MC172]: 35

Participant 080

Do you have any strong beliefs about workplace libraries?

Yes, I mean, I use the library personally as respite from the hectic work of the ward, and more importantly for a reflection on my activities, so in a way I do it on a daily basis, the library is first friendly atmosphere, secondly (inaudible) and third, I could have access to publications and I do this at least once a month, and in between, I use the library as a more relaxing, although I am reading and trying to find information on the internet, I could find other places, but the library is the best, more relaxing to be in.

Comment [MC173]: 13

Comment [MC174]: 2

Comment [MC175]: 1

Comment [MC176]: 3

Comment [MC177]: 4

Comment [MC178]: 5

Comment [MC179]: 4

Last month, how many times did you come to the library?

I almost come three times a week, if not sometimes four times a week.

How long do you stay on average?

I stay on average, two hours if I have time, but sometimes just ten minutes if I have to see patients, then I'll come back and I do some of this reflection on the internet and books, it works for me as a focus for further ongoing reflections.

Comment [MC180]: 1

Comment [MC181]: 7

Comment [MC182]: 1

How would you describe the library environment / physical space?

The environment is quite friendly, the personnel in the library, they are very helpful, almost to invite you to ask them and to do all the library services for you, and also the copies are always ready and they also have this service of selling old books and things and it's quite enriching especially for people who like to collect these things.

Comment [MC183]: 3

Comment [MC184]: 6

Do you bring your own books, journals, magazines, reports or do you use library resources – books, journals whilst you are here.

I only bring some material if I want to do copying, because this is, as far as I know, the only place for people like me to have the scanning of material.

Comment [MC185]: 8

Do you use library PCs or do you bring your own device?

Do you use the library wifi?

I haven't started yet, not for any particular reason

What would make you come to the library more?

I think to have access to material that would help me in my everyday practice.

How could the Trust encourage you to use the library more?

I think there will be a record of the attendance somehow, logged automatically that could be subject to checking, that would be one of the encouragements.

Comment [MC186]: 9

Secondly if they expand on the number of the computers and also to use one of the computer only for library purposes rather than for education.

Comment [MC187]: 10

I think they should provide an educational venue somewhere else rather than the library

Comment [MC188]: 11

Comment [MC189]: 11

Do you think it would be useful if trust policies on the subject of well-being recommended spending time in the library to encourage personal and professional development?

For sure, I mean, one of my profession requirements is to have the CPD and part of it is how much you spend time exploring literature and reading journals and so on, I think because of the financial constraints these days, I think we have to share these resources (inaudible) prescribe (inaudible) the online material.

Comment [MC190]: 12

Is the way library staff behave towards you important?

Of course, it is the most important.

I have had an experience in the past that will be some intimidation because if you ask for a book and things and the attitude in a way that intimidates you, then you feel you are asking too much, and that you are asking people to do more work and so on, I think in this library particularly, it's so friendly, as I said before, they almost invite you to ask.

Comment [MC191]: 3

Is the way library staff behave towards you different from other staff in the trust?

I think nowadays there is a universal good behaviour everywhere, thanks to direction and training and so on, but in particular the staff - I don't have work relation as such, it is indirect - that's why the attitude...I think mutual attitudes, more friendly, more relaxed.

Comment [MC192]: 3

Would a poor encounter with library staff dissuade you from visiting the library again? If so why?

Of course, we are human after all, and er, whatever we push through to achieve our goal, the emotional side of it is important, and as I say, Intimidation and indirect intimidation and not being friendly of course (inaudible) trying to come to (inaudible).

Comment [MC193]: 3

Does your Manager support a learning environment within the workplace where the sharing of knowledge and skills is encouraged?

There is no agenda but I am sure when it comes nitty gritty, with the direction of the trust, the training, education, interactions, it would be encouraged.

Comment [MC194]:

Do you have personal objectives in mind when you use the library?

Yes, to get informed, gain more information.

Comment [MC195]: 15

Have you ever used library's fiction collection or books on prescription collection or other resources for your own personal development, not relating to your work?

Yes, I did use them just to see what is there and what my colleagues are reading and it would be great if you could have some information on how many of which publications are used.

Comment [MC196]: 5

Comment [MC197]: 15

Do you find the library a social environment where you can meet colleagues on a different level from other places in the workplace?

Not really, I'm of the opinion that in spite of not putting constraints on people communicating and thing I think there should be quietness, this is important, so people should not really use the library as a social environment, especially when they quiet that's fine, beyond that it gets very irritating

Comment [MC198]: 16

Comment [MC199]: 16

Do you think using the library helps you achieve trust objectives, by giving you a thinking space?

As I said before, reflection, informed reflection obviously is very important, and I think being in the library reflecting on patient care with access to standards and what other people do is great.

Comment [MC200]: 1

Comment [MC201]: 1

Comment [MC202]: 1

Do you feel the library is part of the networks within the organisation?

Definitely, because I see general doctors, I see nurses, I see midwives, I see administrator coming into the library and that's a very good thing, of course, when they go out of the library, they refer to these activities and thus will be part of the network.

Comment [MC203]: 17

Do you feel that the library knows about other organisations that could support you in your development?

Yes, I mean, recently because I'm attending the course on public health the library have responded very beautifully to bring all the material that's needed, or most of it, that's needed, and they are helping your thinking about how to do analysis, to redirect you to books, websites, which is really, by itself is a fair thing.

Comment [MC204]: 6

Comment [MC205]: 18

Have you ever come across things you hadn't set out to find in the library?

So often I come for something and I see something else, it's stimulating, it is appetising, it is almost like going to the high street to have some food and you would choose from different things to which you had not thought of initially

Have you ever asked / would you feel comfortable asking library staff about training on “modern technologies” e.g. social media Twitter, Facebook, apps, Kindle?

Definitely, yes, I trust them very generally, and their helpfulness and general information that they supply, so they are very honest in that sense, and then the way they provide the facilities is really great, I could see at times when the ceiling is dripping water and how quickly they put the bucket and asked people to take care, in that sense, also they sympathise with the customer, it is very important.

Comment [MC206]: 19

Comment [MC207]: 6

Anything to add?

I admire the people who work in the library who work to improve the library and always asking and discussing ways to fulfil this.

I have seen libraries in small villages in Scandinavian countries

I think, in that sense, there is a lot changing the atmosphere, but hopefully, when the economic crisis finishes.....

Yes, I was talking about the ways I look at libraries and book shops and public libraries with the different functions and different populations, though nowadays, I mean, medical library used to be for doctors, but nowadays you will find students, managers, which is really good, it's expanded the role of the medical library, but in the public libraries of course there is an overlap I think, and er, which is great, and now it's a very sensitive issue, people want to close them, but I think there will be a reaction to that, because people are getting isolated and lonely in spite the connection with the faceless whatever, so the library firstly, gives you a sense of belonging, you would know who is reading and what information is shared by who and that's why and it's important, and I think the pendulum will swing back to more interaction, more library interaction from people because though you are dependent on internet and books. The classroom and that and this, that's the way nowadays people educate themselves, action, learning, online and library, so we learn as we go, and that's one way of touching shoulders with other people, to see what they sometimes interaction, depth and insight.

Comment [MC208]: 20

Comment [MC209]: 6

Comment [MC210]: 15

Comment [MC211]: 21

Comment [MC212]: 11

Comment [MC213]: 22

Comment [MC214]: 22

(Interviewer asks about wifi & internet training)

Indeed, I'm sure you are approaching people that are new, or in training, and perhaps you would presume people like me that are old in the business, but that's the other thing, this is the place where we are not very conscious about what we lack and possibly I think I would be less intimidated to approach for help. Lets face it the population has changed, practicing in modern ways, and they need this unconscious

Comment [MC215]: 14

Comment [MC216]: 8

sort of lack of confidence and learning and education, and I think, as one of those people, I would appreciate to be told about the available information

Comment [MC217]: 22

Comment [MC218]: 11

Participant 090

Do you have any strong beliefs about workplace libraries?

Yes, they're really necessary, it's where you can get some solace instead of the hustle bustle of your work place. It's the reason I came and when members of my family and myself started having problems, it was a good place to sit down and read and take it all in quietly, so yeah, I think they're essential to be perfectly honest.

Comment [CM(M219): 2

Comment [CM(M220): 2

Comment [CM(M221): 5

Comment [CM(M222): 16

Why do you come to this library?

Because it's the only one in the hospital. And it's the closest, we deal with each other every day and it seems a natural place to come and spend your dinner hour.

Comment [CM(M223): 8

What do you use the library for?

For quiet contemplation and to learn what's wrong and what can be done, when, like I had both knees replaced, was a really good place to come and ask people if they could put you onto the literature, and if they had an article that they knew about, that they could get it for you, and you had a lot more understanding about what was going to happen to you when you were under the surgeon's knife, which I found extremely helpful.

Comment [CM(M224): 16

Comment [CM(M225): 2

Why do you choose to come to the library rather than go elsewhere?

I could have sat in the car which I have done for several years, but um, once somebody had told me how quiet and relaxing it was up here, before they left the hospital, I thought I'd give it a go and I've been doing it for about four and a half years now. For quiet, you can't get it anywhere else, literally, if you go to a canteen or whatever, it's just hustle bustle, and people walking past saying "hello" or whatever, where, there's only about three people that say "hello" when you're here.

Comment [CM(M226): 16

Comment [CM(M227): 4

Comment [CM(M228): 16

Comment [CM(M229): 2

The only time I interact is when people are next door and they start making use of their mobile phones or they're just talking too loud, so you just say "I'm closing the door because I don't want to hear what you're talking about".

Last month, how many times did you come to the library?

If I'm not working downstairs, basically every day.

How long do you stay on average?

Three quarters of an hour to an hour.

Do you come during working hours and / or during your breaks?

Yes.

How would you describe the library environment / physical space?

It's comforting to have a place that...I suppose it's a bit like the chapel, you can go there, just relax and gather your thoughts, but you can do that in a totally different way here.

Recently, I found out my brother needs two heart valves and it was comforting to know that you could go to a section, pick out a book, and you could read what it was about, and it was just so quiet you could think about what you were reading and how it would affect you after, you told them because they're scared stiff, but if you can get a photocopy or whatever, pass it on, it's just a natural process.

Comment [CM(M230): 4

Comment [CM(M231): 18

Comment [CM(M232): 5

Comment [CM(M233): 16

Comment [CM(M234): 5

Do you bring your own books, journals, magazines, reports or do you use library resources – books, journals whilst you are here.

I do both to be honest, a young lady lends me her paper every day, but when I need to go and use the library, for magazines books whatever, I know they're readily available. Probably once a week I'll read the journals.

Comment [CM(M235): 5

Do you use library PCs or do you bring your own device?

No

Do you use the library wifi?

No, simply because we've not been trained to use them downstairs, and they've only just after twenty years decided that we can have a PC. They didn't see any point in us having one before, now we've got one, I tried to get onto it last week and it wouldn't even let me in.

(Interviewer asks about communicating with rest of the hospital)

People come and ask, the chief exec comes and asks you what's going on in the hospital, because as you're walking round, everybody's telling you their woes and whatever.

I think I've actually talked one woman out of committing suicide three times, which was quite an interesting...you kind of did it without knowing you did it, just through talking to her and listening to her and thoroughly getting involved in a way you didn't know you were doing.

I suppose in a way you'd call it a kind of counselling, but talking to people that do use the library, you find that you can pick up on bits and pieces that you can use in your own life and help other people.

Comment [CM(M236): 6

What would make you come to the library more?

Not having to work so long, to be perfectly honest.

How could the Trust encourage you to use the library more?

I think you could do with a slightly bigger library, where it's situated isn't the ideal situation. You could probably do with one of the old type of wards that's long and not really used any more to give you the extra space, but you really could do with being on the ground floor.

Do you think it would be useful if trust policies on the subject of well-being recommended spending time in the library to encourage personal and professional development?

Yeah. Definitely.

Is the way library staff behave towards you important?

Oh yeah, but you should be behaving the same way as you would expect them to behave toward you.

Is the way library staff behave towards you different from other staff in the trust?

I hope not, I have had quite a decent rapport over the years I've been coming here with all the staff, and I'd hope to think they treat me exactly the same as they would treat anybody else.

I mean, that volunteer you had grief with a few weeks ago...that woman is impossible, but the way you handled it or whatever, er, seemed perfectly adequate for what she was griping about, which was nothing. Was just a shame, because she can be a very pleasant woman, but she just gets a bee in her bonnet if somebody hasn't said "thank you" or the right way to her, in her thinking.

You can't help people like that, you really can't.

Would a poor encounter with library staff dissuade you from visiting the library again? If so why?

No. Because it's become part of my life, and we are so hectic downstairs 24/7 basically, I've found recently, that when I go home, I use the sleep apnea machine and, although I know I'm asleep, you know your brain is still active and it doesn't actually switch off, so when you can come to a place like this, which is moderately quiet at times...does drive me up the wall people hitting the keys on the computers too hard, because they are loud, but if you can shut your eyes for ten minutes in an environment like this, a lot of strain and stress just seems to ebb away that you don't seem to be able to do while you're at work or while you're asleep at home, it's a totally different environment.

Well I've only ever found any of them (*library staff*) would only approach you if they needed something from you like picking your brains because

Comment [CM(M237): 26

Comment [CM(M238): 24

they didn't know X, Y or Z, which is exactly the same if I ask, but no, I find them very helpful

Comment [CM(M239): 6

Does your Manager support a learning environment within the workplace where the sharing of knowledge and skills is encouraged?

I haven't got a clue. I'll be perfectly honest, I've never had a manager turn round and say, other than what you have to do for courses to keep your wages...I've never had one that has turned round and said, "I think this would be an advantage to you".

Like the computers, they didn't want us to basically have a computer because that would put us on the next grade.

Comment [CM(M240): 26

Comment [CM(M241): 26

Do you have personal objectives in mind when you use the library?

Just to unwind. As I say, there's two or three people that you interact with as you come in, you acknowledge they're there, you obviously say "Hello" to the library staff, but it's just to unwind.

Comment [CM(M242): 24

Have you ever used library's fiction collection or books on prescription collection or other resources for your own personal development, not relating to your work?

Yes. I haven't used books on prescriptions, but I have used the other library books as well. I'm not a particularly fiction person, so I do find, if I haven't got something to read, you've got that piece of the library you can get to and find something that's worth reading, even if you just read a chapter or two a day, it is worth acquiring.

Comment [CM(M243): 20

Comment [CM(M244): 20

Do you find the library a social environment where you can meet colleagues on a different level from other places in the workplace?

Yeah, I mean, you can actually talk to doctors where you couldn't...Where we used to have the social club, if you felt like having a pint after work, you could go in and physically sit in the same room as a consultant and you'd end up talking to one another, the same thing is similar here, I've never met a consultant or doctor that wouldn't say "Hello" or wouldn't enquire how you are and whatever, but um, it does get up my bosses noses that I can actually interact with 95% of the consultants on first name terms, they always think it should be Mr / Mrs whatever ...

There's probably 3,500 people in this hospital, I probably know over 500 by their first names and probably 2,000 by sight alone that you would acknowledge one another as you're walking past, except junior

doctors, they seem to think they're above everybody else and they just ignore you...until they want something.

Do you think using the library helps you achieve trust objectives, by giving you a thinking space?

Um, A lot of the trust objectives, I don't actually don't get round to using, because I'm not interactive with the patients and whatever, but we do probably about 50 times a day, get asked where X,Y & Z are, and even doctors, consultants, managers come up to us and say "you should know where so and so is" and 99 times out of a hundred, we do. I mean, I was the only person here who knew where every photocopier was.

Recently, they had a new contract with all the water suppliers, and I knew where all the only ones that weren't being used were being stacked away, because you walk past them every day, and finance came down and asked us where we thought X, Y & Z were and we could give them 80/90% of where they were just by walking past and observing what's going on...which most people don't you know, in an environment like this.

When I think someone's looking for somewhere, you normally watch their heads and they're going like that (assumes motion) and there's a good chance if you turn round and say "Are you looking for somewhere", they're going to say "Yes", as you say, most people walk along and they are in tramlines.

Do you feel the library is part of the networks within the organisation?

I think it's a totally necessary part of the fabric of the hospital, because without it, most of the doctors wouldn't get where they are today. The likes of me and other people like me, who need information, get a very good result by just being able to ask. It's like the post room, it's like a heartbeat in the hospital that you need.

Comment [CM(M245): 15

Do you feel the library staff know people in the Trust?

Probably not as well as they could do, nor should do, because you're fairly isolated, where, if I'm stuck in the post room, I'm fairly isolated. I've got a 20ft area to walk around in where you've got a bit more space, but you don't really get out and about to see where places are.

Do you feel that the library knows about other organisations that could support you in your development?

I would hope so, I'd be very surprised and worried if you haven't.

Have you ever come across things you hadn't set out to find in the library?

Yeah, the interactive bit with the fiction and the other stuff with other libraries, I did find that strange at first, but there are times when you just

want a space and you don't want to be indulged in heavy reading, and it has to be said that the medical library is heavy reading to say the least, where light relief is enjoyed, greatly I think.

Comment [CM(M246): 5

Comment [CM(M247): 5

Well, a while ago, I actually saw somebody walking along, that I knew someone wanted to speak to and they walked past that persons office, and the door was open, and I thought to myself "It's much nicer to talk to somebody", e-mails are so non interactive, and that's half the trouble in this place, there's not enough interaction between managers and what people do, there's too many managers that are coming in and trying to work this place like a factory, and it's not a factory, it's a hospital, and I think we've lost that sign that we're here to help people and not rush people through the system.

(interviewer dialogue about library use / hospital interaction)

Oh yes, pace is a lot slower, but you interact when you want to interact, you're not forced to interact and that makes a big difference in the minimum time that you've got for yourself. I normally start at say, quarter past eight, and leave at quarter to five, and other than that hour, you're pressurised to do X, Y & Z and I've just had a row this week with the admissions people because my boss says he'll do one thing, you know he's not doing it, but he doesn't want to rock the boat, and I find that very awkward because I would just turn round and say, "no, there's a cut off time for that size of letter", and we have to take figures and he will...if they turn up 20 minutes later say Yeah, I'll do that for you" but you know he's going to put it on the side, so yeah when they come down and say "oh, the other guy does it, why can't you do it?".

Oh, it has to be, I mean, when I had the chief exec supposedly walking round with me doing the rounds, he was so negative, saying "we haven't got the money for this, we haven't got the money for that", but a new manager will turn up and when we mention this to a certain manager, she turns round and says I haven't got enough managers to manage the managers, and I just thought "how Dads Army is that?".

Have you ever asked / would you feel comfortable asking library staff about training on "modern technologies" e.g. social media Twitter, Facebook, apps, Kindle?

I hadn't even thought about it, but that would probably be a very good way of upgrading to be a 'silver surfer' on mobile phones, and I've got part of the technology, but it would be very helpful if there was somebody else who could tell you "well, this is what you can do with your phone to pick up this information and all of this, that and the other, without having to go to a PC and whatever.

Comment [CM(M248): 15

(interviewer dialogue about policy and development)

Yeah, that would be tremendously helpful.

That would be an absolute godsend, to me personally, but because I didn't know you could ask, I never thought about it.

Well at the moment, you've got a radiographer out here and you've got somebody from the path lab and they're interacting, you do get an awful lot of nurses, even nurses that have retired that come in and do voluntary work or whatever, are keeping up with whatever's going on by spending an hour or two a week in the library.

You do notice, there's probably a hard core of about 50 people that you see on a regular basis, that spend a lot of time here.

Do you trust the library staff? If yes, why?

I've never found them anything other than trustworthy, and there are places in this place that do a similar sort of service that you think to yourself "Yeah, am I asking the right questions of the right person?"

It's a nicer atmosphere here, I think a lot of things that go on in this place are down to atmosphere, and the people that are there are producing that atmosphere, I know you've lost half of your staff recently, but you've never stopped having that atmosphere where, even if they were stretched to the limit, you can ask something, and you come back with a polite answer, and it makes all the difference.

Anything to add?

Yes, you've given me with an insight into some of the stuff that I didn't know you provided, so I shall try and use it to the best of my ability.

Participant 100

Do you have any strong beliefs about workplace libraries?

My personal opinion of libraries is that they've been extremely useful throughout my whole academic career, it's helped me with studies, basically everything.

Comment [MC249]: 3

Why do you come to this library?

Currently I'm using it for my dissection course and now I've transferred to St George's, I still come over because some of my work is here and I know the staff who are extremely friendly and they're willing to help, so that's why I come back, another reason is that, for me, with the computer system, it's always available for me, usually at the medical school, the students have taken the computers.

Comment [MC250]: 3

What do you use the library for?

Why do you choose to come to the library rather than go elsewhere?

For me, because it's convenient, I know the staff well, they're always willing to bend over backwards just to help me and it's also to visit other staff from other departments, it's just a friendly atmosphere.

Comment [MC251]: 3

Last month, how many times did you come to the library?

It was every day. As you probably know, you've seen me every day.

How long do you stay on average?

Do you come during working hours and / or during your breaks?

On average, it's usually my lunch break, so you're talking just under one hour.

How would you describe the library environment / physical space?

Physical space? Now that I can compare and contrast with another hospital, I personally think this library should invest a lot more money into what's available, because certain books that are used, I've noticed are either out of date, or some of them were actually missing, which I don't know the reason why, even though we've looked for them.

Much more computer space. I also disagree with blocking certain e-mail access because, for me, I need to send information from one hospital to another, or from home and I find it inconvenient with USB encrypted, I can appreciate why, because of patient confidentiality, but that is the only thing I would say negatively about the CUH library, because sometimes, you just can't get your work done, I'm not the only one to say that, some of my colleagues have said that.

Comment [MC252]: 10

Do you bring your own books, journals, magazines, reports or do you use library resources – books, journals whilst you are here.

I use the hospital and I also use the internet, bringing my own material, I can't because it's encrypted, so there's no point me bringing items over, and some of the books I do have to use in the hospital library, or even the medical school because CUH just doesn't have the information which I require or that have actually been missing.

One example is, I did a case study on a prostate cancer patient, and the volume I wanted, it was 1234, I wanted 2 and volume 2 was actually missing, so that's one example.

And I also noticed, from my own experience, the medical school has about 20 copies, while this hospital has just the one, and I think there should be at least 2, if there's one on loan, at least there is one for staff.

Do you use library PCs or do you bring your own device?

I use library PC because some of my work is on hospital net, but unfortunately, I have considered bringing my own PC, at the medical school, they supply staff with PC's and I've noticed that, with even more students, they have about 20 plus laptops for their students, and I would recommend that here, because the amount of times I hear, "why do you have to bring your own", so that's one example.

Do you use the library wifi?

That is a no, because we know we're being charged, I know it's only pounds, but it's the principle of the matter, whereby ,at St George's, it's completely free throughout the whole hospital, NHS & medical school and it really is a place of **learning**, so why are we paying to use a service when we're actually working here, so it's out of principle, not out of costs, I really think, and my colleagues say the same, why are we paying for something that we work here, and now we go to another hospital, everything's completely free.

Comment [CM(M253): 22

What would make you come to the library more?

What I've just mentioned, for me, I live in South Croydon, so actually going to the public library where you have to queue, here it's just distance wise, it's just so convenient. Unfortunately, there's a lot of barriers stopping staff such as myself using it to it's full capacity really.

How could the Trust encourage you to use the library more?

I think from what I've just said, because, without being too rude, I don't think higher management understand what staff of all levels here require, they just think, it's a PGMC or a UGMC, that's great, but I think they'd have to use it, or be on an actual course to understand what we require, because a lot of what I require, isn't available to me, so that is one factor.

I only come here because I know the people, the PC, and you guys are willing to help me, you're always here to help me, so I think really it's more of an issue not of staff, yes there could be more staff, because you guys are stressed, but the staff are, what can I say? they're perfect,

it's really the infrastructure what goes into the library which is the biggest problem, and again, going back to what I've said before, it is just what everyone says.

People who I know who are of consulting levels don't even use the library anymore because it's just...they're wasting their time coming over here, so that's another thing, and these are consulting level, let alone my level.

Is the way library staff behave towards you important?

Well, I've never had...the staff here have always been great to me, they treat me like one of the family, I can't see any complaints to be honest with you, I've been here for ten years plus and it's just been such a...I come back here just to say 'Hi' sometimes, I don't know if you've noticed, and it's again, staff wise is not a problem, yes there could be more staff because that's for your benefit, but it's just...just looking round now compared to the medical school, it's just...even my own department in my own block probably has more books than here, I'm not exaggerating, because sometimes you just think...I know it could be better, it's just possibly higher management will have to come down and have a look themselves.

Is the way library staff behave towards you different from other staff in the trust?

No, because you guys are great, and possibly, I know a lot of other people in different departments, they treat me the same, even now if I needed some help...I was going to go to my department, (inaudible) you've actually saved me time, luckily the work was there so I was able to do this, but yeah, the books, they were just there wasted, you helped me with that one...so yeah.

Would a poor encounter with library staff dissuade you from visiting the library again? If so why?

Yes, I mean, yes and no, because if you get a negative image, you will always have a negative opinion of the person or the persons, but I don't think it would stop me because at the end of the day, I'm still on the course, I do still need library resources, but I think it's still important, I think very important.

Does your Manager support a learning environment within the workplace where the sharing of knowledge and skills is encouraged?

My manager didn't, she actually deterred, because she didn't want to spend money, and we all got very frustrated. It took me forever just to

get on my course and it's wasted some people's time when they didn't even have the opportunity, luckily for me, but once the manager left, things started rolling, so my old manager sort of stopped people from learning because she didn't want to spend money, which is, we just thought...we were just shaking our heads. and it took HR and managers higher up to say "this is getting silly, none of your staff are X,Y,Z," and a lot of people have been frustrated from my own department and, I was just shaking my head..."you need us, why are you stopping us?" But then we knew why so then yes ,I didn't have much support I'd say. My new manager, yes, she's great, she bent over backwards, forever grateful for that, so yeah.

Have you ever used library's fiction collection or books on prescription collection or other resources for your own personal development, not relating to your work?

No I haven't. I was really concentrating on my course.

Comment [CM(M254): 31

Do you feel the library is hierarchical? A place that anyone can come into?

Yes, everyone is entitled to knowledge, I've not noticed anything since I've been here, yes you see some consultants studying here as well, but I wouldn't know how it worked if it did.

Do you feel the library is part of the networks within the organisation?

I've made many friends through the library, so in a way, beside learning and gaining knowledge here, you also make friends here.

Comment [MC255]: 3

Comment [MC256]: 22

Comment [MC257]: 3

Do you feel the library staff know people in the Trust?

Yes, I've had experience where certain library staff have asked for help from other department.

Comment [MC258]: 6

Do you feel that the library knows about other organisations that could support you in your development?

I would say yes, you guys advised me to go to the British library when you didn't have a book, so you guys know your stuff, yeah.

Have you ever come across things you hadn't set out to find in the library?

Yes.

Have you ever asked / would you feel comfortable asking library staff about training on "modern technologies" e.g. social media Twitter, Facebook, apps, Kindle?

No, I know how to do that.

Do you find the library a social environment where you can meet colleagues on a different level from other places in the workplace?

Yep.

Do you trust the library staff? If yes, why?

Yes, because, I think it's built on years of trust really, and years of seeing each other. I come in to learn, you guys actually give me the trust, you guys are willing to help me etc, get me journals in the past, I would say it's more you guys putting towards me rather than the other way round, so yes.

Comment [MC259]: 19

Comment [MC260]: 22

Comment [MC261]:

Participant 110

Do you have any strong beliefs about workplace libraries?

No.

Why do you come to this library?

It depends really, if you look historically, I would perhaps be prompted to come to the library because I'd been doing a course, so there were reasons there, those reasons aren't applicable now because I'm not currently studying, so they were important reasons why I came because your team are always so helpful when I was doing study part-time and didn't have very easy access to the university library, so this was convenient, and also there were very big libraries when you're doing things part-time, you don't get to know the library so well, the people there, so everything takes much longer, this was a smaller library, people knew me, so it's much easier to come in and access people, talk to people, express what I needed and get a response.

Comment [MC262]: 31

Comment [MC263]: 6

Comment [MC264]: 31

What do you use the library for?

It's very unpredictable because I'm so busy in my work. I often start the day and think "I must pop by the library" and I'll bring something that I want to read and I'll come here because it's a quiet space, I like the low chairs, they're a bit more comfortable on the legs, sometimes I put my feet up, and read something work related, so that's kind of an unplanned visit. I quite like coming and dipping into things like the health service journal, might pick up the one on dementia, so again, unplanned, trying to do something that's not work unrelated, but just gives my brain a bit of a different space, it's sort of relaxing.

Comment [MC265]: 5

Comment [MC266]: 16

Comment [MC267]: 5

Comment [MC268]:

Why do you choose to come to the library rather than go elsewhere?

Because there aren't very many spaces, I would go somewhere like the chapel because that's another quiet space where there aren't too many people, but the chairs aren't so low and I like the sense that the chair is comfortable when my legs are down all the time, makes me sound very unfit, I'm not really, but when they're hanging down all the time, you know, your legs don't feel so comfortable, at least when you're lower, you're more comfortable.

Comment [MC269]: 16

And other places, if you got to the main restaurant, they don't want you to sit in the main restaurant in the comfy chairs which are lower and unless you've bought something... You can go down to main reception, again, there's sort of more standard chairs there, I have gone down there as a different space as well, but I tend to feel I ought to be buying something, so the library is quiet...

I think in general, you're not interrupted about work, although one time I was, someone spotted me and it made me think twice about where I sat in the library because they spotted me, and they came in and told

me to do something and I went back and I immediately did that thing for that person because they were senior and that individual never did anything with it, and I thought, that's interesting.

(Interviewer dialogue regarding 'private space')

I think that's right, now you know me, and I think you're always very respectful of me, and I appreciate that. Sometimes I come in with the Bible sometimes, and I come in and take my shoes off and I put my feet up, never have any kind of breaks because we eat at our desk, and I get to half two in the afternoon and I think I need to just try and relax a little bit for a few minutes, so I come in and do that, and I appreciate the way you don't interrupt me, I know that if I came knocking, you'd say "ooh, no, no, come on in" so that's really what I'm saying...there's that sense that...and I see other people in here and I would never ask them about work matters, you know, I wouldn't even interrupt them to say "hello" unless they looked at me and smiled and quietly said "Hello" If I went to the main restaurant, everybody...that's kind of like a space where people can come up to you and interrupt you and say "I'm really glad I've seen you here, can I just mention X or Y?"

Comment [MC270]:

Last month, how many times did you come to the library?

I've probably only been four or five times, and I want to come, but when you're so busy, and sometimes you're under so much pressure that you aren't come, and I brought in a book this morning that's about... it's called 'Brilliant Manager', and I've read it in the past, but I wanted to read it again, but here we are, and it's ten past three and I actually had to ring you at two to say "I won't make it for two" because I brought that book and thought "if I can only get ten minutes, I'm going to go and sit in the library" I knew I was going to get into work really early, and I debated about reading at home and I thought "No, you've got so much to do, get in early" because that book, you can read when you're feeling tired later in the day, but I won't get in here today.

Comment [MC271]: 5

Comment [MC272]: 5

Comment [MC273]: 5

Comment [MC274]: 5

But it's not through lack of will, it's like a reward almost. In some respects.

How long do you stay on average?

Between ten minutes and half an hour.

Do you come during working hours and / or during your breaks?

Yes.

How would you describe the library environment / physical space?

Calm. Peaceful.

Comment [MC275]: 23

Comment [MC276]: 16

(Interviewer prompts question of differences between library and other spaces)

I think it's quite difficult to describe because I could sit in my office, I could lower my chair a bit, I could shut the door and the team wouldn't disturb me, but I'd be surrounded by all this work I've got to do and the computer screen, it's not the same, it's that different physical location and quietness.

Comment [MC277]: 16

And you can have space around you, because there are less people in here in a way, so you feel a sense of space, and it just takes you away somehow from the intensity and strain of what you're working in, even if you actually haven't got people physically at you all the time, um, it feels like that.

Comment [MC278]: 2

Do you bring your own books, journals, magazines, reports or do you use library resources – books, journals whilst you are here.

Mostly I'm bringing my own, occasionally I think "ooh, I'm now interested in this or that" and I will come in and get a book, but I don't necessarily generally read them here, I tend to get them here and take them away. So when I'm coming here, I might, because I know I've got my journal with me, I can bring it and sit in another space, it's something I don't have to sit and look at a computer.

Do you use library PCs or do you bring your own device?

Rarely, and on the occasion when I've used them, I've used them to try and get a bit of space away from the intensity of the environment that I'm working in, I have an office within an office, it's quite a small office, I've got no complaints, I'm grateful for it, but it feels...some of it's almost psychological, you can be interrupted at any point, phone can ring, e-mails are coming through, even if you try and switch e-mails off, um, hours and hours and hours of that. It's a lot for the brain to cope with, so if I can come here, it's almost as if I can sit and look at all my e-mails and try and read through some of them and clear some of them, respond to them, but I don't have all the other sense of stimuli coming in quite the same way, so that may be a help for me to concentrate on a job that needs doing.

Comment [MC279]: 2

Comment [MC280]: 7

Do you use the library wifi?

No, on occasion I come into you and have talks to you about it, about using it, I think it's one area that I haven't really mastered that I would like to and that would be to be able to come in here at any time and be able to look at webinars, there's lots of material available, especially in the States, where I'm a membership of the professional body, I could never sign in at the right time because of the time-zone difference, but to be able to just come in and be able to sit and read webinars...I mean, it would be lovely to do from the desk in my office if I could do that, and I think, partly again, it's the time, because as I've said to you, my visits here are so unpredictable and there are so many competing requirements on my time, that again is almost like a luxury.

What would make you come to the library more?

If I was less busy. If I was less busy, I would come and bring work that I would like to work on to maybe do some more of that innovation development that often I can't do because I'm pushing paper around that has to be done at a desk because there's so much kind of e-mail work involved and maybe accessing different files that are in a shared drive.

So I feel I would come here more for innovation, for moving on and progressing, not me personally, but actually me and infection control.

How could the Trust encourage you to use the library more?

I think it's a; about the whole time/pressure thing, all the sort of short staffing in different areas, sometimes people have such a huge workload that it doesn't permit you to use the library more.

Do you think it would be useful if trust policies on the subject of well-being recommended spending time in the library to encourage personal and professional development?

I think from what I've said, in terms of it helping my well-being, I come here to help my well-being, so when I feel I've had seven/eight intense hours, this can help my well-being because it's just some place I can just sit and process things in a different way, maybe not work related, so that's important for my well-being. Helps manage stress, helps cope with stress.

Everybody should be doing personal and professional development.

Much of it, to be fair, can be accessed from a computer and that's the way you're expected to access it, but speaking personally, it's quite difficult to do it when, at your work environment, you're under so much pressure in the here and now. If that makes sense?

I'll tell you what I'm debating about at the moment, I feel so under pressure at work, and the volume of e-mails, part of my professional development and updating, and partly for the benefit for infection control here, or very much so, is I have the library Health Service journals link that comes through that gives me feeds from infection control journals.

I have another one as well, the IV forum, and I'm under leadership one and I'm...infact I thought I'd cancelled the leadership because I just couldn't um...read e-mails, but I'm seriously thinking about cancelling both of them because I'm not able to deal with them and look at them which I want to and it worries me that I haven't cancelled them yet because, professionally and for the good of the organisation and the way I work, I should be keeping up to date, but I'm bombarded with so many other e-mails, that I'm in danger of not responding to the trust e-mails because of these other e-mails that are there almost getting in the way.

Comment [MC281]: 34

Comment [MC282]: 34

Comment [MC283]: 13

Comment [MC284]: 12

Comment [MC285]: 12

Is the way library staff behave towards you different from other staff in the trust?

I don't know how to answer that really because the library staff are always polite and friendly, but there is wide variation around the trust in how people behave to you there, and people can be nice and friendly to you there, but you can also deal with people that are not nice and friendly, behave in different ways

Comment [MC286]: 16

Comment [MC287]: 16

Comment [MC288]: 16

But that's a requirement of every member of trust staff, part of our registration as a health care organisation is about quality and diversity, and many, many staff like nurses have their code of conduct, so people may not be adhering to it, but...

Would a poor encounter with library staff dissuade you from visiting the library again? If so why?

Yes. If I felt somebody was unhelpful and a bit abrupt with me, yes.

I suppose to be fair, it might affect me not in terms of coming and putting my feet up and reading a piece of work I've brought, it would affect me in whether I asked the library for help for anything in particular that I thought they might be able to help me with.

If someone wasn't being particularly helpful and then I came in and asked them if they've got a book about something then I wouldn't bother to go back, I think that's probably true in many walks of life, if somebody's not very nice to you in a restaurant then you don't go back there.

Does your Manager support a learning environment within the workplace where the sharing of knowledge and skills is encouraged?

No idea. My relationship with my line manager has always been quite distant and I'm not sure if this is in their mind or not.

I would go and have one to one's, explain any difficulties, they would help me unblock them, we haven't talked about this though. So I couldn't really answer fairly on their behalf.

Do you have personal objectives in mind when you use the library?

There's that unconscious objective to help me cope with the stress and the strain, so much about coping when you stay and work in this environment.

So that's my objective.

Have you ever used library's fiction collection or books on prescription collection or other resources for your own personal development, not relating to your work?

I never realised there were books on prescription, I'd noticed there were lots of books on depression and things like that and I wondered why there were so many of them.

No I've picked them up because I've never struggled with things like depression and they didn't particularly attract me those books, and I've noticed the fiction, but I'm just too busy to read fiction, but I have noticed it with "ooh, that's interesting, some fiction", but life doesn't allow fiction.

Do you find the library a social environment where you can meet colleagues on a different level from other places in the workplace?

I don't regard it as a social environment, I almost come here to be alone.

I come here for peace and there are one or two people in here, and I see them regularly, maybe at lunchtime, and I think maybe they've come here for peace as well, I can relate to that, I'm not going to disturb them. I respect them.

Comment [CM(M289): 16

Comment [CM(M290): 16

Do you think using the library helps you achieve trust objectives, by giving you a thinking space?

No, not directly, I think it probably helps the trust in a sense by helping people to cope and have the stamina to stay in the job, then the trust wants to retain its nurses, that's good.

Comment [CM(M291): 24

Do you feel the library is part of the networks within the organisation?

No, not particularly, It's not that I mean I don't think you're not part of us, I don't see you as part of the network in the sense of when I come in you're somehow helping me to network, because I think what I like is the separateness, and it's the separateness that's the attraction. Infact, you're quite convenient for my office, if you were in a different building, it might make it even better, but I don't think it would because I often want to go to the chapel and play the piano, but the distance of having to go outside stops me, so no, I like almost the sense of separateness.

Do you feel the library staff know people in the Trust?

I know that you do, but I don't know about your colleagues. That's because we chat informally about things and it's clear to me that you interact with different people and you do know people.

Do you feel that the library knows about other organisations that could support you in your development?

I'm not sure you do, but I'm not sure that's necessarily a right kind of assessment to make. You helped me get books for my masters, but that's all really, it's something about the space, the separate space that I think is the real mark for me.

Have you ever come across things you hadn't set out to find in the library?

Often in the past, not so much recently, I've picked up books about management and other topics, sometimes I've taken them and I haven't really read them, but I think they've kind of floated through my mind, maybe dipped into them briefly, so yes, especially if things aren't on the shelf but new books are out and visible.

Comment [CM(M292): 5

Have you ever asked / would you feel comfortable asking library staff about training on "modern technologies" e.g. social media Twitter, Facebook, apps, Kindle?

Yes, I would always feel happy about asking. I've never asked because of time, I've got so much to cope with and so much to do I'm struggling, so I didn't want anything more to do.

Yes, It's so exhausting, I've got an i-Pad, and I use the it a lot for work related studies, well, not work related, but for my university and I find that quite an effective way of reading things, I'm not using it for Twitter accounts, that sort of thing, It's for reading electronically, and I can read better in that form, but when I'm at work there is just so much electronic stuff, it is exhausting, I can't cope with any more.

Comment [CM(M293): 31

Comment [CM(M294): 5

It's not necessarily face to face interaction with a person, it's stepping away from the myriad of computer generated information and material.

Comment [CM(M295): 26

Comment [CM(M296): 15

It's too exhausting, there's so much of it in different forms, on so many different topics, that you're almost distracted by one so you're trying to do so much multi-tasking, each one needs you to dedicate time to it, but you're surrounded by bits of paper you've printed off, you have a telephone which can bring more messages, potentially a bleep, but I'm trying to put that t one side, so it's this combination of information coming through on e-mail, information that's electronic that you have to review, comment on, darting about on the internet, darting onto the intranet, looking in the shared drive, I mean, I'm not thick, but the pace you're dealing with is hour after hour after hour...

Comment [CM(M297): 15

Comment [CM(M298): 15

One of the things I do like to do, and I don't do it here really because of the lack of space, is that on my own days off, when I've not got work to do, I would go to a coffee shop and I would have a bit of paper with me, I might have my i-Pad and notebook, but I actually haven't got that computer screen there, I'm not sat in that upright position looking at the computer screen, again, it's a different space, and perhaps you are relying on technology, but not quite with the same intensity.

Comment [CM(M299): 26

Comment [CM(M300): 26

Comment [CM(M301): 26

You're absolutely right, because it's not home, and there's some drawbacks in being at home, there are other distractions there, it's not work, it's that third space, available for work, but not available anywhere else in the hospital.

So no pressure can move you on in the same way...

Do you trust the library staff? If yes, why?

Yes, I would trust them, I would never have thought of the idea that you might particularly tell other people what I'm looking for, but then I suppose I never come about things that you told anybody about. So in terms of trust, it's not something I'd ever regard.

Anything further you'd like to add?

Only really I guess to say that my colleagues have said what a valuable space it is, and the organisation would be unwise to say we don't need this space, it's not a good utilisation of space when I really think the whole well-being thing, for those of us who know it's here, it is a valuable way to help well-being. That may not be why the library is here, but that's why some of us are using it.

Even with the WebEx and things like that, and that discourages you when you haven't got the time to learn all these things, if you're not naturally 'techy', or respond to the technology and you're not sure if it's the technology or you...

Comment [CM(M302): 26

Comment [CM(M303): 26

I would perceive IT here very much as busy, stressed, short staffed, appear to solve, to focus on the here and now, can we access patient data? Rather than actually having the capacity or time in their brain to innovate and help with those types of aspects, that'll be the cherry on the cake, they might want to, but realistically, I think there's more likelihood that the library has the potential, not that you're not busy.

Comment [CM(M304): 26

Comment [CM(M305): 34

It probably helps your staff that you're working so hard that probably helps you to feel calm, because you've got the space and the quietness, so people aren't coming in and having intense conversations about problems.

I'd love to work in this environment all the time. It's not the place for managers to come in having spotted somebody.

Participant 130

Do you have any strong beliefs about workplace libraries?

I think they are important. I think they offer resources that probably aren't available in other areas of the trust and expertise which aren't available elsewhere. And I think they are quite central if we are a learning organisation, it's quite important that we offer that resources which should be quite extensive and it needs to be for all staff not just nurses and doctors.

Comment [MC306]: 8

Comment [MC307]: 8

Comment [MC308]: 22

Why do you come to this library?

This is the only library I am aware of in the trust. It is positioned quite near a public eating area so I think a lot of staff are aware that it is here if they use that area but then it is only on one side of the trust. So in a way a lot of staff may be totally ignorant that there is a library on this side of the Trust. I know where it is. Sometimes have to request journals and articles for my boss who is a senior director in the trust. I sometimes come to use it for my own learning if I am doing a course. I come to use the pcs. And I have used it for WebEx as well as this is the only facility that I am aware of that is easily accessible. The trust only has 2-3 areas and 2 of those are in director's offices and is very hard to set up but here is it easy and you are supported by the library staff and yes, it's a quiet room for you to hold it.

Comment [MC309]: 22

Comment [MC310]:

Comment [MC311]: 8

Comment [MC312]: 16

Last month, how many times did you come to the library?

Erm, I think I would like to come a lot more to be honest. I think I should be using it a lot more. I would probably come between 3-4 times a month.

How long do you stay on average?

It really depends on what it is for. If it for WebEx I'll be here for at least an hour, an hour and a half. If it is just to pick up a book or return a book then it will be very quick. If I am looking for a book I might stay half an hour. It is variable.

Do you come during working hours and / or during your breaks?

I never come out of hours. Erm, I don't tend to come here to take a break but it is a lovely space in which to take a break because it is quiet and peaceful.

Comment [MC313]: 16

Comment [MC314]: 16

How would you describe the library environment / physical space?

It is maybe what you've got in here for such a small space really. It is informal I think and comfortable for staff. It's quiet, peaceful. It is welcoming cos you have lots of information by the door. You have a really helpful team. It is somewhere you feel you can come and just be yourself and not be watched and you have a bit of freedom.

Comment [MC315]: 30

Comment [MC316]: 28

Comment [MC317]: 16

Comment [MC318]: 16

Comment [MC319]: 32

Comment [MC320]: 6

Comment [MC321]: 35

Do you bring your own books, journals, magazines, reports or do you use library resources – books, journals whilst you are here.

Generally to use resources but actually I have done that before if I have needed to edit a film I have come here because it is quiet. It's great here to concentrate.

Comment [MC322]: 16

Comment [MC323]: 7

Do you use the library wifi?

Yes, actually that is a very strong drive to come here but on several occasions it hasn't worked and that has put me off from coming back which is a real shame. I think it is a massive draw for me to use the wifi especially to do a lot of uploading of videos to YouTube and things that we can't do in the normal trust, you know high security trust internet uploading things.

(How did you feel when you couldn't access the wifi?)

The only other place is at home. I end up doing it in my own hours at home so that is a bad thing. It's just disappointing because I know when it works its brilliant. It is a brilliant space to use it in. Just to add that the wifi anywhere else in the trust that you have to pay for so this is the only free source of wifi in the trust. And for staff there needs to be some spaces that offer this. Come on this is 2015 there should be places where you can have free wifi; it is not really fair that staff have to pay to get full access.

Comment [MC324]: 8

Comment [MC325]: 8

What would make you come to the library more?

If I knew the wifi was definitely working then I would come more! It is on the wrong side of the site. I am based opposite. I think it is a long way to come over here for my break, that is half my break gone when I get here. If there were more events I would definitely come to the library and that might spill over into my work life that I just use this space and see it as my space that I come to and use.

Does your Manager support a learning environment within the workplace where the sharing of knowledge and skills is encouraged?

They don't but they do encourage my self-development so maybe management need to be promoting the library more and engage with them more about the resources available. I mean only recently I found out just from chatting with the library manager about some things that you do in the library which I was totally oblivious to and some of that was on staff wellbeing and since then I have definitely taken books out that are of interest to me. I think you don't remember the library is here unless you've got reminders to use it.

Comment [MC326]: 12

I don't know how you feel about this but I sometimes think that if you are seen to be in a library just reading a book that you are seen as skiving and the fact that it is very essential in your role to be researching or picking up a book and reading especially as some users use it as a rest area it does reinforce that the library is not somewhere where you do your stuff you do extra stuff outside your job.

Comment [MC327]: 5

Comment [MC328]: 5

Comment [MC329]:

How could the Trust encourage you to use the library more?

Maybe, I don't know really. Flagging up different resources that are in the library at induction or on particular course that we do or health and wellbeing. You know just feeding it into more of the trust structurally.

Do you think it would be useful if trust policies on the subject of well-being recommended spending time in the library to encourage personal and professional development?

Yeah definitely. I mean I know the trust has to document the work we do around wellbeing for staff so are we not feeding into that already? There is something the environment of the library, it is not corporate it is more stimulating and somewhere where you come to get away. For the environment we are in it is a very unique space.

Comment [MC330]: 2

Is the way library staff behave towards you important?

Oh definitely, it's all about your customer experience, coming to the library and how welcome you feel. I think some of your staff are more friendly and engaging than others and it really comes across and it does let the experience down sometimes.

Comment [MC331]: 32

Is the way library staff behave towards you different from other staff in the trust?

Those codes etc you mention, you encompass those. When I come into the library you immediately engage me in things about what's going on and what do I need whereas some of your other team members don't do that so much. I suppose I have partitioned you off from other staff and you are right it should be the same values that should apply. We do see you separately I think.

(Why is that?)

I guess you are like neutral aren't you actually. You are a bit separated from the politics and also bound by your own values that is for the greater good.

Would a poor encounter with library staff dissuade you from visiting the library again?

Erm yes potentially I think it would cos if they're are not helpful or I might choose to do my work at home instead of coming up to speak to someone who isn't helpful or defiantly in terms of showing me what is

Comment [MC332]: 6

Comment [MC333]: 6

available in terms of resources. I would probably come up on a different day.

Do you have personal objectives in mind when you use the library?

It isn't a space you come to talk is it really. I personally use if I have a learning objective for myself but how often I do that I can't say I don't that very often, I should do that. More professional than personally.

Comment [MC334]: 22

Comment [MC335]:

Have you ever used library's fiction collection or books on prescription collection or other resources for your own personal development, not relating to your work?

I don't think I would use the personal ones although I would be encouraged to go in my own library and seek them out because I would be too embarrassed to be honest. But I think it is great you are doing that for health and wellbeing. I probably wouldn't take them out because of the lack of confidentiality.

Comment [MC336]: 13

The fiction too I probably wouldn't to be honest. I have a kindle; I download everything on the kindle. I don't tend to carry books around with me.

(You know we can send articles to your kindle)

No I didn't know that! That's great! Do staff know about these things? Unless you seek this out you wouldn't know about this.

Do you find the library a social environment where you can meet colleagues on a different level from other places in the workplace?

I don't because it isn't an area where you can talk. Not really. There is a small meeting room so it's very useful to use the WebEx. So social through WebEx.

Comment [MC337]: 25

Do you think using the library helps you achieve trust objectives, by giving you a thinking space?

Oh yeah definitely; absolutely.

Do you feel the library is part of the networks within the organisation?

Oh yes, you are very attached to education, medical, clinical groups more so than other staff groups so not so much admin. My previous roles have been admin and clerical and I don't think I came up here particularly.

Comment [MC338]: 11

Do you feel the library staff know people in the Trust?

They probably know a lot of people, yeah. You seem to integrate yourself and team in other things as well.

Do you feel that the library knows about other organisations that could support you in your development?

I'm sure you do I am sure you've got all that information! If I needed to find anything out I would probably here as a starting point.

Comment [MC339]: 15

Have you ever come across things you hadn't set out to find in the library?

No not really. I think on a notice board there are all these interesting stuff and I probably would have a wander around every time I come up here just to see what's happening around the area. It would be helpful if things were highlighted more then I would be more likely to use the library more.

Have you ever asked / would you feel comfortable asking library staff about training on "modern technologies"?

Oh yes obviously Kindle!

Now I know you have that resource I will definitely be asking more advice on it. I am fairly literate on most of the other things. I wouldn't necessarily see that as your role though actually to advise on IT. Our trust policy sort of discourages us to use a lot of social media without it getting signed off first. You have to be very careful and stuff. I think a lot of people know what Twitter is but they don't know how to use it properly and well.

Comment [MC340]:

Do you trust the library staff? If yes, why?

I think it's just personal; there is no privacy and dignity in the library.

Everyone can see what you are doing. It's quite open the library isn't it.

I would trust any staff member whether you are a library member or not but I wouldn't share with any member of staff.

Comment [MC341]:

Participant 140

Do you have any strong beliefs about workplace libraries?

Erm I do because I think they are a really important part of the NHS as it is a **learning** organisation and so I see the library as you know, one particular aspect of that. It's got a lot it can offer in that sense. So it should be place where people can come and **learn** and **share** really.

Comment [CM(M342): 22

Comment [CM(M343): 22

Comment [CM(M344): 21

Why do you come to this library?

Because I find the staff **welcoming**. It's on route to where I go and take lunch usually. I am reassured, for me it's like a quiet space so I see a synergy between the library **quiet** space and a time to reflect so that is why it's important to me. My diary is marked out usually between 1-2pm saying where I am going be which is PGMC.

Comment [CM(M345): 32

Comment [CM(M346): 16

What do you use the library for?

It's looking at the health service journal, er and in particular just around some of the **reflective** bits just to get a bigger picture of what is happening within the NHS generally. So the health service journal arguably is the most widely read of all. I would choose that above the nursing times.

Comment [CM(M347): 1

Why do you choose to come to the library rather than go elsewhere?

I see the PGMC, because this is a university hospital site, I see this very much linked with, and I suppose it's just about the **learning** aspect which I'm really passionate about. The NHS **learning** as a **learning** organisation, we might say we are a **learning** organisation but how does that translate in practice? It's about behaviours, so I like to be visible, I come into the library.

Comment [CM(M348): 22

Comment [CM(M349): 22

Comment [CM(M350): 22

Comment [CM(M351): 22

Last month, how many times did you come to the library?

I come in pretty regularly maybe once or twice a week. It's face to face contact.

How long do you stay on average?

Erm it depends actually. If I pick up the HSJ it's going to be a minimum of fifteen to twenty minutes. Erm, sometimes if I get more involved then it might actually be a longer period. Occasionally it might be a shorter interaction, it depends really. I might be looking for this journal, can you locate this article and I know you very kindly sign post for me. It really can be variety so the time I am here depends on the time I've got and the nature of the particular project I'm working on.

Do you come during working hours and / or during your breaks?

It can be any actually cos if I'm coming through the library, I see the library as no different from any other department in other words I can in and I don't differentiate between coming in the library and having interaction with the staff in here to any other aspect of my work so, for me it's quite perfectly legitimate for me to come in as I have come in today. I'm a senior manager and I am quite happy to take a seat on the comfy chairs in visible

full view of whoever is walking by and they can see I'm looking at a journal and I'd be more than happy to be challenged on that because I will give a clear and concise reason. If others want to see it as skiving I will give them a clear and concise reason that I am not and thus far no one has asked me but I am mindful of that. I suppose that is why I sometimes deliberately sit in a prominent position because it is quite legitimate for me to be there. I do it in that way rather than hide away outside.

How would you describe the library environment / physical space?

Erm, I visit libraries at the weekend and spend typically half an hour in there choosing some sort of material and also looking at the newspapers and the like. I've got a real empathy and endearment towards libraries; I think they have a valuable, societal benefit. It's a really good idea that libraries exist and not, if you like, become extinct because I know a lot of libraries are because of the changes in technology. So in this case here I just see it as a natural thing. I know candidly that a lot of money is going to be spent on this library and it is pretty obvious. You only have to look at the environment to say well, if you were to score it let's say, out of 10, er you would probably be hard pushed to give more than 5 out of 10. It's got to affect the way people use the space. Is it fit for purpose? A library environment which is now in part currently as we talk today 2015, we've got basins on the floor ready to collect water which are a health and safety hazard. 5 out of 10 is pushing it really. We do need to make the environment safe, we do need make it fit for purpose, and we do need to bring it up to the 21 century. There is a lot more that can be done really.

The business case has been approved and looked at so from my perspective it can't come soon enough really. The money being spent will really transform the service. LIA will suggest something, when doing a business case, what will the end user want and then you build your thing around that really. What is the opinion about our services? How will we know we have a better facility so questionnaires will be useful? We should be aiming for 10 out of 10 and if we fall short then how will we know we've fallen short?

Do you bring your own books, journals, magazines, reports or do you use library resources – books, journals whilst you are here?

If I come in here I want to be seen to be using library resources rather than bring my own in because it will almost be, I'm not saying this as a slight, I am thinking why would I want to be bringing in a Guardian or a Times let's say and sit and read those in here when they have not been provided by this service.

Do you use library PCs or do you bring your own device?

I think only on one occasion and that was basically to log on to the resource which escapes me. The clinical one, the clinical resources that's available.

Do you use the library wifi?

No. I wouldn't naturally think of that erm, what might encourage me to use that is if we move towards tablets. Some of peers are trundling around with technology that is enabled and they can get wifi wherever they are, and they are already logged on and I'm not in that bit. I think the roll out of IT, ipads to senior managers and the like, I think it should be rolled out more. What would be quite interesting is, think about this one for a second, is that I was offered to do a webinar recently because of the software package that we have and the organisation that provided, we pay a fee to this organisation but it looks as though I'm going to have to cancel the webinar because we haven't got a pc or laptop that is enabled. Our IT systems block it.

Comment [CM(M352): 26

Comment [CM(M353): 26

Comment [CM(M354): 26

(You can probably do it here) Oh maybe this is another conversation I could have then about trying to enable it, so if I can say that I want you to do a webex maybe for Friday (you can book it in, the IT room or you can book that room opposite as well). I might make some contact about the webex.

Comment [CM(M355): 26

What would make you come to the library more?

I think maybe more the environment. Maybe and just see, the whole thing needs reconfiguring really just to open it all out and make it more welcoming. It needs the wow factor. You want a library that is vibrant and used and you know, encourage people. I see you've got the drinks thing going there but there's probably some other things that could be done to make it just, you know, a little bit more, maybe more of a message from the director level as well. Does visible Wednesday include coming to the library?

Comment [CM(M356): 32

How could the Trust encourage you to use the library more?

I think there needs to be more of a steer, there needs to be an engagement by the Board, clear statement within a policy document, within the annual report, within the Board agenda to say what a valuable resource if they haven't already done it.

How does that too work in the community if we are an integrated care organisation what is the relationship, is this library about CUH site, how does the other sites, they may not be able to visit but can they draw on the resources? You can engage with them and about communication side of things.

Do you think it would be useful if trust policies on the subject of well-being recommended spending time in the library to encourage personal and professional development?

Most definitely yes however I would probably use a different narrative which is not how much time you want to spend in the library but what a valuable resource it is, this is what it offers and then some examples of how it is helped other professionals. We do so much around the physicality of people but the emotional needs are important and they need to be met and arguably the most important resource we have is the library to do that.

Is the way library staff behave towards you important?

Most definitely. So you have a bad interaction as you do in life, you tend to avoid especially if it's a negative reaction, you tend to avoid that situation that might actually mean avoiding that location, so it's crucial is the long and short of it.

Is the way library staff behave towards you different from other staff in the trust?

I think I'm pretty well placed to give a view about that. I currently do audits of all the departments so I know exactly the nature of those departments. Then library is all about not being rushed, not being fazed, the staff don't rush me. Contrast that with an audit or inspection where it is for a precise amount of time, it is much more time bound whereas coming to the library, you know, I'll come to library for as long as I need. That kind of answers things in that bad experiences are rare here. And days happens, I have poor encounters on the wards but return nonetheless. Time and pressure factor into things. People change under pressure and without resource. Contrast that to here, sense of calm and wellbeing.

Comment [CM(M357):

Does your Manager support a learning environment within the workplace where the sharing of knowledge and skills is encouraged?

I've got a new director so I don't actually know what he really thinks about that. Erm, they need to be a bit more appreciative is that there is elements of my job that would lend itself to home working, using a PC to do evidence based practice, so ok, so er, that's again part of the learning thing so let's look at work as also not just about CUH and the community, but I've often done work from 2 hours before I come in to work and then pinged in on an email. We need to look at how people work. It depends on who the manager is but some staff work from home and others don't. There ought to be more of an understanding around flexi working.

Comment [CM(M358): 22

The culture of the organisation, are we a learning organisation? We might say anecdotally that we are or where's the hard evidence to support it, so learning is an integral part and a fascination of what I am about, understand more.

Comment [CM(M359): 22

Comment [CM(M360): 22

Do you have personal objectives in mind when you use the library?

There can be both but I suspect...the real drivers to use the library are understanding more holistically what is going on in the NHS. I don't do it intrinsically for CUH, I think you put yourself first. I put myself first before everyone else on the basis that if I can put myself first I'm better placed to look others really, whatever that might be. Everyone is different of course.

Have you ever used library's fiction collection or books on prescription collection or other resources for your own personal development, not relating to your work?

Never used those. It raises the point though that who is the principle users of the library? And I know that all junior doctors for example they all have to do audit. They all should be doing audit and revalidation. Rightly or wrongly there might be a sense of it's a university so we need to be clear

in that what's that about. Is it about medical and nursing colleagues principally? I dip in because I consider myself loosely as an allied health professional. As long as my needs are met, then I'm quite happy to use the library really.

Do you find the library a social environment where you can meet colleagues on a different level from other places in the workplace?

Not really no. I don't see how that would evidence itself now. Hopefully that's an objective for the new library.

Do you think using the library helps you achieve trust objectives, by giving you a thinking space?

It does in that sense but I think it needs to do more.

Do you feel the library is part of the networks within the organisation?

I've no sense that you do, but that said looking at who is in the library I get a sense of who is coming in and why they are here. I get a sense that it's probably a spike in the matrix of people doing these **Postgraduate diplomas** that might encourage them to come here. I know a lot of staff get management days in the wards. Now how that relates and translates, it may be an opportunity to understand who benefits from that.

Comment [CM(M361): 31

Do you feel the library staff know people in the Trust?

I think you do

Do you feel that the library knows about other organisations that could support you in your development?

I would have said yes, obviously though our professional liaison that I can draw upon you as a well-grounded and well informed resource about I might tackle things differently so yeah in that sense I know you network.

Have you ever come across things you hadn't set out to find in the library?

Yes I have. There have been times I have come in looking for, er books on a piece of research on something and when I was going through the hardcopy library, the sections, because the library is indexed in such a way you can find links to other resources and linked information in different parts of the library.

Have you ever asked / would you feel comfortable asking library staff about training on "modern technologies"?

Not particularly. I mean I've got a twitter account, don't use it very often. I would probably be more inclined to use family than ask. So not necessarily. I know the trust has a social networking type policy stance on the use of social media, erm, about using it responsibly. So beyond that, no. I know John's got a blog and stuff like that but I sense it's still in its infancy and I suppose really we know that people make faux pas with putting stuff on social media it is probably its best to err on the side of

caution rather than get heavily involved in that. It's rather stick with the traditional email rather than go to social networking

Do you trust the library staff? If yes, why?

Yes, yeah, yeah. All that track record and evidence is that you've been able to sign post me a lot quicker than I've ever got there. Erm and that freed up my time more and yep, the bond of trust is there. So that is the expectation and it's fully realised really.

Appendix 6

Croydon Health Services ethical approval

Appendix 7

Informed consent

Croydon Health Services Library

February 2015

morag.clarkson@croydonhealth.nhs.uk

0208 401 3196 (direct line)

Dear colleague,

I am undertaking an MSc in Public Administration at London South Bank University

I am researching:

Why and how workplace library users utilise library space for non-library activities

Objectives:

- For what purposes do library users use the CHS library and the spaces within it?
- Why do CHS library users use the CHS library space rather than non-library locations?
- How do CHS library users think their use of the CHS library contributes to their feelings of well-being?
- How do CHS library users think their use of the CHS library space contributes to developing and maintaining workplace social relationships?

As a workplace library user would you consent to taking part in a short interview lasting about 30 minutes?

- All information collated will be confidential.

- All responses will be anonymised.
- Interviews will take place in the Library Manager's office, at a time convenient to you.

Please sign and date this letter to indicate your consent to participate in the research.

Please let me know when you will be able to meet with me, in the next two weeks.

Your participation is very much appreciated.

Best wishes,

Morag Clarkson

.....
.....

I,

.....
.....

give my consent to participate in MSc research conducted by Morag Clarkson

Signature:

Date:

I will be able to meet you at the following time(s)

I would like to receive a copy of your dissertation / the research results

(please delete as applicable)

Appendix 8

Interview schedule

Interview schedule

Why and how workplace library users utilise library space for non-library activities

Objectives:

- For what purposes do library users use the CHS library and the spaces within it?
- Why do CHS library users use the CHS library space rather than non-library locations?
- How do CHS library users think their use of the CHS library contributes to their feelings of well-being?
- How do CHS library users think their use of the CHS library space contributes to developing and maintaining workplace social relationships?

Library space

1. Do you have any strong beliefs about workplace libraries? (attitude and opinion, open)
2. Why do you come to this library? (behaviour, open)
3. What do you use the library for? (behaviour, open)

Probes

1. Reading
2. Studying
3. Thinking
4. Computer use
5. Meet colleagues
6. Working
7. Sleeping
8. Collaborative working
9. Other

4. Why do you choose to come to the library rather than go elsewhere? (behaviour, open)

1. Informal environment
2. Quiet
3. Close to my department
4. Doing a course
5. Comfortable furniture
6. Good place to meet colleagues
7. Other

5. Last month, how many times did you come to the library? (behaviour, closed)

1. Daily
2. Weekly

3. Monthly
 4. Many times a day
 5. Varies
 6. Other
6. How long do you stay on average? (behaviour, closed)
1. 10 – 20 minutes
 2. 30 minutes
 3. 1 hour
 4. 1-2 hours
 5. 4 hours
 6. All day
 7. All night
 8. Other
7. Do you come during working hours and / or during your breaks (behaviour, closed)
8. How would you describe the library environment / physical space: (attitude and opinion, open)
1. Comfort
 2. Size
 3. Quietness
 4. As an environment to focus when learning and working
 5. Informal
 6. Variety of study areas
 7. Attractive and welcoming
 8. Small
 9. Uncomfortable
 10. Other
9. Do you bring your own books, journals, magazines, reports or do you use library resources – books, journals whilst you are here. (behaviour, open)
10. Do you use library PCs or do you bring your own device? (behaviour, closed)
11. Do you use the library wifi? (behaviour, closed)
12. What would make you come to the library more? (behaviour, open)
1. Manager allowing you specific library time
 2. Different opening hours
 3. Better designed environment
 4. Bigger space
 5. More comfortable furniture
 6. Being able to use more technology in the library

13. How could the Trust encourage you to use the library more?
(attitude and opinion, open)

Wellbeing

14. Do you think it would be useful if trust policies on the subject of well-being recommended spending time in the library to encourage personal and professional development? (attitude and opinion, open)

15. Is the way library staff behave towards you important? (attitude and opinion, open)

1. Kind
2. Calm
3. Friendly
4. Knowledgeable
5. Approachable
6. Good communication within the team
7. Being able to talk to a person
8. Being listened to
9. Being able to ask "silly" questions
10. Sense of being cared for
11. Feeling that you and your needs are important

16. Is the way library staff behave towards you different from other staff in the trust? (attitude and opinion, open)

Professional library staff are bound by professional ethics:

- Concern for the public good in all professional matters, including respect for diversity within society, and the promoting of equal opportunities and human rights.
- Commitment to the defence, and the advancement, of access to information, ideas and works of the imagination.
- Equitable treatment of all information users.
- Impartiality, and avoidance of inappropriate bias, in acquiring and evaluating information and in mediating it to other information users.

<http://www.cilip.org.uk/cilip/about/ethics/ethical-principles>

The CILIP code of professional practice also stipulates working practices that embody clarity, trust, openness and equality:

- Make the process of providing information, and the standards and procedures governing that process, as clear and open as possible.
- Avoid inappropriate bias or value judgements in the provision of services-
- Promote equitable access for all members of society to public domain information of all kinds and in all formats

<http://www.cilip.org.uk/cilip/about/ethics/code-professional-practice>

17. Would a poor encounter with library staff dissuade you from visiting the library again? (behaviour, open) If so why?

18. Does your Manager support a learning environment within the workplace where the sharing of knowledge and skills is encouraged? (attitude and opinion, closed)

19. Do you have personal objectives in mind when you use the library? (attitude, open)
20. Have you ever used library's fiction collection or books on prescription collection or other resources for your own personal development, not relating to your work: (behaviour, open)
 1. Self help books
 2. CDs
 3. DVDs
 4. Books not in my subject area

Social relationships

21. Do you find the library a social environment where you can meet colleagues on a different level from other places in the workplace? (attitudes and opinions, open)
22. Do you think using the library helps you achieve trust objectives, by giving you a thinking space? (attitude and opinion, open)
23. Do you have any personal objectives in mind when you use the library? (attitude, open)
24. Do you feel the library is part of the networks within the organisation (attitude and opinion, closed)
25. Do you feel the library staff know people in the Trust (attitude and opinion, closed)
26. Do you feel that the library knows about other organisations that could support you in your development? (attitude and opinion, closed)
 1. Colleges
 2. Other NHS organisations
 3. Universities
 4. Medical schools
 5. Other libraries – British Library, BMA library, public library
 6. Charities
27. Have you ever come across things you hadn't set out to find in the library: (behaviour, closed)
 1. Book
 2. Subject area
 3. Article in a journals
 4. Information from staff
28. Have you ever asked / would you feel comfortable asking library staff about training on "modern technologies" e.g. social media Twitter, Facebook, apps, Kindle (behaviour, closed)
29. Do you trust the library staff? If yes, why? (attitude and opinion, open)
 1. To get accurate information
 2. To treat your request as confidential
 3. To use reliable sources of information

30. Any other comments?

Appendix 9

Croydon Health Services “here for you” promises

At Croydon Health Services we promise that we are always **here for you**.

We promise everyone in Croydon, whether you are in hospital, in the community or at home, that we will do our best to ensure:

- **You feel cared** for by helpful and welcoming staff, who respect you as an individual
- **You feel in safe hands** with highly professional staff who work well together in clean clinics and hospitals
- **You feel confident in your treatment** from skilled teams of compassionate clinicians who listen to you and keep you informed
- **You feel we value your time** with convenient appointments, minimal waiting and care closer to home
- **You feel it's getting better all the time** as we continue to improve our services.

These promises, developed with our patients, carers and staff help us deliver the pledges in the NHS Constitution and our own corporate objectives.

<http://www.croydonhealthservices.nhs.uk/about-us/>

Appendix 10

CHS trust objectives

- care which improves outcomes, patient safety and patient experience.
- To work with partners to improve the health and wellbeing of the people of Croydon.
- To develop our workforce and to establish a way of working that builds a culture that is committed to an open transparent evidence based approach.
- To deliver best practice performance standards against the national operating framework.
- To deliver well managed quality services which are value for money for the tax payer.

<http://www.croydonhealthservices.nhs.uk/about-us/>

Appendix 11
Dissertation Proposal

Managing through Critical
Research

BBM-7-MCR

London South Bank University

Faculty of Business

Croydon Health Services NHS Trust

Lecturers: Dr. Sheena Murdoch and Dr. Jan Rae

Research proposal

**An Investigation into the barriers for
library managers to developing the
physical space in NHS libraries in
London**

Morag Clarkson

Research proposal

An Investigation into the barriers for library managers to developing the physical space in NHS libraries in London.

Morag Clarkson

Introduction and context

The London Health Libraries network was established in 2003 to bring together libraries in the capital serving health staff and students. The network includes NHS managed services, libraries managed by Higher Education (HE) and independent health libraries such as those of the Royal Colleges and voluntary agencies based in London. Over 60 libraries in the NHS and HE sectors receive NHS funding, with 200-250 staff employed in these services. (LHL 2013)

NHS Libraries provide access to print and online resources, study spaces, qualified information professionals and professional information services. The Strategic Health Library Leads (SHaLL) record annual statistics for NHS libraries in England. This includes annual budget, staff costs and grades, operational usage (loans, article requests) and expenditure on print and online resources.

NHS library users are mainly drawn from clinical staff who will typically be members of professional regulatory bodies (Royal College of Nursing, Royal College of Physicians, Chartered Institute of Physiotherapists) Membership of these bodies typically includes access to print and online journals which may or may not be replicated in the national or local NHS library collection. Other NHS staff in the organisation will still require access to profession specific resources. E.g. Healthcare assistants will use nursing resources, physiotherapists will use medical resources. Within the London Health Libraries (LHL) network and wider, libraries interlend with each other to supply resources to other libraries which do not have access to specific books or journals.

Conceptual framework, theory and hypotheses

Human user interaction with the design of physical and online services is often not part of the design process (Buchanan 2012, p.259). Without adequate design, services may work but not be user friendly.

Users' emotional engagement with design is often overlooked in the design process (Ibid). In a constrained financial climate libraries may be have a role in engaging staff with the organisation by increasing learning capability and supporting the creation of a learning organisation. (Bennett, 2003 , preface)

When new library builds in other sectors are examined, design appears an important consideration (Designing Libraries 2013) With Increased use of mobile devices, social media and other technologies to access information and keep updated, it would appear logical that the space in which these tools are accessed needs to be updated. With an over-abundance of online resources and multiple access points to online journals users can choose where they physically spend time accessing the information they require.

The use of the physical library space is not nationally recorded by SHaLL. I suggest that the physical library space provides more than just a repository for resources and services. These qualitative aspects are not recorded. I suggest that NHS libraries contribute to the production of the learning capability of the organisation amongst other unrecorded social and business benefits. The development of the physical library space is not explicitly detailed in budget lines. The cost of staff and resources take up the majority of library budgets. With whom the responsibility for the upgrade of the library premises sits remains unclear.

In the wider library sector (higher education, public libraries) new builds are being invested in (Designing Libraries, 2013)

McKenna (2006, p. 75) recognises that there is a lack of evidence to support the impact of design on the use of libraries. However, Brown (2008 p. 92) suggests that many problems need, what he calls a design thinking approach, which uses creativity and human-centred solutions. I intend to examine the London Health Libraries strategic aim of "promoting physical libraries as attractive study and learning spaces for the whole health and care workforce" (LHL 2013) I suggest that guidance and support should be produced at a sector level to ensure the implementation of this aim. I wish to look at the barriers for library managers and the benefits to the host organisation of achieving this aim. I wish to measure specific qualitative outputs of the library service in NHS trusts.

Purpose of the study

1. To examine the barriers to LHL Managers of developing the physical library space
2. To examine the benefits of library development to the host organisation.
3. To examine the library users' qualitative experience of the physical premises.

At a national and regional level there is no specific guidance about how to develop space in NHS libraries and measure the benefits of such a

development e.g. using the library as a community hub or learning hub and the benefits of this to staff and the organisation.

I wish to examine whether LHL Managers and users perceive investing in the upgrade of the physical library environment as being of equal priority to the purchase of online and physical resources.
I would like to establish how far users of NHS libraries expect a "knowledge experience".

Research aim

To investigate the barriers perceived by LHL Managers to developing the physical library space.

To discuss the drivers for the host organisation to enable this development and the unrecorded qualitative outputs of the physical library service in NHS trusts.

My research objectives are to investigate whether:
LHL Managers perceive spending NHS budgets on design is seen as a waste of resources.

If an NHS estate is in disrepair can funds to upgrade a library service be justified .What proportion of budget should be spent on upgrading premises

I wish to investigate the subjectivist, qualitative experience of using the library service relating to:

- Staff engagement
- Job satisfaction
- Reduction in stress about how to access information
- Likelihood of staff studying for CPD after gaining information skills
- Increased confidence of using technology

Is it possible to ascertain who is responsible for the upgrade of NHS premises?

Should the library as a learning environment should be resourced according to the learning needs of the organisation as part of improving staff and organisational learning capability.

Review of the literature

Why investigate the development of the physical library space when the increased use of mobile devices, social media and other technologies to access information proliferates?

The library as place is not only a functional entity but a complex sociological, psychological and emotional discussion, not easily replaced by an ipad. The perception of the library's value is linked to the library as place Gorman 2000 p.41)

Gorman (2000, p. 44) adds that we need libraries as meeting places for the community because we require human interaction. People need help human help negotiating online "stuff". Gorman (2000 p. 45) Further, online may not be the most efficient or effective way to access information.

Libraries sit within the UK knowledge economy, which Brinkley (2008, p.9) defines as "A story of how new general purpose technologies have combined with intellectual and knowledge assets – the 'intangibles' of research, design, development, creativity, education, science, brand equity and human capital – to transform our economy. The UK is leading the way in this sector."

There is no national measure for the benefit to staff or patients of the NHS library as "place" This with any intangibles related to knowledge, is difficult to quantify.

Brinkley (2008, p.21) suggests an association between innovation, human capital, and knowledge acquisition, and investments in intangibles (IT capital, labour quality)

The Chartered Institute for Library and Information Professionals (CILIP) recognises the opportunities for information professionals in the knowledge economy stating that there is an unrivalled opportunity for the development of information skills. (CILIP 2002)

Is the knowledge economy something everyone can engage with? Is it relevant to the diverse population of staff and students served by NHS libraries?

Brinkley (2008 p.9) identifies that the knowledge economy could reinforce economic and social divides between a new working elite of knowledge workers at the top and those at the bottom.

For many, access to computers is limited. Fryer (2013) reports that 62% of American libraries are the only source of free internet access and computers in some communities.

Goh (2012, p.94) draws parallels between learning capability and organizational and financial performance

The library space offers a supported and resourced working area for all staff, regardless of hierarchies or grade. The egalitarian nature of the

library space offers an equal service to all regardless of clinical specialty or job title. It is a truly open environment.

U.S. Department of Commerce (2000) as cited by Gorman (2000 p. 47) states that "race, location, gender age and income are controlling factors in the question of access to electronic information resources"

The digital divide in the UK is still a current concern. Digital Britain 2 reports that online working is central to the delivery of government services but there are many who cannot or do not want to go online. National Audit Office (2013)

The NHS has a particularly diverse workforce, requiring varied support. Many staff are highly educated and technologically able, whilst many are not. Engaging with staff at all levels is an important task. Goh (2012, p.93) suggests there is a significant positive relationship between learning capability and organizational performance.

Staff engagement can mean employees stay longer in post and are keen to develop personally and professionally. Creative staff management in a constrained financial climate can engage staff, which is a vital component of achieving effective patient care (Thompson 2011)

As social media becomes more important in people's learning strategies, and social networks become more influential (Rainie 2011) so it could be argued that people value the face to face social interaction they do engage with. Similarly, the places where people can physically meet and interact may take on greater significance and value.

Pink (2008), as cited by Brown (2008 pg 92) " Abundance has satisfied, and even over-satisfied the material needs of millions - boosting the significance of beauty and emotion and accelerating individuals' search for meaning" As more of our basic needs are met, we increasingly expect sophisticated experiences that are emotionally satisfying and meaningful. These experiences will not be simple products. They will be complex combinations of products, services, spaces and information."

There are many innovative, ecological and technologically well-equipped new library builds. New libraries are winning design awards; they are exciting community events; they are a symbol of social cohesion by providing a community learning hub open to all. Smith (in Bennet 2003, preface), asks "whether the goal of libraries today might more appropriately be described as supporting collaborative learning by which students turn information into knowledge and sometimes into wisdom. As technological advances

have made it possible to find information without entering a library building, some have asked whether the bricks and mortar library is doomed to extinction. Yet others maintain that the growth of technology has made the library even more important because it enables access to electronic content, services and training that would otherwise be unavailable to information seekers” (Bennett , 2003)

Gorman (2003 p. 43) describes the “seductive notion” of “all the citizens of a digital nation finding all they need in the way of recorded knowledge and information without having to leave their homes. Such an idea depends on all recorded knowledge and information being: Available, and permanently available in digital form Organised and readily retrievable and individuals be able to interact fruitfully with the universe of recorded knowledge and information without the assistance of any other humans. It is almost impossible to overestimate how far we are from those 3 basic requirements.” Significantly more information is now available digitally however it is not all free and neither is it all quality controlled.

Since the publication of the Francis report (Mid Staffordshire NHS Foundation Trust Public Inquiry 2013), there has been a declared "shift" in values and culture in NHS away from targets and towards a caring, nurturing and compassionate service: a human service that treats people as people. Well-equipped libraries allow NHS trusts to explicitly demonstrate that they are supporting and developing staff. Further, they are improving patient care as they are encouraging access to the evidence base for staff and providing an adequate place for people to learn and develop. The Francis report recommendation to set up a NHS Leadership College explicitly states that it should be physical and not virtual and “will serve the role of reinforcing the required culture through shared experience and will provide a common induction into the expectations of the NHS (Mid Staffordshire NHS Foundation Trust Public Inquiry Executive Summary pg 78 1.197)

Positive human interaction with physical and online services will influence the success of services. Often the emotional connection to a product or an image is what engages us in the first place (Brown 2008 p.92)

As print holdings reduce, the library space can be designed around the learning needs of the organisation. Although some of the physical resources may diminish to be replaced with online alternatives, the library environment itself remains an important tangible asset.

As Braun (2012, p.48) describes, in an information commons (or learning commons), books and traditional materials are pushed to the

periphery - or they aren't included in the space at all. Rather, the space is open, with lots of seating, technology and collaborative areas.

However, quiet in libraries remains a key concept in the library as place with 78% of parents surveyed stating it is very important to the community for public libraries to provide quiet study spaces for adults and children. Zickuhr et al (2013 pg 44)

Whilst new builds emphasize the importance of collaborative working and discussion areas, Massis (2012) emphasizes the need for quiet.

Design planning takes time, observation and expertise. "There has been a lack of validated empirical evidence in the literature about the impact of building design on the use of library facilities" (McKenna 2006)

Bennett (2003 p.1) recognizes that in academia issues with library space go unsolved for years, or even decades.

Human interaction when designing the functionality of online services is also neglected

"far beyond technical considerations, there are complex social, economic, organisational, and ergonomic requirements and relationships to consider. Such a perspective cannot be gained without direct user involvement, yet evidence suggests that development teams may be failing to effectively engage with users, relying on requirements derived from anecdotal evidence or prior experience." Buchanan (2012 p.256)

Do library managers have the skills to design their libraries and services to keep up with the knowledge economy?

Bouchard (2012, p.328) describes "meta-design as a skill that cannot be learned at school but one that can only be acquired through multiple years of professional practice.

It is important that library professionals who know their users drive this process

"design methods and tools appear quite accessible to the extent that they become fashionable. The first peril for "management as design", is the reduction of design approaches and methods to a set of tools in the hands of self-appointed experts. "Bouchard (2012, p.331)

The library as a well-designed visible symbol of an organisation's espoused values and learning style could rebrand that organization as one that values knowledge, evidence and contributes to a corporate memory.

Currie (2008) cited in Dodds (2011) suggests that knowledge sharing is likely to be inhibited by issues concerning the 'nature of knowledge, professional cultures, and institutional power and politics'

I suggest that libraries are the hub of learning communities. Access to information and the storing and retrieval of knowledge are political issues.

As Rainie (2011) asks "What is the future of knowledge, reference expertise, public technology, learning spaces and community anchor institutions?"

Research Design

Methodology

The epistemological position of this research is interpretivist. (Bryman, 2011, p. 17) The ontology is constructionism (ibid, p.20) investigating a negotiated order.

The research is overt and is theory generative.

Research methods

The research will be qualitative.

The survey instrument will be semi-structured qualitative questionnaires to library managers and library users, backed up with further semi-structured interviews based around themes drawn from responses.

The research problems addressed by the questionnaires are:

What do LHL Managers perceive as the barriers that prevent them from developing the physical library space. Is this seen as an issue or an area that does not need development. Do Managers perceive that money is best spent on resources. Do Managers perceive that there are benefits to users, the service and the host organisation from the development of the physical library space.

Can library users assess how using the physical library space influences them qualitatively? Do users perceive that the physical space provides them with more than repository for resources. Would a strategically designed physical space improve the potential learning capability of the individuals and contribute to the organisation becoming a learning organisation?

The ontological, interpretivism position intends to collect research data around the subjectivist (Bryman, 2011, p.24) socially constructed topics of:

- Comfort of the library environment
- Size of the library
- The experience of using the library
- The immersive dimension of the library environment to focus learning

The social aspects of using the library
The friendliness of library staff,
Quietness
Talking face to face with library staff as part of human interaction
Having face to face guidance and training as part of human interaction
Being able to ask "silly" and repeated questions without being judged
Sense of being cared for by library staff who know the staff member and their information needs
Calm manner of the library staff,
Kind manner of the library staff.
Knowledge and expertise of the library staff,
Option to ask about / receive training on Twitter, Facebook, apps, Kindle

Subjectivist research data from LHL Managers is intended to be collated around the topics:

It is the responsibility of the Trust, Library Manager or IT Department to upgrade library premises and/or technology options in the library
Using a percentage of their budget for annual upgrades to the library environment to facilitate organisational learning, technological upgrades and/or to make the space more effective to study in.
Should the library, as a tool to enable learning capability, be resourced according to the learning needs of the organisation

Sampling and Selection Strategies

Sampling will be purposive. (Punch, 2012, p.187)

The target population for the LHL Managers questionnaire approx 50 LHL services managers

A representative sample of at least 10 LHL Managers could be taken if response rates are low from the target population.

The Londonlinks email list will be used as the sampling frame.

For the Croydon Health Services library users questionnaire, availability samples will be taken by people using the library. The questionnaire will be handed to users of the library during the survey period. Users accessing the

library online (by email and website) and by telephone will also be invited to take part in the research. They will be informed that a survey is taking place and will be invited to participate by telephone, by completing the questionnaire online or by being sent a hard copy. If they do not use the physical library service they can still give valuable data about why they don't use the physical library e.g. Working hours, lack of time to come to the physical space.

In addition, a stratified randomised sample (stratified by job role - doctor, nurse etc) using a sampling fraction of 1/5 will be used to also access further participants. The sampling frame will be the library management system. This will target a population of registered users who may not physically or virtually use the library during the survey period.

Limitations

To an extent the participants will be picked as they will be the people using the library during the research period. This could be a shortcoming of the research. There is a potential that users will not respond to the questionnaires as they do not have strong feelings about the research question.

It would be useful to also have a sample of non-users to measure why they did not use the library and compare this qualitative data and their attitudes about the organisation as a learning organisation. This sample could be found in the population using the staff cafe in the same building as the library.

Transcription of interviews may be very time consuming if the total population respond and specify that they will participate in interviews. Common themes will be drawn from frequently occurring words.

It is important for the researcher to be aware of the political, ideological discourse within the qualitative research. (Punch, 2012, p.135) and to remain objective during the interviewing process.

Access and Ethics

All efforts will be taken to ensure that the researcher is unbiased in the treatment of research participants.

The researcher will ensure that no harm or risk comes to participants during the research process. This will include: anxiety, stress, loss of self esteem, physical harm, detrimental effects on development and persuading participants to take part in reprehensible activities

The researcher will ensure that participants cannot be identified either personally or by reference.

Personal information relating to participants will be kept confidential.

Highly sensitive information will not be recorded if requested.

The Londonlinks email list will be used to contact LHL Manager participants. The researcher is a member of this list and has permission from the list owner to use it for research purposes. The owner (Strategic Library Lead for London) supports the research being undertaken and hopes it will inform a planned overview of NHS library space..

All information about and from participants will be confidential. All participants will remain anonymous.

Informed consent will be gained from all participants. Participants will be fully informed about the research and its implications. It will be made clear to participants that they are under no obligation to take part in the research, they can withdraw information from the research at any stage and they can withdraw themselves from the research at any stage.

Access to the LHL Manager participants will be via the SHaLL strategic library lead.

The sampling frame for Croydon Health Services library users will be the library management system which the researcher has access to. Walk-in users of Croydon Health Services library will be given a questionnaire. The researcher has daily access to the library. The library has a regular footfall of users of approximately 30 people per day. In order to gain a representative sample of library users, telephone and online users can be approached to participate in the questionnaire once informed consent has been given by them

Data collection methods

Grounded theory will be used in data collection (Punch, 2012 p.155)

Survey monkey will be used to host and collate the online questionnaire responses.

The users of the library at Croydon Health Services will be surveyed via a questionnaire that will be distributed in paper form and emailed to a

stratified randomised sample of Croydon Health Services library users. Themes may be drawn from the questionnaires that can be further developed through semi-structured interviews. Interviews with some participants will be carried out either individually or in small groups (maximum of 4 participants) in a convenient location to the participants. The interview venue will be secure and private. The interview process will not be interrupted. Confidentiality will be assured throughout the interviews. The researcher has the agreement of a colleague to assist with the interviewing process. Data will be recorded in the form of notes and will additionally be recorded electronically. Interviews will be transcribed.

Data will be stored securely and will be password protected.

Data will be anonymised.

The researcher will record the context of the participants - where they are from (organisations or departments) and what prompted them to take part in the research

Piloting and preliminary work

Two pilot questionnaires will be trialled. One pilot questionnaire will be sent to three LHL Managers for completion and comment. One pilot questionnaire will be sent to three Croydon Health Services library users for comment and completion.

Pilot participants will be selected from library super-users and LHL Managers who are willing to pilot the questionnaire. Notes will be taken and when possible an electronic record will also be taken, with permission of the participants.

A pilot of semi-structured interview will be conducted with both pilot groups (LHL Managers and Croydon Health Service Library users)

Data analysis

Grounded theory will be used for data analysis (Punch, 2012 p.212) Themes will be drawn from the data as a basis for further interviews. The data will be displayed in table form with comments listed.

Validity

The validity of the data and whether it is plausible and realistic will be discussed. This will be related to the venue where interviews are taking place and how easy the questionnaires are to complete and understand.

Contradictions in the data will be explained.

Timescale

No submission dates have been made available from the university at time of writing. The following dates are a guide.

	Jul 201 3	Aug 201 3	Sept 201 3	Oct 201 3	Nov 201 3	Dec 201 3	Jan 201 4	Feb 201 4	Mar 201 4	Apr 201 4	May 201 4	June 201 4	July 201 4	Aug 201 4	Sept 201 4
Selecting relevant sites and subjects															
Pilot questionnaires sent out															
Collection of relevant data															
Survey data will be analysed															
Interviews															
Analysis of findings															
First draft submitted															
Revisions to draft															

Interviews (semi structured) will be carried out with participants if recurring themes emerge from respondents.

January 2014

Interpretation of data

The questionnaire findings and interview transcripts will be analysed

April 2014

Conceptual and theoretical work and tighter specification of the research question

Research write up begins

May 2014

Writing up findings and conclusions

First draft of research submitted

July 2014

Revisions made to draft

September 2014

Research submitted

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Appendix 12

Related research

Pratchet, T. (2014) *Tell us your stories*. Personal email to LIS-MEDICAL UK medical/ health care library community / information workers, 10th November.

Some initiatives in NHS libraries, in particular around knowledge management, demonstrate the role that libraries play in developing social networks and social capital, although they are not branded as such. A recent email sent on LIS-Medical, a mailing list for medical librarians highlights an attempt to solidify an intangible benefit of the library service around networks: Further research to critically investigate this concept would be useful.

From: UK medical/ health care library community / information workers [mailto:LIS-MEDICAL@JISCMAIL.AC.UK] **On Behalf Of**

Sent: 10 November 2014 14:23

To: LIS-MEDICAL@JISCMAIL.AC.UK

Subject: Tell us your stories

One thing I like about working in NHS libraries is that they are generally friendly and we get to know our customers quite well. Have you ever had someone mention a problem they have and you have been able to put them in contact with someone else to solve it?

Generally making connections is something that we are good at, but take for granted. Libraries have a unique position in the NHS – we speak to everyone irrelevant of hierarchy and division. We have lots of contacts outside of our organisations.

What would happen if we started to collect stories of the links we have made?

- Similar problems are likely to exist in other Trusts
- It could help us use the tacit information of other people to make connections within our own organisations
- It cheers us up (generally we all like to feel useful)
- These little stories can be used as knowledge management case studies to help demonstrate impact

We are starting to collect stories and we would love that you share some of yours too! We have made a start to give you some ideas:

<http://maptoolkit.wordpress.com/category/km-stories/>

Find out more about what you can do with the power of storytelling or sign up to alerts at: <http://maptoolkit.wordpress.com/useful-resources/km-stories/>

Stories are also tweeted via **@maptoolkit @traceypratchett @LIHNNQuality**

We are not looking for great epistles, just simple little stories to share. So if you have a story to share or would like more information please email myself or (name removed) The details we need are:

- **Your name:**
- **Organisation:**
- **Contact details:**
- **Description – what did you do? What was your role?**

We have the optional extras of:

- **Outcome – what happened as a result of your involvement?**
- **Next steps – do you have any future plans to take this further?**

Appendix 13

Reflective Diary

Dissertation Reflective Diary

This a reflective journal on the process of thinking about research and research writing

Date	Activity	Consequence
July	Starting to clarify my thoughts around the topic. Found lots of recent research that backs up my research proposition and rationale for research – e.g. HEE document.	Finding lots of linked research about happiness which I am very interested in. The topics I have chosen really interest me – wellbeing and social capital. I truly feel it is important to encourage well-being in the workplace and not just think of it as healthy eating or exercise. Developing the mind also helps with well-being as does having a safe place in which to do this.
Aug	Lots of talk in the media today which run parallel with my dissertation topic e.g. the closure of small bank branches. Replace this with small library branches in my case. Interesting to be able to apply the concepts to many other fields – it's about community and social capital. It's very interesting.	
Sept	Met with Sheena	
28 October	Sent revised literature review for marking and comment	Incorporated comments. This helped me to further formulate

2014		my research question which is still unclear
12 Nov – 17 Nov	Wrote bulk of Research chapter	Writing my biography was very enjoyable and interesting. I wasn't expecting this to be the case. I was able to set the scene about why I had chosen this area for my research and write in "natural language" rather than feeling I needed to reference everything.
24 th November	Finally formulated my research question. It has taken a long time to be able to unpick what I actually want to ask.	Feel more confident about moving onto the actual research
1 Dec	Review of our services at CHS has highlighted the exact issue that I using as my research question. It is incredibly ironic and interesting.	Research is now very relevant and may impact on any future reviews of the service
3 Dec	Nearly ready to send of chapters 1, 2 and 3. Still finding it difficult to put words and thoughts into the framework correctly. I know I need to move text around but as yet it isn't always clear exactly where it should go.	Still struggling with the formal flow and layout of the actual dissertation. As I become clearer on what I am actually researching it makes a little more sense.
10 Dec	The review of education, including library services and the subject of my dissertation, have intersected. There is a block on the refurbishment of the library despite evidence to show the value of the refurbishment and the support it gives to the health and wellbeing of staff. I have identified that the Health and Wellbeing agenda at board level has been "shelved"	Feel wary of saying too many negative comments in my dissertation

	<p>despite a new framework being written. The Health and Wellbeing Board has been disbanded and there appears to be little support for health and wellbeing in the trust. The health and Safety Manager has told me that the Health and Wellbeing Policy does not feed into any trust Board committee. No-one on the board can say where the health and wellbeing committee report into.</p>	
17 Dec	<p>Have to stop reading now. I am adding more and more information to my dissertation, which I am very interested in. But I am wary that I am going off the point and I need to be very specific</p>	<p>Ready to look at interviews questions now, as reading is taking over my life and I need to stop!</p>
22 Dec	<p>Telephone meeting with my dissertation supervisor, Sheena. She points out that I have been using the wrong dissertation handbook. This makes sense as I have put the chapter headings in the wrong order. I am now re-jigging everything and feel slightly more confident.</p>	<p>On the right track with layout now</p>
23 Dec	<p>In conversation with other MPA students about our dissertations, I realise that there really are gaps in wellbeing and equality policies and policy implementation. It is very interesting how it suddenly starts to come together somehow and the circle is squared.</p>	<p>Feeling vaguely confident that I am on the right lines.</p>
12 Feb	<p>Still feeling very muddled with direction of work. Have lots of</p>	

	content and will need to drastically cut	
10 April	Emailed final ethics forms to Sheena for approval	Feel the shape of the thing is coming together now. Still a lot to do but it "feels" about the right size
25 April	Finishing off details	Drastic editing has helped me to focus the topic. Just need to keep re-reading to make sure it flows.

Appendix 14

LQAF monitoring questions

<http://www.libraryservices.nhs.uk/forlibrarystaff/lqaf/>

1.3c

The positive impact of library/knowledge services can be demonstrated.

Fuller explanation of requirement

There is a process for the regular evaluation of library/knowledge services to demonstrate positive impact on the organisation[s] served, and for example on patient care outcomes, service improvement, learning and development, cost-savings, reduction of risk, and other organisational objectives as appropriate.

N.B. This criterion is **not about** complimentary feedback from customers. Examples can be included as evidence only if they clearly show a difference or change in an individual or group resulting from the contact with library/knowledge services.

Definitions

Impact: demonstrable evidence that the library/knowledge service is enabling the organisation[s] served to meet their strategic objectives in improving patient care.

This could be evidence demonstrating a change in treatment, cost savings made, changes made to delivery of services because of using library/knowledge services.

<http://www.systems-thinking.org/mcsc/mcsc.htm>

Suggested admissible evidence

- Results of qualitative and quantitative surveys.
- Quotes that demonstrate where use of library/knowledge services has led to changes in practice or specific care episodes.
- Case studies, papers or notes from meetings where this evidence has been presented.
- Annual reports that include evidence.

Guidance on full compliance

Evidence that a **variety of methods** are used to **systematically** gather information about the impact of library/knowledge services on organisational objectives/patient care, and that the information that has been gathered has been used to demonstrate the impact of services.

Guidance on partial compliance

Evidence that some limited progress has been made towards demonstrating the impact of library/knowledge services, and some information about impact is available.

OR

Evidence that the evaluation process is unplanned.

Guidance on non-compliance

No techniques are currently used to gather information about the impact of services, and no information about impact is available.

Additional tips, tools, templates or references

Library Impact Toolkit

<http://www.libraryservices.nhs.uk/forlibrarystaff/impactassessment/>

and subsequent pages of the impact toolkit, case studies

FOLIO Managing Service Quality

<http://foliomsq.pbworks.com/w/page/27403076/FrontPage>

FOLIO – Maxim (Maximising the impact of your service)

<http://foliomaxim.pbworks.com/w/page/6853635/FrontPage>

Lib Value Project

<http://libvalue.cci.utk.edu/>

MAP: Making Alignment a Priority for health libraries (NW)

<http://maptoolkit.wordpress.com/>

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<http://online.library.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/j.1471-1842.2008.00782.x/pdf>

Search for 1.3c in "text" at:

<http://ksslks.co.uk/data/web/innovations.htm>

For updates to URLs and additional references see

<http://www.libraryservices.nhs.uk/wiki/LQAF.MainPage.ashx>

4.3a

The physical space occupied by the library/knowledge service meets current service needs.

Fuller explanation of requirement

This relates to the appropriateness of the physical space e.g. for housing stock, different types of study space to accommodate different learning styles and workstations etc.

Accommodation should not be cramped and there should be some spare capacity at peak times.

Use of this physical space should also be actively reviewed to meet changing, and where possible projected, needs.

Suggested admissible evidence

- Photographs.
- Floor plans.
- Feedback from customers.
- Measurement of current usage through occupancy surveys.
- Evidence the library space meets the requirements of HSE office space standards
<http://www.hse.gov.uk/office/index.htm>
- User surveys on the library space or extracts from a general usersurvey that relate to the library space.
- Documents demonstrating that a review of the library space has been undertaken.

Guidance on full compliance

No issues with physical space for **95%** of the opening times.

Guidance on partial compliance

There is a recurrent identified issue.

Guidance on non-compliance

There is insufficient (or inappropriate) space to meet customer needs for the majority of the opening times and no plans to address this.

Additional tips, tools, templates or references

Designing Libraries

<http://www.designinglibraries.org.uk/index.asp?PageID=1>

A resource for library planning and design, a database of library buildings and a marketplace for services.

JISC InfoNet Learning space design

<http://www.jiscinfonet.ac.uk/infokits/learning-space-design>

For updates to URLs and additional references see

<http://www.libraryservices.nhs.uk/wiki/LQAF.MainPage.ashx>

Appendix 15

Croydon Health Services Workforce and Study Leave Policy

WORKFORCE DEVELOPMENT AND STUDY LEAVE POLICY

Version: 1

Ratified by: Policy Committee

Date ratified: 22nd March 2013

Approving Committee/Group (Date) POD, JSCC, HR Policy Panel

Date Approved by Medicines Management

Committee:

(NB: All Procedural Documents which include details of drugs or their management must be approved by the Medicines Management Committee)

N/A

Name and Title of originator/author: Courine Stewart

Workforce Development & OD Manager

Date issued: April 2013

Review due date: March 2016

Target audience: All Trust Staff

Superseded documents Staff Learning & development policy (nonmedical staff) - version 4

Relevant Standards(e.g. NHSLA, CQC, HSE)

N/A

Acknowledgements None

Key Words Study Leave, Learning, Training, Development, Support,

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1 INTRODUCTION

Croydon Health Services (CHS) is committed to promoting equitable workforce development opportunities to its staff, in order to support achieving its Corporate Objectives. Effective education and development activities should meet the individual, corporate and service requirements. All development activity and staff contribution should focus on ensuring The Trust"s key business needs are met. Workforce and Organisational development activities are crucial to supporting the delivery of high quality patient centred care, support clinical governance and the continued modernising and integration of our NHS services. It will also prepare our staff for new ways of working that enhance our patient experience and service improvement programmes. We also believe that professional and personal development opportunities enhance staff"s motivation and engagement as well as increasing skills and knowledge. It will enhance our ability to attract high calibre staff and promotion of being an employer of choice.

CHS is establishing a learning culture based on patient and organisational need with a strong focus on staff personal development review, as well as continuous personal and professional development.

The Trust annually reviews its workforce development and education activities in line with corporate and business requirements, with an endeavour to ensure equitable access to all staff. Staff have equal access to workforce development opportunities based on an assessment of their needs and an agreed personal development plan that reflects the requirements of their current post; their professional development needs and any career development aspirations they may have.

As an integrated organisation, it is necessary for this policy to draw upon best practice currently in place that will meet all aspects of our services. This Policy will inform all staff across the

Trust and ensure that specialist areas of development across all Trust disciplines are met. The

Trust will support staff to update skills in their current area of practice and/or extend their skills

in order to adapt, or move into new roles within the organisation as our services continue to integrate further.

2 PURPOSE

This policy provides information for staff regarding access to workforce development and education opportunities at CHS. It also provides a guidance framework for line managers who review and approve requests for such activities. This document sets out the Trust's approach to workforce development and provides guidance on the responsibilities for the reviewing, approval and access of these opportunities.

2.1 Scope

This policy applies to all employees working for the Trust in understanding the commitment

CHS has towards all types of training and developmental activity; from in-house workshops,

bespoke training, corporate initiatives, conferences and accredited programmes including

university courses leading to various Degrees and Master Accreditation.

2.2 Identifying and Prioritising Development Needs

The Staff Performance and Development Review Policy & Procedure is the Trust's main

mechanism through which the learning and development needs of employees will be identified and for agreeing how they will be met on a planned basis. It is through this mechanism that decisions about the priority of different learning and development needs will be agreed. Every staff member will have set personal objectives that relate specifically to their role and links to the corporate and or service requirements. It is a requirement that staff must be up to date with prescribed mandatory and statutory training before approval can be given for non-mandatory training support. Fixed Term and Temporary Workers will have access to essential mandatory and some corporate training; advice will be given on enquiry.

2.3 Equity of Access

The Trust will ensure that all staff have fair access to workforce development and education opportunities on a non-discriminatory basis. All staff should be able to fulfil their developmental needs regardless of their ethnicity, level of seniority, work patterns and the location in which they work. Development opportunities should be available on a flexible basis wherever possible. Workforce Development will undertake routine reporting on the uptake of training by ethnicity, gender and disability. The Trust aims to ensure openness regarding funding arrangements and equity in access to developmental opportunities and study leave where possible.

2.4 Disputes or Grievances

The Trust Grievance Policy applies to access to training and study leave. It should be acknowledged that not all developmental and education opportunities can be met and they are dependent of the annualised funding that the Trust receives. Reduced funding or a lack of resources is sufficient reason to refuse applications for funding or access to study leave.

2.5 Study Leave Application Form

The Trust's Study Leave Application Form can be found on our internal Intranet. To access any workforce development or educational activities, staff must discuss with their manager and seek approval, prior to submitting applications to Workforce Development. A Trust Training

Application must be completed with any accompanying details required to process the individual's request. The Manager's signature indicates approval of the development opportunity. Once approval has been made, individuals should receive the form returned with "Approved" stamped on the sheet. Individuals should enquire on progress of application if they do not receive their form back within 1 week of the development date requested.

3 DEFINITIONS

Following the guidelines below these definitions should be considered when establishing the priority of the training or development need along with agreeing the support that will be available to achieve it.

Mandatory Training: Defined as necessary and compulsory training which the Trust Board NHS Litigation Authority and or Professional Bodies have identified.

Statutory Training: Defined as training where the Trust has a legal responsibility as an employer to ensure that all staff are appropriately trained and updated on a regular basis. The training requirements are reviewed annually in line with The Litigation Authority Assessments and any recommendations passed by recognised inspections authorities. Both Mandatory and Statutory training requirements for all staff (including fixed term and temporary workers) are outlined in our Mandatory and Statutory Policy. It is necessary for all staff to adhere to these requirements and ensure they reference the most up-to-date policy held on the staff intranet.

Essential

Training will be deemed essential when it is one of the following:
Needed to carry out the role set out in the JD/Personal Specification should there be a need for update or revision of duties.
To achieve Service Priorities
To achieve Trust Priorities
Highlighted within the Personal Development Plan
Related to competence levels

Desirable

This is development activity that will allow the employee to develop beyond their current role within the organisation. This type of training is not considered to be fundamental to the staff

member's competence to do their current role but it may add value to the service or organisation as part of succession planning or career aspirations. If no added value to the service can be seen this type of training or development will not be supported.

4 ACCOUNTABILITIES AND RESPONSIBILITIES

THE CHIEF EXECUTIVE AND BOARD

The Chief Executive and Board are ultimately responsible for ensuring that policy and provision are in place to support national and local workforce development priorities in line with our patient values, strategic direction and local service needs. Provision should address both permanent staff along with fixed term (where necessary) and temporary workers. Fixed Term and Temporary Workers will have access to essential mandatory training and anything corporately deemed applicable to their role while working within Croydon Health Services. The Chief Executive has strategic responsibility and will discharge operational implementation to the Director of Human Resources and Organisational Development. The Chief Executive will approve arrangements to ensure all staff receive relevant training to enable them to work safely and effectively as soon as possible on joining the Trust.

THE DIRECTOR OF HUMAN RESOURCES AND ORGANISATIONAL DEVELOPMENT (HR & OD)

The Director of HR & OD is responsible for ensuring the delivery and monitoring of all workforce development and OD activities and that systems are in place to monitor compliance of all mandatory and statutory training as well as workforce development activities across a multidisciplinary workforce. As a developing organisation, the Director of HR & OD will ensure that development requirements directly affecting the competence and capability of staff through external audits or reports will be addressed in order to support professional services for both clinical and non-clinical staff. A clear process to access learning interventions will be detailed in this document and form the basis of guidance for all staff wishing to enhance their skills and future career within CHS or the wider NHS community. The Director of HR & OD will oversee

any update required to this policy in line with changing practice and legislation.

THE MEDICAL DIRECTOR AND POSTGRADUATE MEDICAL CENTRE (PGMC)

The Medical Director will oversee medical education as stipulated by the Learning and Development Agreement (LDA), Deanery and NHS London requirements to ensure that appropriate policy, processes and systems are in place to support the training of medical students, junior doctors, consultants and other medical personnel within the Trust. Further guidance can be found in the Study Leave Guidance/Process for Doctors & Dentists Policy. PGMC will promote any training that will support learning and development activity and report regularly to People and Organisation Development Committee, and The Professional Education Group (PEG). Responsibility for approving and processing the allocation of study leave in line with Medical & Dental Education Levy (MADEL) as part of the LDA will sit with PGMC, along with the promotion, training, support and development activities. Members from the medical education team will reside on PEG and POD to ensure alignment with the corporate objectives and overall Trust workforce and Organisational Development Plan.

THE TRUST MANAGEMENT GROUP/ PEOPLE AND ORGANISATIONAL DEVELOPMENT GROUP

The Trust Management Group (TMG) chaired by the Chief Executive will receive a quarterly report detailing compliance against mandatory & statutory training as well as corporate, local induction and other corporate or identified OD activities. Devolved responsibility for directorate follow-up will be disseminated to Directors and senior staff to ensure that appropriate action is taken back to area management teams where reinforcement and necessary action is taken to ensure compliance is met. The People and Organisational Development Committee (POD) will oversee any learning and development activities in line with corporate priorities and will review education spend and the Scholarship Process.

THE DEPUTY DIRECTOR OF WORKFORCE DEVELOPMENT & ORGANISATIONAL DEVELOPMENT

The Deputy Director of Workforce Development and OD is responsible for the overall management of workforce development and education activities and will ensure that systems are in place for the booking, monitoring and reporting of attendance for all multi-professionals with the exception of Medical Staff. Medical development and education activities are captured through the Medical Director and his team within PGMC. Adjustments to policy for the identified groups as well as procedures and protocols will be coordinated in line with external agency requirements whilst equally ensuring that discussions with key individuals capture both staff and organisational needs.

THE WORKFORCE DEPARTMENT

The Workforce Development Team will ensure that staff have access to workforce development and education interventions as deemed necessary to meet corporate, local and their individual development. The department will manage its designated training rooms and equipment
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across the Trust and will also provide advice and support and promotion of corporate training events. Advice on career and academic progression and Continuous Personal Development (CPD) opportunities is available to assist staff in making decisions; expertise on these topics is also available within Higher Education Institutions and through professional bodies. The promotion of corporate, service and individual development activities are available to meet the demands of the Trust and wider national NHS. Expert staff are available to provide advice on published learning interventions and support managers to implement policy and guidelines as determined by The Director of Human Resources and Organisational Development. To demonstrate compliance in key areas of training along with monitoring all workforce development activity, the Workforce Development Team will record the uptake of all training processed through the department and record activities against individual names using the Trusts official Oracle Learning Management (OLM) system which is linked to our Electronic Staff Records (ESR).

Funding streams and budgets will be monitored through workforce development in line with NHS London's Learning and Development Agreement where regular reports will be submitted based on internal activities and financial spends. All directorates will have equitable access to funds including vocational, sponsorships and access to professional programmes. Workforce Development will process all applications in line with the policy to ensure consistency in supporting staff across a multi-professional workforce.

ADVERTISING TRAINING OPPORTUNITIES

Workforce Development will produce an annual Training, Education and Development Prospectus which will be readily available to all departments on the Trust Intranet. This is a live document constantly being updated with new and exciting opportunities. Here staff can peruse details of required programmes along with dates as well as download at their convenience.

MANAGER'S RESPONSIBILITY

Line managers are responsible for ensuring that the training and workforce development needs of their employees are identified in order to provide safe and quality driven services. This includes ensuring that all individual mandatory and statutory training requirements are met prior to any other development intervention being sanctioned. It must be noted that higher educational interventions will be sanctioned after a staff member has completed at least a year to eighteen months employment at the Trust, following satisfactory service delivery. This will satisfy both Trust and manager that the staff member is committed, reliable and productive in order to return investment to their service area and The Trust.

Under no circumstances should a **recruiting manager** make promises to a member staff during a recruitment process without further discussion and agreement with Workforce Development. This process will be in line with current internal processes to ensure fair equity and access is evident to all across the Trust. It is common place that an individual complete at least 1 year (or 18 months, if necessary, due to extended observation around performance) of

substantive employment prior to any decisions being made to support their external development aspirations. A decision to defer development will also be considered should the individual be undergoing performance or disciplinary measures.

The Manager Must

Ensure all new employees attend corporate induction and receive a local induction into their workplace
Ensure that each employee has an annual personal development review in line with agreed objectives and an agreed personal development plan
Support a learning environment within the workplace where the sharing of knowledge and skills is encouraged
Consider the implications training and workforce development will have on the workload of the department and individual team members when granting study leave
Value the contribution staff make to the work place on return from training and education opportunities and evaluate to assess the return on investment
Ensure that all staff complete the requisite Mandatory And Statutory Training (MAST) and any other refresher training that is required
Ensure that all workforce development is provided to staff in a fair and unbiased manner
Work with the Workforce Development Department to identify training and development needs and assist in the commissioning process so similar needs can be addressed
Honour study leave arrangements/agreements including allowing staff to leave work on time to travel to the desired opportunity. If necessary a mutual local agreement must be entered into in order to avoid any potential disruption or contradiction of agreement by either parties.
Ensure that the employee is aware of their expectations, responsibilities, conduct and behaviours as laid out in relevant Trust policies.

The Employee Must

Identify if study leave will potentially impact their role and responsibilities and negotiate a solution with their line manager prior to the commencement of the course
Attend all sessions for which paid study leave has been granted and ensure that they always sign the attendance register
Ensure that their Personal Development Plan (PDP) is kept up to date and any requirements for professional registration are met

Inform their line manager, the training provider and workforce development if they are unable to attend any session or wish to withdraw
Submit or undertake any assessment when required as part of the programme
Consolidate and put in practice skills and knowledge gained from training which may benefit the service or fellow colleagues
Provide adequate notice to the training provider should they need to cancel their session
and inform their line manager and workforce development should there be any cost implications as result.

5 ACTIONS/PROCEDURES TO FOLLOW

5.1 Study Leave Guidance and Protected Time

The Trust will roll out a series of developmental, education and learning activities that will feed into the Trust's core values, objectives and business transition, impacting on all services across the Trust. This will mean that the Trust has committed resources in ensuring that these interventions are available for staff across the Trust, whereby attendance will address, mandatory, internal skills enhancement and capability development, succession and talent management activities and or Trust cultural and change behaviours. It is therefore necessary for managers to address the area of Protected Time during discussion and this must not be exclusive to mandatory or essential activities.
In order to adopt a culture of support, empowerment and development within the Trust, managers must sign up to ensuring that staff receive protected time for programmes in order to support the core value of supporting staff to develop and utilise these skills for their service and department.
Managers should also consider supporting employees through flexible working in order to support the employee to attend the desired developmental opportunity. Please refer to the Work Life Balance Policy for additional guidance.
Managers should also ensure there is equitable access awarded to developmental opportunities in order to discount any favourable or disproportionate access to anyone individual in relation to Study Leave Allocation.
Study leave allocation will be determined on the actual activity, duration of programme,

consideration of service specific activity along with referencing the guidance under "Training Definitions" as highlighted earlier on in this policy. Discussions on learning opportunity, workload, Shifts and work patterns along with team composition should be considered when sanctioning study leave for staff. Managers must take an equitable and consistent option of managing support to all staff requesting leave. It may be necessary for there to be a "fair" staggered approach to the team members in relation to support and service continuity. .

5.1.1 Bank Staff and Temporary Workers

Bank staff will be given paid study leave for courses which are deemed to be a mandatory and statutory requirement for their role. Bank staff will also be able to access CPD courses provided internally by the Trust. However as part of their CPD updates, they will need to attend these courses in their own time and will not be given paid study leave. The Trust will not provide funding or study leave for any external training.

5.2 Training Budgets and Support

5.2.1 Centralised Training Budget

This is a key resource to providing staff development and continued quality of patient centred care. This is demonstrated through the allocation of an annual centralised training budget to support in-house bespoke corporate, directorate and service developmental activities. All these programmes are fully funded. Business and service relevance is always ratified prior to agreement. Based on organisational priorities, there will be corporate programmes where all staff are required to attend. Place allocation is made by completion of a trust training application form and authorisation from the individual's line manager.

5.2.2 Direct Funding

The Trust currently receives CPD monies in order to support all staff across bands 1 – 9 with development opportunities pertinent to their service priorities and individual role. Directorates are allocated funds for their services in order to support devolved local decision making relevant to individual developmental needs and service specific development opportunities. Directorates are able to plan specific activities that will enhance service delivery and promote knowledge and skills of their team members. Vocational development is also a key driver to sustaining and

supporting the workforce of the future. Band 1 – 4 staff have the opportunity to discuss career

pathway options and receive additional support towards bite sized learning interventions, career enhancing modules as well as professional sponsorship.

5.2.3 Higher Education Institutions (HEI"s/Universities)

Through the annual appraisal process, Personal Development Plans and Learning Needs

Analysis, the Trust is able to offer places to employees at approved designated Universities, as

part of funding contract administered through NHS London. Staff must try wherever possible to

use these Universities as places can be supported through our commissioning process. The

approved Universities are not negotiable.

MSc and BSc modules or programmes that form part of this contract will not incur a cost to the

service. Any employee who accesses this type of funding will be required to submit and pass

the required assessment stipulated by the HEI.

Where Faculty courses have been commissioned for individuals, staff and managers must

ensure that the relevant faculty application form is completed, internal Training Application

Form, including manager"s signature where required. Any queries regarding which application

to complete should be directed to the Workforce Development Team who provide direction

where necessary.

5.2.4 Scholarship Support

The Trust accepts there maybe developmental opportunities that staff wish to access that may

not be covered by the aforementioned funding streams. We also accept that individuals may not

register their university programmes in advance of the commissioning process, and therefore

may fail to secure places for the coming academic year. Subject to resources the Trust will

allocate a budget for any higher education or professional accredited programmes. To ensure

equitability of access to learning and educational opportunities the Trust has implemented a

Scholarship Scheme where staff are able to submit a request for financial and study leave

support for programmes, modules, courses, degrees and masters. A panel from the

Professional Education Group (PEG) will preside over each application and if successful, will

proportion an amount of funding that will support the individual to access their desired activity.

(Please see scholarship guidelines).

5.2.5 Internal Higher Education Sponsorships/Secondments

Staff who are band 1-4 are able to access sponsorships or secondments opportunities to pre or post-registration programmes such as the Access to Nursing, Foundation Degrees in Nursing, Professionally accredited AHP programmes to name a few, as well as other recognised programmes which form part of our national contract. Places may be limited and subject to funding availability, such programmes do not incur any costs to the service and salary costs are also repaid for a non-negotiable amount.

5.2.6 Professional Fees

Memberships with professional bodies or institutes will not be paid by the Trust and are the responsibility of individuals. There may be an arrangement where the Trust undertakes a programme where corporate membership will enable employee access. When this is evident, staff will be advised that any further advancement of membership fees outside of programme will have to be taken up by the individual should they choose to continue membership with that professional body.

5.2.7 Study Materials

It is the individual's responsibility to purchase books and study materials where these are indicated as necessary. If it can be demonstrated that such materials could be used to support similar programmes in the future, due consideration will be taken to provide subject matter material resources to the library in order to afford access to topical study materials. The Trust will ensure that all staff have access to library resources and information services; the Trust also supports the use of internet access for development purposes in designated areas.

5.3 Booking Procedures for Conferences or External Courses

Where individuals request a conference place, it is the responsibility of the employee to book places directly with the provider along with any arrangements for accommodation if required.

This should be as soon as confirmation that financial support has been given from Workforce

Development. **Financial support to accommodation and travel should be sort locally from**

the employee's service or Directorate; *(please see Exams, Travel & Accommodation*

Contribution" of this policy) Workforce Development will only process the approval and

payment of any development activity. Equally should the employee wish to cancel the place, they must inform their line manager, Workforce Development and the provider with supportive information or reasons. There should be an attempt by the employee to support any recovery of fees paid to the provider in the event that payment has been made.

5.4 Failure to complete or withdrawing from the course

Where a staff member fails to complete and pass a course or withdraws following course commencement, the staff member may be restricted from accessing further CPD training and may be asked to make a repayment of the financial assistance provided by the Trust unless there are exceptional circumstances. At the very least it is expected that the individual will selffund any further attempts to gain accreditation on the said programme if so desired in the future.

Employees must submit or undertake any assessment as a requirement of their programme that has been funded or study leave granted by the Trust. Failure to complete assignments or sit exams after the normal period of instruction will count as failure to complete a course.

Employees are required to provide their line manager with a copy of their receipt from the education or training provider. If an employee requires an extension for their assessment they will need to apply to the university or training provider. If this is granted the employee must inform their line manager.

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5.5 Financial Contribution Range, Scholarship Contribution & Learning Agreements

Equitable access and support to workforce development and educational opportunities is essential, for this reason we have provided a sliding scale of financial support which should be referenced locally and will be implemented centrally to demonstrate the Trust's commitment to fairness. It is as follows:

100% Funding - where it is mandatory, statutory or essential to the service
75% Funding – where there is a major benefit to the Trust or service
50% Funding – where there is an equal benefit to the Trust, service and employee

25% Funding – where the main benefit is to the employee with some advantages to the Trust

5.5.1 Scholarship Contribution and Learning Agreements

In some cases staff members will be asked to complete an internal learning agreement and or a staff contribution form which will set out the support the Trust will provide and contribution towards the course by the staff member. Should there be a case where agreements or contribution forms **are not returned** or completed, but the member of staff attends the programme and remains fully participating, the Trust will take this as acceptance under this Workforce Development and Study Leave Policy that both staff and manager accept responsibility of potential recoup of funds by the Trust should they decide to leave the programme or Trust. This will be outlined in the Internal Learning Agreement and or Staff Contribution Form.

Depending on where the funding is allocated, clear information will be given to the applicant on decisions made and allocation amounts awarded. Should funding be allocated through the Scholarship Panel, the panel comprising of POD members, will make a decision on award granted for each applicant. However, if the applicant's support is funded through Workforce Development, Workforce Development will make a decision on how much funding is allocated and communicate this to the applicant. Should applicants or managers dispute decisions made towards allocations, they have a right to contact the Deputy Director of the Service.

5.5.2 Interest Free Loan Support

Permanent staff may access an interest free loan to support their personal contribution if they so wish but must be aware that:

If an employee voluntarily withdraws from a course (including failure to attend) without good reason or voluntarily leaves within 12 months of completing the programme; **the**

Trust will recover any outstanding loan balance which will be taken from their final salary upon leaving the Trust.

If an employee voluntarily leaves the Trust 6 months or less after the course completion,

The Trust will recover **75% or any outstanding loan balance which will be taken from their final salary upon leaving the Trust.**

If an employee voluntarily leaves the Trust more than 6 months but less than 12 months of the course completion, **the Trust will recover 50% or any outstanding loan balance**

which will be taken from their final salary upon leaving the Trust

5.6 Exams, Travel and Accommodation contribution

As previously outlined, the Trust will support learning activities once clear criteria have been met. It is essential that all allocated training budgets contribute towards actual workforce development and educational activities. In line with NHS London reporting requirements, Workforce Development and Study Leave Policy, Version 1.0 March 2013 Page 13 of 16 budgets will not contribute towards travel, exams, books, study materials or accommodation costs. These areas are usually met by the employee.

EXAMINATIONS

Approval for examination leave is at the discretion of the line manager, employees will however be granted paid leave to sit any exams that are mandatory, statutory or essential. Study time for exam preparation may also be granted at the line manager's discretion. In the event of examination failure, re-sits will not normally be funded by the Trust.

UNSATISFACTORY PROGRESS

In the instance of a staff member being unsuccessful in formal examinations or assignments at the first attempt, the Trust will not provide further assistance or protected time off. Discussion with the manager may result in agreed annual leave being taken as an option, should the staff member wish to continue. This approach must be fair and equitable to all staff within the service and subject to service needs.

UNSATISFACTORY LEVEL OF ATTENDANCE

Where individual attendance on a course falls below the minimum days acceptable to the training provider or awarding body; taking into account illness, annual leave, and/or other extenuating circumstances, the employee may be restricted from accessing CPD training for a period of up to one year. In cases where absence from training has not been authorised by the line manager the non-attendance may be addressed under the Trust's disciplinary policy and procedure.

6 TRAINING

STAFF AS TRAINERS, SUPERVISORS AND MENTORS

The Trust recognises the need for strong links between practice and education and will support Partnerships, University and NHS initiatives to support corporate or service improvements. It is acknowledged that there is a large pool of expertise within the Trust's workforce and where possible the Trust will encourage those expert staff to provide training. National Programmes will be promoted and staff encouraged to access further development in „Train the Trainer“ programmes to support corporate priorities and build internal capacity. Supervision and or mentorship to other colleagues will be supported where identified, this further maximises the expertise of our workforce and provides development opportunities for staff. There will be no associated costs for staff involved in these types of opportunities unless stipulated upon recruitment to the course.

6.1 Equality Impact Assessment

The Equality Impact Assessment for this policy is attached in Appendix A.

7 MONITORING COMPLIANCE

The implementation, monitoring and review of this policy will be led by the Deputy Director of Workforce Development & OD; and overseen by the Director of HR & OD, and monitored at POD and PEG. It is recommended that this policy is reviewed as when there are significant changes to both national and local funding arrangements which would inform local policy and procedure.

The Director of Human Resources & OD will ensure that Workforce Development supports the delivery of the Trust's Workforce Plan. The department will provide the necessary infrastructure to monitor central training and education budgets derived from NHS London. Workforce Development manages the Trust-wide training database (OLM) on which all training is recorded to maintain accurate staff records. All departments who manage their own training also have a responsibility to maintain these records and keep them up to date. Where there are service and specialist trainers, engagement with Workforce Development is necessary in order to maintain effective record keeping. The purpose of record keeping is to

monitor attendance and completion at training events and observe the amount of training activity occurring across all staff profiles within the Trust. Mandatory and Statutory refresher training will also be monitored using this database. Data is made available to line managers on a monthly basis and is regularly reviewed at People and Organisational Development (POD), the Professional Education Group (PEG), Health and Safety Committee (HSEC) and Trust Management Group (TMG). Information will also be accessible in cases where the Trust is undergoing any kind of external assessment. Information will be fed into these groups on a bi-monthly or quarterly basis.

8 REFERENCES

This policy must be read in conjunction with:
Grievance Policy
Equality and Diversity Policy
Work Life Balance Policy
Scholarship Guidance

9 ASSOCIATED DOCUMENTATION

None

10 VERSION HISTORY TABLE

Version	Date	Author	Ratified by	Comment/Reason for change
1	March 2013	Courine Stewart	Policy Committee	New

APPENDIX A – EQUALITY IMPACT ASSESSMENT

To be completed and attached to any procedural document when submitted to the appropriate committee for consideration and approval.

Yes/No Comments

1. Does the policy/guidance affect one group less or more favourably than another on the basis of:

Race No

Ethnic origins (including gypsies and travellers)

No

Nationality No

Gender No

Culture No

Religion or belief No

Sexual orientation including lesbian, gay and bisexual people

No

Age No

Disability - learning disabilities, physical disability, sensory impairment and mental health problems

No - Should individuals require support due to Learning Disabilities; additional support can be made available.

- Please contact

Workforce

Development should there be any concerns regarding venue accessibility

2. Is there any evidence that some groups are affected differently?

No

3. If you have identified potential discrimination, are there any exceptions valid, legal and/or justifiable?

N/A

4. Is the impact of the policy/guidance likely to be negative?

No

5. If so can the impact be avoided? N/A

6. What alternative are there to achieving the policy/guidance without the impact?

N/A

7. Can we reduce the impact by taking different action?

N/A

APPENDIX B – CONSULTATION TEMPLATE

1. Procedural Document's Name: Workforce Development and Study Leave Policy

2. Procedural Document Author: Courine Stewart

3. Group/Committee Consulted: POD, JSCC, HR Policy Panel

4. Date of Consultation: 23rd May 2012, Nov 2012, January 2013

5. Comments Received:

To be explicit on Staff – Fixed Term and or Temporary/Bank Worker as well as group to be

named under Scope, Accountabilities and Responsibilities.

Essential – reword support around JD/Person Specification

State name of reference under Booking Procedures rather than section no.

6. Highlight where policy changed following consultation or state reasoning why comments not

incorporated:

Explicit reference to staff group, e.g. fixed term, temporary workers and staff referenced

through document.

Essential Training (pg 5). Change of wording to read "*needed to carry out the role set out in*

the JD/PS should there be a need for update or revision of duties"

Desirable Training (pg 5): additional sentence added "*but it may add value to the service or*

organisation as part of succession planning or career aspirations. If no added value to the

service or organisation can be seen this type of training or development will not be supported

Managers" Must Section (pg 8) Addition ... "Honour study leave arrangements/agreements

including allowing staff to leave work on time to travel to the desired opportunity. If necessary

a mutual local agreement must be entered into in order to avoid any potential disruption or

contradiction of agreement by either parties".

Study Leave Guidance Section (pg 9): Final paragraph added in relation to Study Leave

Allocation.

Bank Staff and Temporary Workers Section - moved to Study Leave and Protected Time

(Pg.9)

Monitoring Compliance Section (pg 16) More comprehensive. Paragraph re-adjusted and

combined between Workforce Department (pg 6) & Monitoring Compliance Section (pg 16)